

DOCTORAL THESIS

SPATIAL AND TEMPORAL DYNAMICS OF ARTHROPOD
COMMUNITIES ON OCEANIC ISLANDS

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on oceanic islands

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TESIS DOCTORAL

La dinámica de las comunidades de artrópodos en islas oceánicas en
el espacio y el tiempo

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Thesis abstract

Oceanic islands have long been viewed as natural laboratories for the study of ecology and evolution, providing a suitable framework to improve our understanding of processes such as colonisation, community structuring and speciation. In the present thesis, by applying a population genetic approach, spider communities within an insular ecosystem across different spatial scales have been studied to understand drivers of species formation and community assembly. Within this thesis it is demonstrated that dispersal limitation is an important driver promoting both geographic structuring of genetic variation within lineages that approximate species-level divergence, and speciation itself. Lineages with limited dispersal ability present higher levels of geographically structured genetic variation than that of lineages with higher dispersal ability. Non-dispersive genera were found to have lower mean node divergences among species, but with similar maximum node divergences when compared to dispersive lineages, and thus higher rates of diversification. A positive significant relationship between the geographic structuring of genetic variation within lineages and diversification rate is also found. Dispersal limitation, together with niche breadth, influences patterns of abundance and occupancy among spider species. It was demonstrated that poor dispersers and non-specialist species were less abundant than good dispersers and specialists at the same level of occupancy. An across-ecosystem study revealed that spatial and temporal environmental heterogeneity are the main drivers of contrasting patterns of spider communities. Additionally, by applying an objective mitochondrial-based classification, high levels of cryptic species have been recovered. Overall, the findings from this thesis highlight the usefulness of spider communities to study non-adaptive processes, and the relevance of dispersal, by applying a dichotomous classification of dispersal ability.

General introduction

Oceanic islands: biogeography and evolution

Charles Darwin's five-year voyage around the world was an important contribution to the onset of island biogeography, largely due to his famous theory of evolution by natural selection postulated after the finches of the Galápagos Islands (Darwin 1859). Since then, insular systems have been viewed as natural laboratories for the study of ecology and evolution (Emerson 2002; Fernández-Palacios *et al.* 2015a; Whittaker *et al.* 2017). Islands are a suitable system for studying evolution due to some geological and ecological characteristics. First, islands present discrete geographical entities with well-defined oceanic boundaries. Therefore, gene flow is likely to be reduced between islands, which offers one explanation for high levels of endemism. Another characteristic that makes islands attractive is their usually small geographic size, which facilitates the cataloguing of island biotas. Finally, their geological dynamism may allow for temporal comparisons among islands, and potentially among different stages within a given island (Emerson 2002; Warren *et al.* 2015).

Islands, defined as a geographical entity surrounded by water, can be classified into three main categories; i) oceanic islands, which have formed over oceanic plates and have never been connected to continental landmasses (e.g., Canary Islands, Hawaii, Madeira, Galápagos, Iceland, Réunion, Mauritius), ii) continental fragments, which are derived from ancient fragments of continental rocks isolated within oceans by plate tectonic processes (e.g., Madagascar, New Caledonia, Sicily, Crete, Cyprus, New Zealand) and iii) continental shelf islands, which were connected to the continent during glaciations, when sea level were significantly lower (e.g., British Isles, Falkland, Sumatra, Sri Lanka, New Guinea) (Whittaker & Fernández-Palacios 2017). Other systems such as islands occurring within freshwater bodies, or discrete patches of habitat surrounded by strongly contrasting habitats, can be also considered as islands. Among them, oceanic islands are typically the most attractive because, as they have never been connected to the mainland or to each other (but see Fernández-Palacios *et al.* 2011; Rijdsdijk *et al.* 2014), most of their endemic biota has evolved *in situ*.

MacArthur & Wilson (1963) put forward the first theory of island biogeography, the ‘Equilibrium Theory of Island Biogeography’ (ETIB). The ETIB states that the number of species present at a given island is a balance between both immigration and extinction rates, which will vary depending upon island area and the distance to the source mainland. Based on this theory, Lomolino (2000) and Heaney (2000) highlighted the importance of speciation as a biogeographic process shaping species richness of a given island. However, the aforementioned contributions consider islands as static entities with constant area, isolation, and as part of a static archipelagic configuration through time. In contrast to this, oceanic islands are geologically dynamic, following a broadly predictable geological trajectory throughout their life cycle. This cycle comprises an initial emergence from the seabed, followed by a period of intense island-building, until reaching maximum area and elevation. Then, after a latency stage, erosional processes reduce volcanic peaks over timescales typically measured in millions of years. Finally, islands erode below the sea surface (Whittaker & Fernández-Palacios 2017). During island ontogeny, several geological processes such as volcanic activity, gravitational landslides, and erosion shape within-island biogeographic boundaries, which can have a major influence as drivers of diversification within island biotas (e.g., Cotoras *et al.* 2018; Cutts *et al.* 2019; García-Olivares *et al.* 2017, 2019; Goodman *et al.* 2019; Macías-Hernández *et al.* 2013; Salces-Castellano *et al.* 2020). The ‘General Dynamic Model’ (GDM) was put forward as a holistic model of island biogeographic pattern that incorporated the aforementioned geological processes (Whittaker *et al.* 2008). The GDM describes the relationship between speciation, immigration, and extinction through time and in relation to island ontogeny. More recently, the ‘Glacial-Sensitive Model’ (GSM) (Fernández-Palacios *et al.* 2015b) includes the effect of glacial cycles, which are known to modify global sea levels and thus, have a major effect on geographical parameters such as island area, isolation, and elevation as well as fusion and fission of islands. Thus, both the GDM and GSM seek to explain biogeographic patterns through processes such as colonisation, establishment, extinction, and speciation, while simultaneously accounting for island ontogeny.

The concept of speciation is strongly linked to the definition of ‘species’, one of the fundamental units of comparison in biology but still under debate among biologists (Wiens 2004). The ‘Biological Species Concept’ (Mayr 1942) is perhaps the most widely used and the one that best facilitates the study of speciation. Under this framework, speciation is viewed as the evolution of reproductive isolation between potentially interbreeding natural populations (De Queiroz 2005; Wiens 2004). Adaptive radiation, defined as the proliferation of species from an initial ancestor to many descendants adapted to use different parts of the environment (Losos & Ricklefs 2009), has been the speciation model that has received more attention in island systems (Cerca *et al.* 2023). However, non-adaptive radiations have received less attention despite being common modes of speciation.

Allopatry, i.e., geographic isolation between species, is one of the most common modes of speciation (Pyron & Burbrink 2010). Allopatry can be considered a type of pre-mating reproductive isolation, as populations are physically reproductively isolated from each other (Wiens 2004). Geographic isolation typically requires the separation of suitable habitats by a barrier of unsuitable habitat. Thus, allopatric speciation can occur either (i) when individuals of a species traverse a barrier and found a new population, i.e., dispersal or (ii) when an ancestral population is fragmented by the appearance of a new barrier, i.e., vicariance (Chesser & Zink 1994; Platnick & Nelson 1978; Zink *et al.* 2000). On islands, dispersal is typically associated with inter-island speciation (e.g., Juan *et al.* 2000; Shaw & Gillespie 2016) whereas vicariance may have a more important role within islands, due to habitat fragmentation driven by processes such as climatic oscillations (e.g., Salces-Castellano *et al.* 2020), lava flows (e.g., Carson & Sato 1969; Vandergast *et al.* 2004) or debris avalanches and flank collapses (e.g., Brown *et al.* 2006; Mairal *et al.* 2015).

Dispersal limitation has been a key driver of diversification across numerous lineages and has evolved repeatedly across diverse taxa and ecosystems (Waters *et al.* 2020). Reductions in dispersal ability are caused by processes that alter selective pressures on dispersal traits and can be causally categorised as either (i) spatial (colonisation of isolated habitat patches) or (ii) ecological (shifts in abiotic and/or biotic conditions that a lineage experiences) (Waters *et al.* 2020). Reduced dispersal ability will facilitate reduced gene flow among habitat patches, thus favouring the geographical structuring of genetic

variation through random mutation and genetic drift (Gavrilets 2014), potentially driving allopatric population differentiation.

Study framework: Canary Islands

Geographic and geologic placement

The Canary Islands are an archipelago of volcanic origin located approximately 100 km off northwest Africa. The archipelago comprises eight major islands (from east to west): La Graciosa, Lanzarote, Fuerteventura, Gran Canaria, Tenerife, La Gomera, La Palma, and El Hierro. The total surface area is approximately 7490 km² and the total extension is around 500 km (Troll & Carracedo 2016a) (Fig. 1). Although the origin of the Canary Islands is controversial and several hypotheses have been proposed (e.g., Anguita & Hernán 1975, 2000; Van Den Bogaard 2013; Burke & Wilson 1972), the most accepted theory (Zaczek *et al.* 2015) supports a hotspot origin where the movement of the African plate over a stationary mantle plume successively generated repetitive and similar island-forming processes. The result is a sequential pattern of decreasing age from east to west: La Graciosa-Lanzarote-Fuerteventura (20.6 Ma), Gran Canaria (14.5 Ma), Tenerife (11.9 Ma), La Gomera (9.4 Ma), La Palma (1.7 Ma) and El Hierro (1.1 Ma) (Zaczek *et al.* 2015). The noteworthy differences in altitude between islands are to a large extent a consequence of differences in the ontogeny of each island (Troll & Carracedo 2016a). The broad age range of the islands contrasts with other oceanic archipelagos, such as Comoros (10.5-0.13; Michon 2016), Marquesas (6-1.3 Ma; Florence & Lorence 1997), Hawaii (5.1-0.4 Ma; Price & Clague 2002), Galápagos (5-0.6 Ma; Geist 1996; White *et al.* 1993), or Mascarenes (2.1-1.5 Ma; Thébaud *et al.* 2009).

Figure 1. Map of the Canary Islands with geological ages following Troll & Carracedo (2016).

Biogeographic placement

The Canary Islands belong to the Macaronesian archipelagos in the Atlantic Ocean, which also comprises the archipelagos of Azores, Madeira, Selvagens and Cape Verde. Although traditionally, due to the high similarity of the Macaronesian floras, these archipelagos were recognised to belong to a same biogeographic unit (e.g., Dansereau 1961; Engler 1879; Takhtajan 1969), recent authors classified the floras of the different archipelagos in different biogeographic regions (e.g., Lobin 1892; Rivas-Martínez 2009). These archipelagos are embedded within the Mediterranean Basin hotspot (Myers *et al.* 2000) and stand out within this hotspot due to their outstanding endemic biodiversity. The Canarian-Madeiran subregion (Madeira, Selvagens and Canary Islands) is the Macaronesian territory with the largest number of endemic species (del Arco-Aguilar & Rodríguez Delgado 2018; Fernández-Palacios 2011). The Canary Islands stand out as the archipelago with the highest number of both species (15,994) and endemics (4,321; 27%) of the Macaronesian archipelagos (Gobierno de Canarias 2023). This is the result of a combination of unique geological and geographical characteristics, including (i) the subtropical location of the archipelago, (ii) the unusual longevity of the older islands due to an absence of post-shield stage subsidence (Carracedo *et al.* 1998), (iii) the high altitude achieved by the central and western islands that gives rise to high habitat diversity, (iv) the influence of the North-East trade winds, locally called ‘alisios’, and (v) their intermediate degree of isolation from both

the African (100 km) and European (1000 km) mainland (Fernández-Palacios & Whittaker 2008). This isolation was even less severe during the last glacial maximum, when previously shallowly submerged seamounts (Palaeo-Macaronesia) were emergent and formed an array of stepping-stones between the present-day islands and the Iberian Peninsula and North Africa (Fernández-Palacios *et al.* 2011). These unique features have placed the Canary Islands as an outstanding model for investigating biogeographical and evolutionary processes and their consequences across island biota (e.g., Albaladejo *et al.* 2021; Caujapé-Castells *et al.* 2022; García-Olivares *et al.* 2019; García-Verdugo *et al.* 2019; Pérez-Delgado *et al.* 2022; Řezáč *et al.* 2021; Salces-Castellano *et al.* 2020).

Habitat diversity

Habitat diversity in the Canary Islands, a relevant feature to be considered when discussing biodiversity patterns, is heavily influenced by climatic conditions, altitude, and orientation. The islands are regularly subject to North-East trade winds, which generate cloud banks on the windward slopes. Above 1,500 m these banks are capped by a warm subsiding layer (del Arco Aguilar *et al.* 2010). This thermal cline results in a specific vegetation structured altitudinally, which is especially remarkable on the windward sides of the central and western islands, where their altitude allows the retention of the cloud layer. This give rise to the following vegetation belts, in order of altitude: (i) *Euphorbia* shrublands, (ii) thermosclerophyllous woodlands, (iii) laurel forests, (iv) pine forests, (v) summit shrublands and (vi) violet community (del Arco-Aguilar & Rodríguez Delgado 2018; del Arco Aguilar *et al.* 2010) (Fig 2). The framework of this thesis is focused on two specific vegetation belts: *Euphorbia* shrublands and laurel forests.

Figure 2. Vegetation belt zones in the Canary Islands, structured according to the altitude and orientation (modified from Juan *et al.* 2000). *Euphorbia* shrublands and laurel forest are highlighted in red and green, respectively.

Euphorbia shrublands (phytocoenotic class *Kleinio nerifoliae-Euphorbietea canariensis*, del Arco-Aguilar & Rodríguez Delgado 2018) (Fig 3a,b) are succulent communities of the lower zone of the islands, from the sea level up to approximately 300m on the windward slopes and up to 600m on the leeward slopes (del Arco-Aguilar & Rodríguez Delgado 2018; del Arco Aguilar *et al.* 2010; Juan *et al.* 2000). This vegetation belt is present on all islands within the Canary archipelago and is characterised by an arid or semiarid climate with little rain (50-300 mm), high temperature (annual average >19°C) and high insolation (del Arco-Aguilar & Rodríguez Delgado 2018). The dominant species belong to the genus *Euphorbia* and are split in two groups based on their habit. The first group, which encompasses candelabriform species (subgenus *Euphorbia*, Riina *et al.* 2013) locally called ‘cardones’, comprises two species, *E. canariensis* (at all islands except Lanzarote) and *E. handiensis* (only in Fuerteventura) (Gobierno de Canarias, 2022). They tend to grow over recent lava flows and rock crevices as well as on ridges, cliffs and, outcrops (del Arco Aguilar *et al.* 2010). The second group comprises dendroid species locally called ‘tabaibas’. The ‘sweet spurge’ (*E. balsamifera*) belongs to the subgenus *Athymalus* and is

present along dry coastal areas of all islands (Riina *et al.* 2021). The ‘bitter spurges’ is a common name applied to several species (*E. atropurpurea*, *E. berthelotii*, *E. bourgeana*, *E. bravoana*, *E. lamarckii* and *E. regis-jubae*) within the subgenus *Esula* (Riina *et al.* 2013). *Euphorbia* shrublands dominated by ‘bitter spurges’, especially *E. lamarckii* and *E. regis-jubae*, are widespread and can even develop within potential areas of thermosclerophyllous woodlands as substitutional stages (del Arco-Aguilar & Rodríguez Delgado 2018). Several other shrub species typical from this vegetation belt are *Argyranthemum spp.*, *Periploca laevigata*, *Kleinia neriifolia*, *Rubia fruticosa* and *Plocama pendula*. Historically, these communities experienced a substantial reduction of their area due to human activities, from prehispanic pastoral and agricultural activities through a recent expansion of urbanism and tourist development (del Arco Aguilar *et al.* 2010).

Euphorbia shrublands are considered to belong to the Rand Flora (del Arco Aguilar *et al.* 2010), i.e., a biogeographic pattern in which distantly related plant lineages share a similar disjunct distribution between the eastern borders of the African continent and adjacent areas such as Macaronesia, northwest Africa, or southern Africa (Pokorny *et al.* 2015). This pattern has been explained by two contrasting hypotheses. The first one implies independent long-distance dispersal events followed by *in situ* speciation (Galley *et al.* 2007; Sanmartín *et al.* 2010). The second hypothesis evokes vicariance processes of a now extinct flora across North and Central Africa due to climatic aridification events (Axelrod & Raven 1978; Bramwell 1985; Marrero *et al.* 1998) as time-calibrated molecular phylogenies places the origin of the disjunction after the onset of aridification in Africa. In fact, some iconic species of the *Euphorbia* shrublands have their sister clades in eastern Africa and are estimated to have diverged during the Mio-Pliocene (7.5-3.5 Ma) (Mairal *et al.* 2017; Sun *et al.* 2016), fitting with the onset of aridity in the Sahara (Schuster *et al.* 2006).

Laurel forests (phytocoenotic class *Pruno hixae-Lauretea novocanariensis*, del Arco-Aguilar & Rodríguez Delgado 2018) (Fig. 3c,d) are arboreal plant formations characteristic of mid-altitudes (350 – 1500) of windward slopes that are highly influenced by an annual presence of trade-wind clouds (del Arco Aguilar *et al.* 2010; Juan *et al.* 2000). The presence of these clouds mitigates hydric stress during summers. This vegetation belt grows in all islands except for Lanzarote and is characterised by a subhumid climate with an annual rainfall regime between 500 and 1200 mm and an average annual temperature between 13 and 18°C (del Arco Aguilar *et al.* 2010). The dominant species are lauriphyllous trees and they can be separated into three main formations; (i) the dry laurel forest (*Visnea mocanerae-Arbutetum canariensis*), which grows at low elevations (350-600 m) and is composed by drought-resistant species such as *Visnea mocanera*, *Picconia excelsa* or *Persea barbujana*, (ii) the humid laurel forest (*Lauro novocanariensis-Perseetum indicae*), which develops under a steadier influence of the clouds (600-1250 m) and species such as *Laurus novocanariensis*, *Ilex canariensis*, and *Persea indica* tend to dominate, and (iii) the cold laurel forest (*Pericallido-Myricetum fayae*), which occurs at altitudes (1250-1500 m) where clouds are absent in summer and where plants are tolerant to cold and dryness, such as *Morella faya* and *Erica arborea* (del Arco-Aguilar & Rodríguez Delgado 2018). The typical substitutional shrubland of the laurel forest, locally called ‘fayal-brezal’ (*Myrico-Ericetum arborea*), is widely extended as a transition to good secondary laurel forest on old, abandoned crops. Deforestation and landscape transformation within the potential territory of the laurel forest has been historically intense and, consequently, the laurel forest currently only occupies 35% of its potential area (del Arco Aguilar *et al.* 2010).

Laurel forests within the Canary Islands have been thought to be a ‘Tertiary relict’ (65-2.6 Ma) due to the resemblance of most species to fossil leaves of laurophyllous species belonging to a vegetation that was widespread in Europe until their extinction by the end of the Pliocene (Fernández-Palacios *et al.* 2011). However, a recent molecular approach (Kondraskov *et al.* 2015) showed that most taxa inhabiting the laurel forest were much younger, dating from the Plio-Pleistocene (5.3-0.01 Ma). Laurel forest species appear to have originated from different source areas, such as the Mediterranean basin (Ferreira *et al.* 2011; García-Verdugo *et al.* 2013; Hileman *et al.* 2001; Rodríguez-Sánchez *et al.* 2018),

the Palaeotropics and the Neotropics (Eriksson & Donoghue 1997; Li *et al.* 2011; Mansion *et al.* 2005; Trofimov & Rohwer 2020).

Figure 3. Examples of *Euphorbia* shrublands (A, B) and laurel forests (C, D).

Arthropods in the Canary Islands

Among the approximately 16,000 species found in the Canary Islands, the phylum Arthropoda is the most speciose group, comprising more than half of the known species within the archipelago (8,126), with 3,212 (39.5%) being endemic (Gobierno de Canarias 2023). The high number of endemic genera is also noteworthy (83), which is particularly high in the order Coleoptera (42), with the latter accounting also for a high proportion of endemic species (58.43%) (Gobierno de Canarias 2023). Higher species richness characterises the central islands, with Tenerife being the island with the highest species richness, with a total of 5,283 species, followed by Gran Canaria with 3,487. The western islands of La Palma and La Gomera harbour 3,010 and 2,507 species, respectively. In the eastern islands, richness is considerably lower, with 1,918 species on Lanzarote and 1,572

on Fuerteventura. The youngest island, El Hierro, is the island with the lowest richness, with a total of 1,451 arthropod species (Gobierno de Canarias 2023).

Due to their high richness and often well-known taxonomy, geographic distributions and habitat affinities, arthropods have become a suitable group for studying ecological, biogeographical and evolutionary pattern and process within the Canary archipelago (e.g., Andújar *et al.* 2022; Astrin & Stüben 2010; Emerson *et al.* 1999; Emerson & Oromí 2005; Hernández-Teixidor *et al.* 2016; Husemann *et al.* 2014; Juan *et al.* 1996; Machado *et al.* 2017; Moya *et al.* 2006; Rees *et al.* 2001; Salces-Castellano *et al.* 2020).

Order Araneae

Biodiversity in the Canary Islands

Currently 510 spider (order Araneae) species inhabit the Canary Islands. Among them, 358 (70%) are endemic. 218 species are SIEs (Single Island Endemic), with the remaining 140 being MIEs (Multiple Island Endemic). 121 species (23%) are native non-endemics, with 37 species restricted to a single island (SINE) and the remaining 84 are found in more than one island (MINE). The remaining 31 species (6%) are considered either introduced or invasive (Gobierno de Canarias 2023). Considering single islands, the maximum species richness is reached in Tenerife (288), followed by Gran Canaria (200) and La Gomera (156). The lowest richness is found at El Hierro, with 89 species. More complete data on species richness per island is found in Table 1. Some genera of particular interest that have experienced notable radiations are *Scotognapha* and *Alopecosa* (13 species), *Walckenaeria* and *Spermophorides* (17 species), *Pholcus* (20 species), *Oecobius* (36 species) and *Dysdera* (47), being the latter the spider taxa most studied within the archipelago (Macías-Hernández *et al.* 2016).

Table 1. Spider species richness at island scale considering the total number of species (Total), natives including endemics (Natives), Multiple Island Endemics (MIE), Multiple Island Native Non-Endemics (MINE), Single Island Endemics (SIE) and Single Island Native Non-Endemics (SINE).

Island	Total	Natives	MIE	MINE	SIE	SINE
El Hierro	99	89	49	30	10	0
La Palma	138	119	61	46	11	1
La Gomera	172	156	79	48	25	4
Tenerife	288	266	101	69	83	13
Gran Canaria	226	200	72	57	61	10
Fuerteventura	114	100	49	33	13	5
Lanzarote	109	97	50	28	15	4

Historically, the spider fauna of the Canary Islands has received relatively little attention. Among the 358 endemic species reported to date, 213 (59%) have been described by a single author; Jörg Wunderlich (Wunderlich 1987, 1991, 1994, 2011), who has recently acknowledged that the spider fauna still needs further study (Wunderlich 2011). Lack of knowledge within the Canary Islands is not only restricted to the Linnean shortfall (i.e., lack of knowledge in taxonomy). The Wallacean shortfall (i.e., lack of knowledge in chorology) still needs to be overcome, as still there are many localities with very few or even without any single reported species (Gobierno de Canarias 2023). Much of the focus of studies to date has been to reconstruct phylogenetic relationships (Arnedo *et al.* 2007; Bidegaray-Batista *et al.* 2007; Dimitrov *et al.* 2008; Dimitrov & Ribera 2007; Macías-Hernández *et al.* 2010, 2013), to understand the patterns of evolution in space and time, with more limited focus on the drivers of speciation (but see Bellvert *et al.* 2023; Řezáč *et al.* 2021; Toft & Macías-Hernández 2021). Among the potential drivers of speciation, it is recognised that dispersal ability is likely to play an important role (Waters *et al.* 2020). Spiders provide a very good focal group to explore the importance of dispersal, with regard to evolutionary process, due to the existence of two divergent dispersal strategies within spiders associated with the possibility of displaying ballooning.

Ballooning

Spiders can disperse over long distances via passive transport in air currents by a mechanism called ‘ballooning’. A silken line released by the individual creates the major component of a drag-induced lift that, combined with a proper meteorology, allows for a passive anemochoria (Bell *et al.* 2005). This behaviour is associated with small species or immature stages and seems to be phylogenetically constrained across the spider tree of life (Bell *et al.* 2005). In the most primitive spider lineage (suborder Mesothelae), ballooning is absent and in the other primitive lineage (suborder Mygalomorphae), there are only few records of ballooning. Within the suborder Araneomorphae, ballooning is quite rare in the clade Haplogynae and more frequently in the clade Entelegynae. This phylogenetically constrained ballooning behaviour has been proposed to be linked to microhabitat requirements, with non-ballooning lineages being typically associated with more specialised narrow niches (e.g., species strongly linked to edaphic or underground environments) that are less susceptible to convective air currents.

Ballooning propensity can be used as a surrogate for dispersal ability. Spider families are usually divided into three mobility groups following the categorisation from Carvalho & Cardoso (2014), according to their different ballooning propensities of catches in ballooning studies (Bell *et al.* 2005; Blandenier 2009; Bonte *et al.* 2003)(Bonte *et al.*, 2003; Bell *et al.*, 2005; Blandenier, 2009). These three categories are: (i) frequent ballooners, (ii) occasional ballooners, and (iii) rare ballooners. Frequently ballooning spiders include the family Linyphiidae, which typically represent more than 50% of the catch within studies that sample ballooning individuals. This exceptional behaviour can be explained due to their ability to disperse throughout their lives (Bell *et al.* 2005). Spider species that occasionally balloon typically represent between 1% and 20% of the catches in ballooning studies and comprise the following families: Araneidae, Lycosidae, Philodromidae, Salticidae, Tetragnathidae, Theridiidae and Thomisidae. Spider species that rarely balloon include the remaining families for which ballooning has never been detected, or they represent less than 1% of individuals within ballooning studies. The fact that confamilial spiders tend to have similar life-history traits, even across different biogeographic regions (Cardoso *et al.* 2011), supports the use of families as a surrogate

even in absence of local data on ballooning studies. In this thesis we have grouped together frequently and occasionally ballooning spiders. Then, the categorisation here proposed is composed by ballooning spiders [frequently and occasionally ballooning in Carvalho & Cardoso (2014)] and non-ballooning spiders [rarely ballooning in Carvalho & Cardoso (2014)]. Ballooning categorisation plays a pivotal role within the context of this thesis and is the basis of the proposed objectives and the development of the following chapters.

Objectives

This thesis focuses on spider communities inhabiting the laurel forests and the *Euphorbia* shrublands of the Canary Islands, both at a regional (archipelago) and local (intra-island) scale, with the general objective of describing the geographical patterns of community structure and understanding the ecological and evolutionary processes that promote them. More specifically, the following objectives are developed through the three chapters of the thesis:

- *Chapter I*: Test for a relationship between geographic structuring of genetic variation and diversification rates and the influence of dispersal limitation.
- *Chapter II*: Assess how dispersal ability and niche breadth influence patterns of abundance and occupancy at different geographical scales (from intra-island to archipelago).
- *Chapter III*: Contribute to the understanding of spatial and temporal environmental heterogeneity leading to community structure across and within different ecosystems.

Chapter I

Dispersal ability and its consequences for population genetic differentiation and diversification

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Abstract

Dispersal ability is known to influence geographic structuring of genetic variation within species, with a direct relationship between low vagility and population genetic structure, which can potentially give rise to allopatric speciation. However, our general understanding of the relationship between dispersal ability, population differentiation and lineage diversification is limited. To address this issue, we sampled mitochondrial DNA variation within lineages of beetles and spiders across the Canary Islands to explore the relationships between dispersal ability, differentiation within lineages and diversification. We found positive relationships between population genetic structure and diversification for both beetles and spiders. Comparisons between dispersive and non-dispersive lineages revealed significant differences for both lineage differentiation and diversification. For both taxa, non-dispersive lineages had stronger population genetic structure. Genus-level endemic species richness and proxies for diversification rate within genera were higher in non-dispersive taxa for both beetles and spiders. Comparisons of average and maximum node divergences within genera suggest that species turnover may be higher in non-dispersive genera. Our results reveal a model where dispersal limitation may shape the diversity of lineages across evolutionary time scales by positively influencing intraspecific and species diversity, moderated by higher extinction rates compared to more dispersive lineages.

Introduction

Dispersal ability, defined as the movement of an individual from its natal site to another breeding site *sensu* Clobert *et al.* (2009), is known to minimise competition and inbreeding, while also allowing individuals to encounter new patches of habitat for resource exploitation (Bowler & Benton 2005). Dispersal ability thus has major effects on individual fitness, population dynamics and species distributions. Dispersal ability also has important consequences for the geographic structuring of genetic variation within species (Waters *et al.* 2020), with a clear link between low vagility and population genetic structure (e.g., Dapporto *et al.* 2019; Dussex *et al.* 2016; Fraser *et al.* 2018; Papadopoulou *et al.* 2009). For a given patchily distributed species, where patches are defined by suitable habitat, high dispersal ability is expected to favour higher rates of gene flow among patches, thus favouring population cohesion. Over an evolutionary timescale this is expected to suppress speciation events and thus clade level diversification (Claramunt *et al.* 2012; Weeks & Claramunt 2014). In contrast, low dispersal ability will favour reduced gene flow among patches, which in turn will favour the geographic structuring of genetic variation among them through random mutation and genetic drift (Gavrilets 2014), potentially driving strong allopatric population differentiation (e.g., Burrridge & Waters 2020; Ortego *et al.* 2021). However, for speciation to be successful, there are three requisites: population splitting, the evolution of reproductive isolation and the persistence of incipient species (Rabosky 2016). Dispersal limitation is expected to positively influence the first two, by promoting population differentiation, but can have both beneficial or detrimental effects on population persistence (Bowler & Benton 2005). Limited dispersal ability may enhance extinction probability by constraining the colonisation of empty habitat patches, or by limiting new recruitment within declining populations (Brown & Kodric-Brown 1977). However, dispersal limitation may also limit net loss from populations, particularly if patches are small and isolated and dispersal vectors are high, such as islands where it has been noted that winds can promote such a dynamic (Leihy & Chown 2020).

Our general understanding of the relationship between dispersal ability, population differentiation and diversification remains limited. In recent years attempts have been made to explore the relationship between population structuring and diversification. Using a dataset comprising a phylogeny of more than 170 species of New World birds, Harvey *et al.* (2017) have revealed population differentiation to be positively related to speciation rate, and suggest that the processes involved in population differentiation are connected to those that promote species diversification. In contrast, an analysis of isolation by distance and population differentiation of 104 Australian lizard species found no evidence for a relationship between population differentiation and species formation (Singhal *et al.* 2018). Similarly, Nitschke *et al.* (2018) found that rates of population differentiation within Australian sea snakes are not positively related to speciation. Both studies suggest that population differentiation is not the rate-limiting step in species formation and that alternative ecological and historical factors are primary determinants of speciation rates. While it is informative to understand dispersal as a factor driving either speciation and/or population differentiation, there is a lack of studies that simultaneously incorporate all three processes. Here we aim to address this using well-characterised arthropod assemblages within an insular oceanic framework.

Recent evidence has been found for a positive relationship between dispersal limitation in beetles and the geographic structuring of genetic variation. Using a standardised sampling approach, Salces-Castellano *et al.* (2021) analysed genetic variation from 214 beetle lineages sampled across a singular cloud forest habitat in an oceanic archipelago setting. This study found that population genetic structure was significantly higher for wingless lineages at both the archipelago and island scales, raising the question of how dispersal ability might further influence diversification. Do the patterns observed by Salces-Castellano *et al.* (2021) translate to a model of higher diversification when individual dispersal ability is limited (e.g., Harvey *et al.* 2017), or a model where dispersal ability and diversification are uncoupled (e.g., Nitschke *et al.* 2018; Singhal *et al.* 2018)? In addition to providing a useful framework to understand the consequences of dispersal ability for population genetic structuring, oceanic archipelago settings can also be leveraged to understand the relationship between dispersal limitation and diversification. *In-situ*

diversification can constitute an important driver for the assembly of oceanic biotas, generating endemic monophyletic clades (Paulay 1994; Warren *et al.* 2015) providing potential to estimate diversification across multiple independent evolutionary lineages within a common sampling framework. Additionally, reduced dispersal ability is frequently associated with insular biotas (e.g., Cody & Overton 1996; Hume & Martill 2019; Kavanagh & Burns 2014; Leihy & Chown 2020; Medeiros & Gillespie 2011), emphasising the role of oceanic archipelagos as exceptional geographic templates to study the evolutionary consequences of dispersal limitation.

Here we take advantage of the same sampling framework employed by Salces-Castellano *et al.* (2021) to explore relationships among dispersal ability, differentiation within species, and diversification, while also extending sampling to spider assemblages. Both arthropod orders are appropriate candidates to explore these relationships because: (i) both harbour a sufficient number of species for a comparative approach, with 317 and 1,314 endemic species in the Canary islands for spiders and beetles, respectively (Biodiversity Data Bank of the Canary Islands, <https://www.biodiversidadcanarias.es/biota/>); (ii) both orders are comparatively well understood taxonomically within the Canary Islands, including a well-established characterisation of species as either endemic or non-endemic within the archipelago, and; (iii) both orders can be partitioned into poor and good dispersers using well-defined traits linked to dispersal potential, i.e., wing development in beetles (Ikeda *et al.* 2012; Salces-Castellano *et al.* 2021a) and ballooning ecology in spiders (Blandenier 2009; Bonte *et al.* 2003; Carvalho & Cardoso 2014).

We first test if the geographical structuring of genetic variation within spiders, both between and within islands, is higher for non-dispersive species. To achieve this, we use the same spatial setting previously used to assess geographic structuring of genetic variation within beetles, and a comparable definition of lineages of maternal dispersal history (LMDH) (Salces-Castellano *et al.* 2021a), by applying a conservative maximum intraspecific divergence threshold for spiders (Emerson *et al.* 2017). Linear regressions between geographical structuring within LMDHs and species number within genera are performed for both orders, to test for a relationship between dispersal ability and diversification at the island scale. Finally, within each order, we add publicly available

sequence data to analyse variation among endemic species within genera to test if dispersal ability is associated with diversification at the archipelago scale, comparing endemic species richness, mean node divergence, and maximum node divergence and diversification rate per genus between dispersive and non-dispersive LMDHs. We predict that: (i) similar to beetles, non-dispersive spider LMDHs will present higher levels of population differentiation; (ii) dispersal limitation will lead to higher diversification, through higher net diversification rates in both orders and; (iii) geographic structuring of genetic variation will be directly correlated with diversification rate within genera.

Materials and methods

Field sampling

A total of 31 sites of 50 x 50 metres were sampled within laurel forests across the four western islands of the Canary archipelago: Tenerife (14), La Gomera (7), La Palma (6) and El Hierro (4) (figure 1). In each site, a standardised protocol combining passive sampling (pitfall traps) and active sampling techniques (foliage beating, vegetation sweeping, active searching and leaf litter-sifting) was applied (see Emerson *et al.* (2017) for further details). Sampling was carried out from 2012 to 2020 between the months of November to May. Samples were preserved in absolute ethanol at -20°C until further examination. Six sites (two in each of Tenerife, La Palma and El Hierro) were not included in Salces-Castellano *et al.* (2021), and thus for comparative purposes, they were also sampled for their beetle fauna, sequenced and processed, as described in Salces-Castellano *et al.* (2021).

Figure 1. Sampling sites within the laurel forests of the Canary Islands. Sampling sites are labelled with three letter codes (see supplementary material, table S1 for further details).

Mitochondrial DNA sequencing

Samples were classified into parataxonomic units (PU) by direct examination of external morphology under a binocular lens. Up to four individuals per PU per site were selected for DNA extraction and sequencing. Depending upon the specimen size, a single leg, several legs or prosome were digested using a Chelex protocol (Casquet *et al.* 2012). The 5' region (658 bp) of the mtDNA COI gene was amplified using the LCO1490 and HCO2198 primers (Folmer *et al.* 1994). PCR reaction conditions were as follows: initial denaturation at 94°C for 2 min, followed by 40 cycles of 94°C for 30 s, 42-46°C for 35 s, and 72°C for 45 s, and a final extension of 72°C for 5 min. 1-2 µL of diluted (1/10) DNA extract was amplified with 24-23 µL of PCR mix (for a total volume of 25 µL), comprised of 14.4 µL of water, 2.5 µL of 10x NH₄ buffer (Bioline), 1.5 µL of 50 mM MgCl₂ (Bioline), 2 µL of 2.5 mM dNTPs (Bioline), 0.5 µL of BSA (20 mg/ml), 1 µL of each primer (10 µM), and 0.1 µL of Taq polymerase (BIOTAQ). PCR products were sequenced using the Sanger DNA

sequencing service of Macrogen (www.macrogen.com) with either the forward or reverse primer, or both primers in the event of insufficient read length from a single primer. Sequences were then edited in Geneious version 2021.1.1 (www.geneious.com).

Mitochondrial DNA lineage delimitation for the estimation of dispersal history

To harmonise data with that of Salces-Castellano *et al.* (2021), we adopted their approach by defining lineages of maternal dispersal history (LMDH), that minimise the probability of a given biological species being assigned to more than one LMDH, while simultaneously providing a similar time frame for comparisons among lineages. While mtDNA substitution rate variation may be expected across different spider lineages (Wheeler *et al.* 2017), there is no evidence that these should correlate with species dispersal ability. A custom R script (Salces-Castellano *et al.* 2021a) was used to produce an unweighted pair group method with arithmetic mean (UPGMA) tree from pairwise K2P distances using an alignment of all sequences from all PUs. A conservative maximum intraspecific divergence threshold of 6.8% was used, above which it is unlikely for individuals from the same biological species to be assigned to more than one spider LMDH (Emerson *et al.* 2017; Robinson *et al.* 2009). LMDHs may thus represent different stages of the speciation process, from single panmictic species, through to geographically structured species, incipient species, and species complexes, and ultimately different taxonomic species, which may or may not be taxonomically diagnosable. Each LMDH was taxonomically assigned to species or genus level and categorised for dispersal ability. The potential for juvenile spider stages to be passively dispersed by air currents, while suspended from silk threads, henceforth referred to as 'ballooning', was considered a proxy for dispersal ability (Blandenier 2009; Bonte *et al.* 2003). LMDHs were categorised as either ballooning or non-ballooning following a family level classification established by Carvalho & Cardoso (2014).

Geographic structuring of genetic variation at the LMDH level

To test for genetic structure within LMDHs, two indices of fixation were generated: G_{ST} (genetic distance among haplotypes is unweighted) and N_{ST} (genetic distance among haplotypes is weighted). LMDHs sampled from a minimum of two populations and comprising more than three individuals were selected to estimate G_{ST} and N_{ST} , both within individual islands (considering each sampling site as a population) and among islands (considering each island as a population) using SPAGeDi 1.5 (Hardy & Vekemans 2002).

Diversification proxies at the genus level

The mean number of endemic species within genera at the archipelago scale was compared between dispersive and non-dispersive lineages. Data on endemic species richness per genus were extracted from the Biodiversity Data Bank of the Canary Islands (<https://www.biodiversidadcanarias.es/biota/>). For phylogenetic measures, genus-level alignments were generated using single sequences from each species sampled in this study, and additional sequences available on BOLD or GenBank. For beetles, in addition to the region sequenced by Salces-Castellano *et al.* (2021), we also generated alignments for the barcode region. Thus, two alignment regions were used, COIa (the 658 bp barcode region) for spiders and beetles, and COIb (a non-overlapping downstream region of 735 bp) for beetles.

Endemic species richness and measures of phylogenetic divergence were used to derive proxies for diversification at the genus level. Specifically, we used (i) endemic species number within each genus and (ii) endemic species number divided by maximum node divergence within a genus as a proxy measure of diversification rate, corresponding to age-richness rate estimators (ARR). We also explored the average node divergence within genera (the average of the individual divergences estimates associated with each node) and the maximum node divergence within genera (a proxy for the crown age) to explore the temporal context of lineage diversification. There are recognised theoretical issues associated with the use of ARR estimators (Rabosky & Benson 2021), however, these should be less consequential when comparing across groups of independently sampled

lineages, for which all speciation events are relatively close to the present. We sought to minimise overestimating diversification rates by subdividing non-monophyletic genera within the archipelago (i.e., species are derived from more than one colonisation event) into alignments corresponding to each colonisation event. Also, if a given genus comprised more than one subgenus with mainland relatives, subgenera were similarly analysed independently.

Mean and maximum node divergences were estimated independently for each alignment using two different tree-based approaches, UPGMA with uncorrected p-distances and bayesian estimation. For UPGMA trees, node divergences were estimated using the function 'tree.age' from the package dispRity (Guillerme 2018). Node divergences from Bayesian trees were estimated with BEAST v. 2.6.4. (Bouckaert *et al.* 2014), applying (i) a Kimura-2-Parameter substitution model for each alignment, (ii) a relaxed lognormal molecular clock, (iii) a birth-death tree prior, and (iv) a normal prior distribution representing the 95% confidence interval around specific rates of 0.0125 (\pm 0.0036) for mtDNA COIa in spiders (Bidegaray-Batista & Arnedo 2011), 0.0168 (\pm 0.0018) and 0.0177 (\pm 0.0019) for COIa and COIb respectively in Polyphaga (Papadopoulou *et al.* 2010), and 0.0113 (\pm 0.0034) and 0.0145 (\pm 0.0054) for COIa and COIb respectively in Adephaga (Andújar *et al.* 2012). MCMC analyses were run for 100,000,000 steps, sampling every 1000 steps, with the first 25% discarded as burnin, using values of effective sample size (ESS) greater than 200 as a minimum for acceptance. Both approaches were run independently for each genus-level alignment.

Relationship among dispersal ability, genetic differentiation, and diversification

To test for a relationship between genetic structuring and diversification across all dispersive and non-dispersive lineages within each order, Spearman rank correlation tests (cor.test function, stats R package) were applied to compare mean G_{ST} and N_{ST} indexes for all the species within a genus, with the corresponding endemic species richness, both within individual islands (island scale) and among islands (archipelago scale). To test for a relationship between dispersal ability and the geographic structuring of genetic variation at

both archipelago and island scales, fixation indices were compared between dispersive and non-dispersive lineages, for both spiders and beetles, using Wilcoxon rank-sum tests in R v. 4.0.4 (`wilcox.test` function, stats R package). At the island scale, a linear mixed-effect model was constructed using the `lmer` function (lme4 package) (Bates *et al.* 2015), implementing ' N_{ST} ' as the response variable and 'dispersal ability' as the predictor variable, and including 'island' as a random intercept as well as a random slope. Conditional modes of the random effects, i.e., differences between intercept and slope for each island and the overall intercept and slope, were extracted using the `ranef` function (lme4 package) (Bates *et al.* 2015). Finally, to test for a relationship between dispersal ability and genus level diversification, species number, mean node divergence, maximum node divergence and diversification rate were compared between dispersive and non-dispersive lineages using Wilcoxon rank-sum tests. Additionally, to take into account potential non-independence of transitions from the dispersive to non-dispersive state, a phylogenetic least squares (PGLS) analysis was conducted using the `gls` function (nlme package) (Pinheiro & Bates 2006). Neighbour-joining phylogenetic trees were generated using all available COIa and COIb sequences for spiders and beetles respectively, and then pruned to contain one species per genus.

Results

Field sampling and DNA sequencing

A total of 21,082 spider individuals were collected and classified into 148 PUs, from which 3,338 individuals were selected for sequencing, yielding a total of 2,663 sequences, representing a sequencing success rate of 79.7%. Across the six sites newly sampled for their beetle fauna, a total of 4,266 specimens were collected, from which 1,817 were selected for sequencing, yielding a total of 1,594 sequences, representing a sequencing success rate of 87.7%. Incorporating beetle data from Salces-Castellano *et al.* (2021) yielded a total of 333 LMDH, 214 for beetles and 119 for spiders. Within spiders, 55 lineages (46.2%) were classified as having limited dispersal ability (i.e., non-ballooner),

with the remaining 64 having high dispersal ability (i.e., ballooner). Within beetles, 110 lineages (51.4%) were classified as having limited dispersal ability (i.e., wingless), with the remaining 104 classified as having high dispersal ability (i.e., winged). At the island scale, the total number of LMDHs recovered were 234 for Tenerife (80 spider and 154 beetle), 168 for La Gomera (62 spider and 106 beetle), 150 for La Palma (49 spider and 101 beetle) and 111 for El Hierro (45 spider and 66 beetle). Among these, fixation indices could be calculated for 100 LMDHs in Tenerife (33 spider and 67 beetle), 65 LMDHs in La Gomera (28 spider and 37 beetle), 49 LMDHs in La Palma (21 spider and 28 beetle) and 33 LMDHs in El Hierro (14 spider and 19 beetle). LMDHs may include more than one taxonomic species, particularly within evolutionary lineages that have experienced recent speciation. Across both orders there were only 42 cases (3 spider and 39 beetle) from a total of 333 where a LMDH comprised more than one taxonomic species. Thirty of the 42 cases comprised two taxonomic species occurring on different islands.

Dispersal limitation and population genetic differentiation

Linear mixed-effects models using N_{ST} showed statistically significant differences between dispersive and non-dispersive beetles ($p = 0.02$) but not between dispersive and non-dispersive spiders ($p = 0.13$). For spiders, conditional modes of the random effect in El Hierro and La Palma were lower than the general model (El Hierro: intercept = -0.05, slope = -0.13; La Palma: intercept = -0.03, slope = -0.07) while in La Gomera and Tenerife they were higher (La Gomera: intercept = 0.01, slope = 0.15; Tenerife: intercept = 0.07, slope = 0.19). For beetles, conditional modes of the random effect in El Hierro and La Gomera were lower than the general model (El Hierro: intercept = -0.01, slope = -0.003; La Gomera: intercept = -0.08, slope = -0.02) while in La Palma and Tenerife they were higher (La Palma: intercept = 0.02, slope = 0.01; Tenerife: intercept = 0.06, slope = 0.02). Wilcoxon rank-sum tests revealed that there was no significant difference between dispersive and non-dispersive lineages, neither for spiders ($p = 0.27$, $n = 44$) nor beetles ($p = 0.11$, $n = 66$), when comparing N_{ST} at the scale of the entire archipelago. At the scale of individual islands, significant differences were found between dispersive and non-

dispersive beetle lineages on the islands of Tenerife ($p = 0.003$, $n = 68$), La Gomera ($p = 0.0004$, $n = 37$) and La Palma ($p = 0.03$, $n = 29$), and between dispersive and non-dispersive spider lineages on the islands of Tenerife ($p = 0.004$, $n = 33$) and La Gomera ($p = 0.002$, $n = 28$). Results for both N_{ST} and G_{ST} are presented in Figure 2

Figure 2. Fixation indices for non-dispersive (dark grey) and dispersive (light grey) lineages. (a) G_{ST} and (b) N_{ST} for spider lineages. (c) G_{ST} and (d) N_{ST} for beetle lineages. AR = archipelago, TF = Tenerife, LG = La Gomera, LP = La Palma, and EH = El Hierro. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, ns = not significant.

Geographic structuring of genetic variation and diversification

For N_{ST} at the archipelago scale, all analyses for both orders revealed a positive relationship (supplementary material, figure S1). Significant relationships were found for the combined analysis of all dispersive and non-dispersive spider genera ($n = 31$, $p = 0.0006$), as well as non-dispersive genera alone ($n = 13$, $p = 0.03$), while the relationship was not significant

for dispersive genera ($n = 18$, $p = 0.24$). For beetle genera, no significant relationships were found for any of the three analyses. Analyses using G_{ST} followed a similar positive trend, with a significant relationship found for the combined analysis of all dispersive and non-dispersive spider genera ($n = 31$, $p = 0.006$), while the relationship for non-dispersive genera alone was only marginally significant ($n = 13$, $p = 0.07$) and for dispersive genera it was not significant ($n = 18$, $p = 0.51$) (supplementary material, figure S2). At the scale of individual islands, significant relationships were found for spiders within Tenerife for the combined analysis of all dispersive and non-dispersive genera ($n = 23$, $p = 0.002$) as well as individually (dispersive, $n = 13$, $p = 0.02$; non-dispersive, $n = 10$, $p = 0.09$) (supplementary material, figure S3). Significant relationships were found in La Gomera for non-dispersive spider genera ($n = 7$, $p = 0.02$) (supplementary material, figure S4). Significant relationships were also found in La Palma for dispersive spider genera ($n = 10$, $p = 0.02$) (supplementary material, figure S5). Although there was a tendency toward a positive relationship for beetle genera at the scale of individual islands, no relationships were significant (supplementary material, figure S3-6). Relationships between G_{ST} and species richness within islands were similar to those found with N_{ST} (supplementary material, figures S7-10).

Dispersal limitation and genus level diversification

While all spider genera could be successfully characterised for their dispersal ability, a lack of robust information on the presence or absence of wings for many beetle genera meant that only 335 of the 416 genera (80.5%) were assigned to a dispersal category. Wilcoxon rank-sum tests analyses revealed that species richness within spider genera was not significantly different between dispersive ($n = 92$, mean richness = 2.35) and non-dispersive ($n = 76$, mean richness = 4.38) genera ($p = 0.41$). In contrast, species richness was significantly different ($p = 0.0007$) between dispersive ($n = 198$, mean richness = 2.93) and non-dispersive ($n = 137$, mean richness = 5.65) beetle genera (figure 3). The beetle comparison was repeated removing an outlier (genus *Laparocerus*, richness = 173), with the difference remaining significant ($p = 0.001$). The results also remained significant when accounting for potential phylogenetic covariance. For the PGLS analyses, a total of 519 sequences were retrieved (195 for spiders and 304 for beetles) belonging to 167 genera (62

spider and 105 beetle). Analyses revealed that species richness was significantly different ($p = 0.04$) between dispersive and non-dispersive beetle genera while for between dispersive and non-dispersive spider genera the difference was non-significant ($p = 0.20$).

Figure 3. Violin plot of species number per genera for non-dispersive (dark grey) and dispersive (light grey) lineages for spiders (a) and beetles (b). Plot width represents the relative number of genera with a given species richness. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, ns = not significant. For aesthetic purposes, an outlier wingless beetle genus (*Laparocerus*) with 173 species was omitted.

For diversification analyses, only genera that could be assigned to a dispersive category, and that comprised two or more species with DNA sequence data were considered. Thus, UPGMA and Bayesian gene trees were estimated for a total of 655 species (153 spider and 502 beetle) from 99 genera (29 spiders and 70 beetles, supplementary material, table S2). Taking into account the total number of endemic species across the archipelago for both orders (317 spider and 1,314 beetle) and total number of genera comprising two or more endemic species (47 spider and 198 beetle), the percentage of representation for species richness was 40% (48% for spiders and 38% for beetles) while for number of genera was 41% (62% for spiders and 35% for beetles). Analyses using node divergences estimated from UPGMA and Bayesian trees yielded similar results, with only minor differences between them. We present results derived from Bayesian trees (figure 4), with results from UPGMA trees presented in the supplementary material (figure S11). Non-dispersive beetle genera were found to have significantly higher diversification rates compared to dispersive genera ($p = 0.01$). Similarly, mean diversification rate for non-dispersive spider genera was higher than that of dispersive genera, but the difference was

not significant ($p = 0.37$). Mean node divergences were significantly younger in non-dispersive beetle genera, compared to dispersive genera ($p = 0.02$). While the difference between dispersive and non-dispersive spider genera trended in the same direction, the difference was not significant ($p = 0.98$). There were no significant differences for maximum node divergence between dispersive and non-dispersive genera in either order (spiders, $p = 0.60$; beetles, $p = 0.42$).

Figure 4. Box plot of mean and maximum node divergences, estimated using BEAST, and diversification rate estimates for non-dispersive (dark grey) and dispersive (light grey) lineages. (a) Mean node divergences within spider genera. (b) Maximum node divergences within spider genera. (c) Proxy for diversification rate within spider genera, normalised from 0-1. (d) Mean node divergences within beetle genera. (e) Maximum node divergences within beetle genera. (f) Proxy for diversification rate within beetle genera, normalised from 0-1. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, ns = not significant.

Discussion

Dispersal limitation as a driver of population differentiation and diversification

Positive linear relationships were found between differentiation and diversification both at archipelago and island scales (supplementary material, figures S1-10), being significant for spiders but not for beetles. Within the latter, there are many data points with relatively high N_{ST} , but with richness value close to 1, which is particularly apparent for wingless beetles genera. This points to the presence of genera with few species, but where species experience high geographic structuring of genetic variation. Why this genetic structuring is not reflected in higher species richness could be related to either (i) high extinction rates within these genera, or (ii) a recent origin of such genera within the archipelago. Overall, the positive relationships observed contrast with the findings of Singhal *et al.* (2018) and Nitschke *et al.* (2018), but are consistent with Harvey *et al.* (2017). However, none of these previous studies incorporate the role of dispersal limitation in their models. Dispersal limitation can lead to the limited or complete absence of gene flow among populations over evolutionary timescales, providing conditions that should favour geographic structuring of genetic variation within species, and eventually speciation. Consistent with this, we find that population genetic structure in spiders and in beetles tends to be higher in non-dispersive lineages, at both archipelago and island scales, in line with similar findings from Salces-Castellano *et al.* (2021). Linear mixed models revealed a significant tendency for beetles but not for spiders. Thus, the relationship between population genetic structure and dispersal ability for spiders is not general to all islands, potentially reflecting influences of differing island sizes and ages.

For both taxa, N_{ST} boxplots (figure 2) reveal an apparent stronger effect of dispersal limitation within islands than among them. While differences were not statistically significant at the archipelago scale, strong statistical differences were found at the within island scale, particularly on older islands. This suggests that the evolutionary consequences of dispersal ability are scale dependent, with species of differing dispersal ability being affected more similarly as the spatial scale of a dispersal barrier increases. However, this

interpretation should be taken with caution as (i) each island-scale dataset contains a different set of species, (ii) the archipelago scale data set is reduced to include only species occurring on more than one island, and (iii) due to the low number of non-dispersive species shared across more than one island, the comparison between dispersive categories may be unbalanced. If geographic structuring were to be influenced by those LMDH comprising more than one taxonomic species, we would expect an effect at the archipelago scale, as non-dispersive lineages tend to have more endemic species restricted to one island than dispersive ones. As N_{ST} at the within-island scale is calculated using only genetic data within the island, there is limited impact for bias resulting from LMDH that include more than one species.

As well as exhibiting similar trends for dispersal ability and geographic structuring of genetic variation, both taxa presented similar trends for the relationship between dispersal ability and diversification. Among beetles, the number of species in a genus is significantly higher for non-dispersive compared to dispersive genera (figure 3), and diversification rates are also significantly higher in non-dispersive genera (figure 4). Estimates for the average mean node divergence were also significantly younger within non-dispersive beetle genera compared to dispersive genera, but with no significant difference between both groups for the maximum node divergence (figure 4). This pattern is suggestive of a model where speciation and extinction rate are both typically higher in non-dispersive genera, but more so for speciation rate, contributing to both higher species richness and species turnover compared to dispersive genera. However, as we did not account for the relative impact of extinction rate in our analysis, this interpretation should be treated with caution. Our results are consistent with Ikeda *et al.* (2012), who found that flightless beetle lineages had higher speciation rates than flighted ones, thus placing dispersal limitation as a driver of species richness. In response to (Ikeda *et al.* 2012), Vogler & Timmermans (2012) suggested that loss of flight may be an indirect response to different habitat conditions, thus obviating its role as the driving agent of speciation. By explicitly sampling species from the same habitat and geographical setting, our results strengthen the argument for dispersal limitation's primary role in population differentiation and species formation.

For spiders, results point to similar trends as found for beetles, but there were no significant differences among dispersive and non-dispersive genera for species richness, mean node divergence or diversification rate (figure 4). These results, while pointing to a common model between both groups, suggest that dispersal limitation, as estimated by the absence of ballooning ecology in spiders, is less consequential as a pathway to diversification than the absence of wings in beetles. Immature beetle stages are typically immobile and often hidden within soil or plant tissue, and are thus unlikely to be dispersed by wind. In contrast, immature spiders are much more mobile, and can be found on leaf surfaces, thus facilitating passive dispersal by wind, even in the case of non-dispersive species. However, we cannot rule out that misclassification of species-specific ballooning ecologies may contribute to a lack of relationship between dispersal ability and diversification in spiders. In contrast to beetles, where dispersal categorisation is made by direct species examination, ballooning categorisation is taxonomically inferred at the family level (Cardoso *et al.* 2011). Island taxa often experience niche shifts compared to their mainland relatives, including loss of dispersal power (Whittaker *et al.* 2017). Although confamilial spider species tend to have similar life histories (Cardoso *et al.* 2011), we cannot rule out that some species categorised *a priori* as good dispersers may have lost their ability to disperse by ballooning.

Analytical challenges for extrapolating from differentiation to diversification

Singhal *et al.* (2018) have put forward several factors that they suggest may bias analyses of diversification and differentiation, including species delimitation, errors in estimating diversification rate and inappropriate phylogenetic scale. Regarding species delimitation, spiders and beetles are among the more well-studied and understood arthropod groups within the Canary Islands, having been the subject of substantial taxonomic effort over the last two centuries. Thus, the issue of bias in species delimitation is unlikely to be consequential for the estimation of species richness per genera. For diversification rates, using lineages based on an objective genetic divergence threshold instead of species minimises potential errors associated with taxonomic biases. Errors associated with the

estimation of diversification rates may also confound results. The estimation of diversification rates, and its decomposition to speciation and extinction, is increasingly recognised as complex, both for age-richness rate estimates and estimates derived from phylogenetic trees (e.g., Louca & Pennell 2020; Rabosky & Benson 2021). Rather than seeking to understand diversification within individual lineages, we instead compare age-richness rate and phylogeny derived inferences for speciation and diversification rates between large groups of independent genera. However, it remains possible that issues described by Louca & Pennell (2020) and Rabosky & Benson (2021) may weaken the power of our analyses to detect differences.

In the absence of published phylogenies for the great majority of genera, we estimated node divergences among those species for which phylogenetic data was available. Although incomplete sampling may bias node divergence values (Chang *et al.* 2020), it is not unreasonable to assume that any such bias should be equally distributed between dispersive and non-dispersive genera. Another potential source of error is the assumption that all endemic species within a genus are monophyletic. Although the most common pattern within the Canary archipelago is single colonisation and diversification *in situ* within genera (Juan *et al.* 2000), there are examples of multiple colonisations within the same genus (e.g., Arnedo *et al.* 2001; Emerson *et al.* 2000; Jordal & Hewitt 2004). We have taken account of this by using subgenus affiliation with the continent to partition genera when necessary. Additionally, when a published phylogeny revealed more than one colonisation event within a genus, we partitioned the data accordingly. By adopting these measures, we limit the potential for overestimating MRCA node divergences.

Finally, Singhal *et al.* (2018) suggest that the phylogenetic scale may affect the power to detect relationships between population differentiation and diversification, with broader phylogenetic scales having greater power to detect weaker relationships. Both Singhal *et al.* (2018) and Nitschke *et al.* (2018) focused on single clades of skinks and sea snakes respectively, at subfamily level, and found no evidence for a relationship. In contrast, Harvey *et al.* (2017), recovered a significant relationship between genetic structure and speciation rate at a broader phylogenetic scale comprising a complete phylogeny of Neotropical birds. While our phylogenetic analyses are below the genus level, and thus

more recent than that of Harvey *et al.* (2017), the power issue raised by Singhal *et al.* (2018) is likely to be compensated for by our comparative analytical framework.

Conclusions

Overall, our results are consistent with a model where population differentiation and diversification are positively associated, which has previously been suggested for New World birds (Harvey *et al.* 2017). Our results also point to dispersal limitation as a key factor in both population differentiation and diversification rate. We have found dispersal limitation to be associated with both higher population differentiation and higher diversification rate. Patterns within beetles also suggest that species turnover (species extinction and replacement) may be higher in non-dispersive genera. This argues for higher diversification rates in non-dispersive genera not simply being driven by a higher speciation rate, but also moderated by higher extinction rates than dispersive genera. This is consistent with Brown & Kodric-Brown (1977), who suggest that species that disperse poorly are more prone to extinction than dispersive species as, in the latter, local population extinctions can be buffered by dispersers moving into declining populations. Further research is needed to understand how dispersal ability and population turnover through time interact to lead to species formation. However, our results point to a potentially general model where dispersal limitation leads to higher geographic structuring of genetic variation within species, but where diversification rate depends upon both dispersal ability and extinction rate.

Supplementary material

- Figure S1. Linear regression between species richness and N_{ST} at the archipelago scale.
- Figure S2. Linear regression between species richness and G_{ST} at the archipelago scale.
- Figure S3. Linear regression between species richness and N_{ST} for the island of Tenerife.
- Figure S4. Linear regression between species richness and N_{ST} for the island of La Gomera.
- Figure S5. Linear regression between species richness and N_{ST} for the island of La Palma.
- Figure S6. Linear regression between species richness and N_{ST} for the island of El Hierro.
- Figure S7. Linear regression between species richness and G_{ST} for the island of Tenerife.
- Figure S8. Linear regression between species richness and G_{ST} for the island of La Gomera.
- Figure S9. Linear regression between species richness and G_{ST} for the island of La Palma.
- Figure S10. Linear regression between species richness and G_{ST} for the island of El Hierro.
- Figure S11. Box plot of mean and maximum node divergences estimated using UPGMA, and diversification rate estimates for spiders and beetles.
- Table S1. Sampling sites and coordinates.
- Table S2. Genera and the number of species for which sequences were available for the speciation analyses.

Figure S1. Linear regression between species richness and N_{ST} at the archipelago scale. (a) Ballooning and non-ballooning spiders. (b) Ballooning spiders. (c) Non-ballooning spiders. (d) Winged and wingless beetles. (e) Winged beetles. (f) Wingless beetles.

Figure S2. Linear regression between species richness and G_{ST} at the archipelago scale. (a) Ballooning and non-ballooning spiders. (b) Ballooning spiders. (c) Non-ballooning spiders. (d) Winged and wingless beetles. (e) Winged beetles. (f) Wingless beetles.

Figure S3. Linear regression between species richness and N_{ST} for the island of Tenerife. (a) Ballooning and non-ballooning spiders. (b) Ballooning spiders. (c) Non-ballooning spiders. (d) Winged and wingless beetles. (e) Winged beetles. (f) Wingless beetles.

Figure S4. Linear regression between species richness and N_{ST} for the island of La Gomera. (a) Ballooning and non-ballooning spiders. (b) Ballooning spiders. (c) Non-ballooning spiders. (d) Winged and wingless beetles. (e) Winged beetles. (f) Wingless beetles.

Figure S5. Linear regression between species richness and N_{ST} for the island of La Palma. (a) Ballooning and non-ballooning spiders. (b) Ballooning spiders. (c) Non-ballooning spiders. (d) Winged and wingless beetles. (e) Winged beetles. (f) Wingless beetles.

Figure S6. Linear regression between species richness and N_{ST} for the island of El Hierro. (a) Ballooning and non-ballooning spiders. (b) Ballooning spiders. (c) Non-ballooning spiders. (d) Winged and wingless beetles. (e) Winged beetles. (f) Wingless beetles.

Figure S7. Linear regression between species richness and G_{ST} for the island of Tenerife. (a) Ballooning and non-ballooning spiders. (b) Ballooning spiders. (c) Non-ballooning spiders. (d) Winged and wingless beetles. (e) Winged beetles. (f) Wingless beetles.

Figure S8. Linear regression between species richness and G_{ST} for the island of La Gomera. (a) Ballooning and non-ballooning spiders. (b) Ballooning spiders. (c) Non-ballooning spiders. (d) Winged and wingless beetles. (e) Winged beetles. (f) Wingless beetles.

Figure S9. Linear regression between species richness and G_{ST} for the island of La Palma. (a) Ballooning and non-ballooning spiders. (b) Ballooning spiders. (c) Non-ballooning spiders. (d) Winged and wingless beetles. (e) Winged beetles. (f) Wingless beetles.

Figure S10. Linear regression between species richness and G_{ST} for the island of El Hierro. (a) Ballooning and non-ballooning spiders. (b) Ballooning spiders. (c) Non-ballooning spiders. (d) Winged and wingless beetles. (e) Winged beetles. (f) Wingless beetles.

Figure S11. Box plot of mean and maximum node divergences estimated using UPGMA, and diversification rate estimates for non-dispersive (dark grey) and dispersive (light grey) genera of spiders and beetles. (a) Mean node divergences within spider genera. (b) Maximum node divergences within spider genera. (c) Proxy for diversification rate within spider genera, normalised from 0-1. (d) Mean node divergences within beetle genera. (e) Maximum node divergences within beetle genera. (f) Proxy for diversification rate within beetle genera, normalised from 0-1. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, ns = not significant.

Table S1. Sampling sites and coordinates.

Site code	Site name	Island	Latitude	Longitude
AGU	Monte Aguirre	Tenerife	28.5334	-16.2698
ANE	Aguas Negras	Tenerife	28.54	-16.2251
CHI	Chinobre	Tenerife	28.559	-16.1736
CTE	Cabezo Tejo	Tenerife	28.562	-16.1714
IJU	Hoya de Ijuana	Tenerife	28.5602	-16.1692
MOQ	El Moquinal	Tenerife	28.5368	-16.3088
NIE	Barranco Nieto	Tenerife	28.5341	-16.3163
PIJ	Pijaral	Tenerife	28.552	-16.1892
TAG	Vueltas de Taganana	Tenerife	28.5443	-16.226
ZAP	Zapata	Tenerife	28.5355	-16.2962
COC	Barranco Cochinos	Tenerife	28.3228	-16.8234
PAS	Barranco Los Pasos	Tenerife	28.3349	-16.8316
AGA	Agua García	Tenerife	28.4579	-16.4041
PBL	Palo Blanco	Tenerife	28.3573	-16.5874
CUB	Cubo de La Galga	La Palma	28.7664	-17.7703
CUM	Hilera de la Cumbre	La Palma	28.6304	-17.8267
LOM	Camino del Lomito	La Palma	28.8038	-17.8203
NIQ	Niquiomo	La Palma	28.6003	-17.8103
TAB	El Tablado	La Palma	28.8184	-17.8833
MAG	Barranco de Magdalena	La Palma	28.8109	-17.9079
ACE	Los Acebiños	La Gomera	28.141	-17.2225
APA	Apartacaminos	La Gomera	28.154	-17.3008
CED	El Cedro	La Gomera	28.124	-17.224
EHA	Encima de Las Hayas	La Gomera	28.1355	-17.2773
FUE	Fuensanta	La Gomera	28.1453	-17.2522
MEV	Meseta de Vallehermoso	La Gomera	28.1539	-17.2934
REV	Reventón Oscuro	La Gomera	28.1221	-17.2138
FAY	El Fayal	El Hierro	27.7322	-17.9949
HDC	Hoya del Creal	El Hierro	27.806	-17.949
MEN	Mencáfete	El Hierro	27.7363	-18.0735
PDR	Pedraje	El Hierro	27.7338	-18.0231

Table S2. Genera and the number of species for which sequences were available for the speciation analyses.

Genus	Order	Dispersive category	Richness	Species with sequences	Percentage of representation
<i>Agelena</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	4	2	50
<i>Apostenus</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	4	2	50
<i>Drassodes</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	4	4	100
<i>Dysdera</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	46	46	100
<i>Haplodrassus</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	2	2	100
<i>Loxosceles</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	6	6	100
<i>Macarophaeus</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	3	2	66.67
<i>Nomisia</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	4	2	50
<i>Oecobius</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	37	8	21.62
<i>Olios</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	3	3	100
<i>Palpimanus</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	2	2	100
<i>Pholcus</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	20	18	90
<i>Scotognapha</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	13	3	23.07
<i>Scytodes</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	2	2	100
<i>Setaphis</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	2	2	100
<i>Spermophorides</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	17	5	29.41
<i>Zelotes</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	3	3	100
<i>Zimirina</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	7	3	42.85
<i>Zoropsis</i>	Araneae	Non-dispersive	6	6	100
<i>Alopecosa</i>	Araneae	Dispersive	13	4	30.76
<i>Episinus</i>	Araneae	Dispersive	2	2	100
<i>Improphantes</i>	Araneae	Dispersive	2	2	100
<i>Lasaeola</i>	Araneae	Dispersive	4	2	50
<i>Minicia</i>	Araneae	Dispersive	4	4	100
<i>Palliduphantes</i>	Araneae	Dispersive	4	2	50
<i>Pulchellodromus</i>	Araneae	Dispersive	3	3	100
<i>Tenuiphantes</i>	Araneae	Dispersive	4	2	50
<i>Walckenaeria</i>	Araneae	Dispersive	17	5	29.41

Genus	Order	Dispersive category	Richness	Species with sequences	Percentage of representation
<i>Xysticus</i>	Araneae	Dispersive	8	4	50
<i>Acalles</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	3	3	100
<i>Atomaria</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	6	3	50
<i>Calacalles</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	18	15	83.33
<i>Calathidius</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	3	2	66.67
<i>Calathus (Lauricalathus)</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	13	13	100
<i>Calathus (Trichocalathus)</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	5	5	100
<i>Coptostethus</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	43	3	6.97
<i>Cymindis</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	7	3	42.85
<i>Dendroacalles</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	6	6	100
<i>Dicrodontus</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	3	2	66.67
<i>Echinodera</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	14	12	85.71
<i>Euplectus</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	9	3	33.33
<i>Eutrichopus</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	3	2	66.67
<i>Geomitopsis</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	3	3	100
<i>Hegeter</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	21	16	76.19
<i>Herpisticus</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	20	20	100
<i>Heterotemna</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	3	2	66.67
<i>Laparocerus</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	173	162	93.64
<i>Licinopsis</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	6	2	33.33
<i>Lycoperdina</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	4	3	75
<i>Metophthalmus</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	6	6	100
<i>Metopsia</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	8	2	25
<i>Moreiba</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	6	6	100
<i>Nesacinopus</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	6	2	33.33
<i>Nesotes</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	19	12	63.15
<i>Onyxacalles</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	3	3	100
<i>Othius</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	8	3	37.5
<i>Paradromius</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	10	5	50
<i>Paraeutrichopus</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	2	2	100

Genus	Order	Dispersive category	Richness	Species with sequences	Percentage of representation
<i>Philorhizus</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	11	6	54.54
<i>Pimelia</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	9	6	66.67
<i>Pselactus</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	7	7	100
<i>Pseudodichromacalles</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	3	2	66.67
<i>Silvacalles</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	10	9	90
<i>Stenichmus</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	8	5	62.5
<i>Tarphius</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	31	24	77.41
<i>Torneuma</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	9	4	44.44
<i>Xestus</i>	Coleoptera	Non-dispersive	2	2	100
<i>Acmaeodera</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	6	2	33.33
<i>Agabus</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	3	2	66.67
<i>Anaspis</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	4	4	100
<i>Aphanarthrum</i> (lineage 1)	Coleoptera	Dispersive	13	11	84.61
<i>Aphanarthrum</i> (lineage 2)	Coleoptera	Dispersive	3	3	100
<i>Attalus</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	52	4	7.69
<i>Auletobius</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	4	4	100
<i>Aulonothroscus</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	6	6	100
<i>Canariclerus</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	2	2	100
<i>Ceutorhynchus</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	5	2	40
<i>Cis</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	3	3	100
<i>Cryptocephalus</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	4	4	100
<i>Dasytes</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	7	2	28.57
<i>Deroplia</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	10	4	40
<i>Hesperorrhynchus</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	4	3	75
<i>Leiodes</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	2	2	100
<i>Leipaspis</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	3	3	100
<i>Liparthrum</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	8	8	100
<i>Longitarsus</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	11	2	18.18
<i>Malthinus</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	11	3	27.27
<i>Megarthus</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	3	2	66.67

Genus	Order	Dispersive category	Richness	Species with sequences	Percentage of representation
<i>Meladema</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	2	2	100
<i>Mesites</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	5	2	40
<i>Micrambe</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	4	4	100
<i>Mogulones</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	3	2	66.67
<i>Ocypus</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	8	3	37.5
<i>Olisthopus</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	3	2	66.67
<i>Psylliodes</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	6	2	33.33
<i>Rhopalomesites</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	3	3	100
<i>Scymnus</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	4	4	100
<i>Taeniapion</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	2	2	100
<i>Trechus</i>	Coleoptera	Dispersive	16	14	87.5
			Total = 987	Total = 655	Mean = 66.36

Chapter II

Dispersal ability and niche breadth influence interspecific variation in spider abundance and occupancy

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Abstract

The relationship between species local abundance and their regional distribution (occupancy) is one of the most extensively recognised and investigated patterns in ecology. While exceptions exist, the generally held model is that locally abundant species also tend to be more widespread geographically. However, there is only a limited understanding of both the mechanisms driving this relationship, and their scale dependency. Here we use occupancy and abundance data for 123 species of spider from across the Canary Islands to understand how both dispersal ability and niche breadth might mediate variation among species for local abundance and occupancy. We test the predictions that (i) dispersal ability explains variation among species for both abundance and occupancy, and (ii) species with a higher degree of habitat specialisation, reflecting more limited niche breadth, will have both higher occupancy and abundance. We find no evidence within habitat patches for an effect of dispersal ability on either local abundance or site occupancy, while across all patches species with higher dispersal ability tend to occupy more sites. Species largely restricted to laurel forests have higher abundance than species with broader niche breadth, but similar occupancy. The study revealed that dispersal ability and niche breadth were significant predictors of the abundance-occupancy relationship, highlighting the importance of both factors for understating patterns of abundance and occupancy among spider species.

Introduction

Since its original theoretical development based on multi-taxon evidence (Brown 1984), the relationship between species local population densities (abundance) and their regional distribution (occupancy), i.e., the ‘abundance-occupancy relationship’ (AOR), has been one of the most extensively recognised and investigated patterns in ecology (Blackburn *et al.* 2006; Gaston *et al.* 1997, 2000). Both variables are positively related, with widespread species typically being more locally abundant, while species with more limited distributions are typically found at lower abundance. Occupancy can be measured as the distance/area between the outermost limits to a species occurrence (i.e., the extent of occurrence), or the area over which a species is found (i.e., area of occurrence) (Gaston 1991). The latter will tend to be smaller as species do not occupy all areas within the geographic limits to their occurrence (Gaston 1994). The distinction between those measures is important as it has been shown that the extent of occurrence usually reports no correlation with abundance (Blackburn *et al.* 2006). Regarding abundance, in local scale analyses, it can be measured directly using site population counts. However, local abundance can also be estimated by dividing the total population size of a given domain by the number of occupied sites within that domain. The latter measure may give rise to a number of issues addressed summarised by Borregaard & Rahbek (2010). Attempts have been made to disentangle the factors that may explain the AOR relationship, with Gaston *et al.* (1997) suggesting up to eight mechanisms may drive this positive relationship, with none of them being necessarily mutually exclusive or even independent. The first two mechanisms are due to statistical artefacts, i.e., sampling bias (insufficient sampling effort leads to a systematic underestimation of the range sizes of species with lower local densities) and phylogenetic non-independence (due to phylogenetic relatedness, species do not constitute independent data points, thus inflating degree of freedom for testing statistical significance) (Gaston *et al.* 1997). The remaining six are essentially biological and can be grouped in three categories: range position, resource, and population dynamic explanations (Gaston *et al.* 2000). All six mechanisms have been evaluated and have gained some support, thus leading to a model where a positive AOR may result from the action of

several mechanisms, with varying importance depending upon the system (Holt *et al.* 2002). However, particular emphasis has been placed on the potential role of species dispersal ability and niche breadth as factors shaping AORs.

From a neutral perspective, species that have a high dispersal ability are more prone to be widespread (Gaston 1994 and references therein) as individuals are more able to colonise favourable habitat patches for resource exploitation. Although there are theoretical predictions that suggest that dispersal ability should be an important predictor of relative abundance (Borregaard & Rahbek 2010; Gaston & Blackburn 2003; Holt *et al.* 2002; Kunin & Gaston 1993; Law *et al.* 2003; Rabinowitz & Rapp 1981; Shmida & Ellner 1984), Levine & Murrell (2003) have suggested that even though dispersal ability influences the rate of arrival, other factors such as competition or geographical habitat variation may be more important in controlling relative abundance patterns. Thus, differences in dispersal ability have been a central focus in recent AOR studies, and Freckleton *et al.* (2005) have developed a model incorporating colonisation and dispersal within patchy landscapes to explore AOR. Within this model, both the strength and the shape of the AOR are affected by the ability of species to disperse between habitat patches. For taxa with low dispersal ability, AORs are predicted to be absent while for species with moderate dispersal ability, regional populations are predicted to exhibit classic metapopulation dynamics. Empirical tests of this model using marine macroinvertebrates have demonstrated that, for a given population size, more dispersive taxa exhibit greater regional occupancy, resulting in less aggregated distributions at a local scale (Foggo *et al.* 2007; Sahara *et al.* 2016).

With regard to the role of niche as an explanatory variable for the AOR, two hypotheses have been proposed. The ‘niche breadth’ hypothesis (Brown 1984) posits that species with broader environmental tolerances (generalists) are able to use a wider variety of resources and will thus be locally more abundant and spatially widespread. However, the ‘niche position’ hypothesis (Hanski *et al.* 1993), which has received much empirical support (Fried *et al.* 2021; Hanski *et al.* 1993; Heino & de Mendoza 2016), asserts that species that are able to efficiently exploit the most common environmental conditions within a given habitat (i.e., specialised to a dominant habitat) will be the most both locally abundant and widespread than generalist species. The niche position hypothesis can be seen

as analogous to the ‘jack-of-all-trades is master of none’ (MacArthur 1984) within the context of a particular habitat.

Although factors shaping abundance and occurrence within a given assemblage have been broadly addressed, their interplay with spatial scale has given considerably less attention. He & Gaston (2000) first studied how the AOR curve changes at different spatial grains using a dataset of tree species in a tropical rainforest, showing that curve-fitting is more linear when the spatial grain is lower. More recently, Steenweg *et al.* (2018) revealed that curve-fitting is not only affected by spatial grain (size of the grid cells that are used to discretize continuous space), but also the sampling unit (areal vs. point sampling). If occupancy is measured at broader sampling units, then the AOR is unaffected by spatial grain, whilst at narrower sampling units, the AOR follows the pattern described by He & Gaston (2000). Empirically, Gaston *et al.* (2006) tested the fit of the AOR of soil and canopy arthropod assemblages at three different scales within an oceanic archipelago framework: a small reserve, the island of Terceira, and all the seven islands in the Azorean archipelago. A positive AOR was found at all three scales, but with no further explanation for the potential drivers of this pattern, and to date there is still limited data to explore the drivers of abundance and occupancy at different scales.

Through the implementation of a standardised field sampling and molecular identification protocol to characterise laurel forest spider assemblages within the archipelago setting of the Canary Islands, we explore the influence of both dispersal ability and niche breadth on local abundance and occupancy patterns at two different spatial scales, within and among habitat patches. Our sampling framework comprises laurel forest habitat patches (islands) that have never been connected, thus providing a natural dispersal filter among patches. We sample across 31 laurel forest sites within four habitat patches to test the hypothesis that dispersal ability explains variation in abundance and occupancy among species, wherein good dispersers are both more abundant and more widespread. We also evaluate the influence of niche breadth on both abundance and occupancy. More specifically, we hypothesise that species more specialised to laurel forest conditions will be both more abundant, and more widespread, across habitat patches. Both hypotheses are tested at the island and archipelago scales.

Material and methods

Field sampling

A total of 31 sites measuring 50 x 50 metres were sampled within laurel forest habitat across the four western islands of the Canary archipelago: Tenerife (14), La Gomera (7), La Palma (6) and El Hierro (4) (figure 1; supplementary material, table S1). Sampling was restricted to these islands as the remaining islands in the archipelago have only limited or no laurel forest extension (del Arco Aguilar *et al.* 2010). Within each site, a standardised field sampling and sample processing protocol was applied (Emerson *et al.* 2017), encompassing 16 hours of active sampling (foliage beating, vegetation sweeping and active searching) together with 48 pitfall traps that were set for 14 days, and extraction from leaf litter using Berlese apparatus. This combination of techniques facilitates the collection of species that are highly mobile as well as those that are either less mobile or typically hidden. Sampling was carried out from 2012 to 2020 between the months of November and May. Samples collected in the field were preserved in absolute ethanol at -20°C until further examination.

Figure 1. Sampling sites within the laurel forests of the Canary Islands. Sampling sites are labelled with three letter codes (see supplementary material, table S1 for further details).

Mitochondrial DNA sequencing for species delimitation

Spatially explicit quantification of local arthropod species richness and diversity can be particularly challenging, frequently complicated by the lack of or incomplete regional species lists, limited taxonomic expertise, and potential cryptic diversity (Andújar *et al.* 2017; Cicconardi *et al.* 2013; Pérez-Delgado *et al.* 2022). In response to this taxonomic impediment, the protocol of Emerson *et al.* (2017), which combines parataxonomy with molecular identification, was followed. Spider specimens were classified into parataxonomic units (PU) by direct examination of external morphology under a binocular lens. As in Salces-Castellano *et al.* (2020), we defined two types of PU within each plot: (i) type I are confidently recognised in other plots (e.g., genus is monospecific or with straightforward taxonomy), and (ii) type II are distinct within the focal plot but difficult to cross reference with other plots (e.g., genera with complex or poorly understood

taxonomy). PUs were named numerically, with type II PUs denoted with the addition of an “x” to the numerical code. Up to four individuals per PU per site were selected for DNA extraction and sequencing. Depending upon specimen size, a single leg, several legs or prosome were digested using a Chelex protocol (Casquet *et al.* 2012). The 5' region (658 bp) of the mtDNA COI gene was amplified using the primers LCO1490 and HCO2198 (Folmer *et al.* 1994). PCR reaction conditions were as follows: initial denaturation at 94°C for 2 min, followed by 40 cycles of 94°C for 30 s, 42-46°C for 35 s, and 72°C for 45 s, and a final extension of 72°C for 5 min. 1-2 µl of diluted (1/10) DNA extract was amplified with 24-23 µl of PCR mix (for a total volume of 25 µl), comprised of 14.4 µl of water, 2.5 µl of 10x NH₄ buffer (Bioline), 1.5 µl of 50 mM MgCl₂ (Bioline), 2 µl of 2.5 mM dNTPs (Bioline), 0.5 µl of BSA (20 mg/ml), 1 µl of each primer (10 µM), and 0.1 µl of Taq polymerase (BIOTAQ). PCR products were purified using Exonuclease I and rAPid Alkaline Phosphatase and then sequenced using the Sanger DNA sequencing service of Macrogen (www.macrogen.com) with either the forward or reverse primer, or both primers in the event of insufficient read length from a single one. Sequences were then edited in Geneious version 2021.1.1 (Kearse *et al.* 2012). To identify presumed biological species (PBS) (Emerson *et al.* 2017), a custom R script [Salces-Castellano *et al.* (2021), <https://github.com/asalcescastellano/Divergence-threshold>], was used to produce an unweighted pair group method with arithmetic mean (UPGMA) tree from pairwise K2P distances, using an alignment of all sequences from all PUs. This script first implements a conservative maximum intraspecific divergence threshold of 6.8% (Robinson *et al.* 2009) to create individual alignments. Under this divergence threshold, it is assumed that all individuals of a given biological species will be represented within a single lineage, but that a given lineage may comprise more than one biological species. The script then generates a table summarising: (i) the PU composition within each lineage; (ii) for each PU within a lineage, the proportion of individuals from that PU included within the lineage, and (iii) when a lineage comprises individuals from more than one PU, the presence or absence of monophyly among individuals from the same PU. Lineages exclusively comprising all individuals within a given PU were inferred to represent a single PBS. Individuals from PUs that segregated across more than one lineage were revised to evaluate potential PU assignment error or possible laboratory contamination, with the removal of any sequences

ascribed to the latter. When two or more PUs segregated within the same lineage, individuals were revised morphologically, and in the absence of any differences (as might be expected among type II PUs - see above) the lineage was inferred to represent a single PBS. For lineages comprising two or more morphologically distinct PUs, and where PUs were phylogenetically structured within the lineage, PUs were inferred to represent different PBS. Morphologically distinct PUs that showed no clear segregation with regard to mtDNA variation were inferred to represent recent speciation with incomplete lineage sorting and/or gene flow, and were removed for subsequent analyses. PBS were then taxonomically assigned to species or genus level based on GenBank and BOLD Systems search results, together with additional information and dichotomous keys from Arnedo *et al.* (1996) for *Dysdera* Latreille, 1804; Bosmans *et al.* (2017) for *Clubiona* Latreille, 1804; Dimitrov & Ribera (2007) for *Pholcus* Walckenaer, 1805; Lissner (2017) for *Rhomphaea* L. Koch, 1872; Muster *et al.* (2007) for *Pulchellodromus* Wunderlich, 2012; and Wunderlich (1987, 1991, 1994, 2011) for the remaining genera. This process of identification was further supported with reference to the arachnological collection of the Department of Animal Biology, University of La Laguna, Canary Islands, Spain (coll. DZUL) and that of the Island Ecology and Evolution Group (GEEI) of the Instituto de Productos Naturales y Agrobiología (IPNA-CSIC), Tenerife, Canary Islands, Spain (coll. GEEI).

PBS abundances were extrapolated from PU sequencing results to unsequenced PU individuals. Within a given PU, if all sequenced individuals were assigned to a single PBS, then all unsequenced individuals for the PU were assigned to that PBS. If individuals from a given PU were assigned to more than one PBS, then within each site the proportion of each PBS (within the PU) was estimated (from sequenced specimens) and unsequenced individuals were assigned to each PBS within each site accordingly. As a hypothetical example, if 10 individuals sequenced from a given PU within a given site are assigned to different PBS (e.g., three specimens assigned to PBS001 and seven to PBS002), then, unsequenced individuals are assigned following the same proportions (e.g., 30% to PBS001 and 70% to PBS002). If the result yields a decimal number, then it is rounded to an integer. PBS (hereafter species) were categorised for dispersal ability, considering the potential for juvenile stages to be passively dispersed by air currents, while suspended from silk threads,

henceforth referred to as 'ballooning', which has been broadly used as a proxy for dispersal ability (Blandenier 2009; Bonte *et al.* 2003; Suárez *et al.* 2022). Species were categorised as either ballooning or non-ballooning following a family-level classification established by Carvalho & Cardoso (2014). We adopt the concept of 'niche breadth' as a proxy for the Grinnellian realised niche, i.e., variability in environmental conditions recorded where a species occurs (Clavero & Brotons 2010). A two-step process was used to categorise species as either 'non-specialist' or 'specialist', based on their affinity to the laurel forest habitat, i.e., whether they are present in a broad range of habitats or restricted mainly to laurel forest. As a first step, the species list was assessed by five Canary Island spider specialists (Miquel Arnedo [University of Barcelona], Jørgen Lissner [Aarhus University], Pedro Oromí [University of La Laguna] and the authors DS and NM), to categorise species as either laurel forest specialists or non-specialists based on their knowledge of the biology of the species. Only species that were categorised by at least two experts were considered in this step. When all experts consensually categorised a given species, then that category was assigned. In the absence of a consensus, the majority proposed category was assigned. In the absence of a majority opinion, the given species was assigned a category in the subsequent step. In a second step, species association to the laurel forest was quantified using distribution records within the Biodiversity Data Bank of the Canary Islands (<https://www.biodiversidadcanarias.es/biota/>). The total number of 500 x 500 m cells occupied by a species in the archipelago was quantified and the percentage of those cells corresponding with laurel forest habitat was then calculated. For the subset of species that were categorised by the panel of experts as laurel forest specialists, species were ranked from highest to lowest percent laurel forest occupancy, and the percentage corresponding to the 50% quantile was used for the categorisation of the species non-characterised in the first step (i.e., above this percentage species were considered as 'specialists', whereas below it, species were categorised as 'non-specialist'). Additionally, 10%, 25% and 75% quantiles were also used for niche breadth categorisation to explore the robustness of further inferences. Finally, further analyses were also performed using only the subset of species that were unambiguously categorised in the step one (panel of experts).

Abundance and occupancy analyses

For each species, local abundance was calculated as (i) mean site abundance (i.e., the sum of all individuals divided by the number of occupied sites at both island and archipelago scales, with species being the replicate unit), and (ii) individual site abundance (i.e., the sum of all individuals within each site, with site being the replicate unit). Occupancy was calculated both across islands (i.e., presence or absence of each species within each of the islands) and across sites (i.e., presence or absence of each species within each site). The latter was again calculated both at the archipelago (across all sites) and at the island (across all sites within a given island) scales. Species richness was compared between dispersive and non-dispersive species, as well as between non-specialist and specialist species, using a generalised linear mixed model (glmer function, lme4 package; Bates *et al.* 2015), implementing island as a nesting factor. Abundance and occupancy were compared between dispersive and non-dispersive species, as well as between non-specialist and specialist species, using both mean site abundance and individual site abundances. When using mean site abundance, generalised linear models were implemented in R v. 4.0.4 (glm function, stats package), first with mean site abundance as the response variable, occupancy as a covariable and a Gaussian error structure, and second, with occupancy as the response variable, mean site abundance as covariable and a binomial error structure. When using individual site abundances, generalised linear mixed models (glmer function, lme4 package; Bates *et al.* 2015) were implemented, first with individual site abundance as the response variable, occupancy as a covariate, island as a nesting factor of abundance and a Poisson error structure, and second, with occupancy as the response variable, individual site abundance as a covariate, island as a nesting factor of abundance and a binomial error structure. AORs (abundance-occupancy relationships) were expressed as a logistic regression between the occupancy and the log of the abundance per species (mean site abundance per species). To examine the effect of both dispersal ability and niche breadth on AORs, a generalised linear model was constructed (glm function, stats R package), considering occupancy as the response variable and following a binomial error structure. As predictor variables, the log of the abundance (mean site abundance) and either dispersal ability or niche breadth, as well as their interaction, were considered. The best model was

selected based on AIC criteria (aictab function, AICcmodavg package (Mazerolle 2020)). Additionally, four generalised linear models were constructed after subsetting the data by dispersal ability (ballooning and non-ballooning) and niche breadth (specialist and non-specialist) to calculate slope, intercept, and McFadden R^2 of the models for each species category. Models were performed across all islands, and within each island individually. A chi-squared test was used to test for potential association between dispersal ability and niche breadth (chisq.test function, stats R package).

Phylogenetic analyses of non-independence for abundance and occupancy

As both abundance and occupancy patterns may be influenced by shared common ancestry among species within a given assemblage (Gaston *et al.* 1997), we test for phylogenetic non-independence using Blomberg's K statistic, a measure of the strength of phylogenetic signal of a given trait (Blomberg *et al.* 2003). Values of $K = 1$ or greater imply that variation in the species trait being tested follows expectations under a Brownian motion model of evolution along a candidate tree, suggesting strong phylogenetic signal and thus phylogenetic dependence for the trait. Contrary to this, lower values for K imply phylogenetic independence of a given trait. A phylogeny was constructed using a backbone matrix comprising 4570 sequences for 1450 species retrieved from Macías-Hernández *et al.* (2020), which includes (i) the concatenated gene matrix of Wheeler *et al.* (2017), (ii) sequences bioinformatically extracted from the original transcriptome data in Fernández *et al.* (2018), and (iii) COI and 28S sequences from species of the Iberian Peninsula, Madeira and Azores. Additionally, a local matrix comprising COI and 28S concatenated sequences for each species in this study was added to the backbone matrix. A region of the 28S rRNA gene was amplified using the primers 28S-O and 28S-B (Hedin & Maddison 2001; Whiting *et al.* 1997), using conditions described in Macías-Hernández *et al.* (2020). The phylogenetic tree was inferred using maximum likelihood implemented in the program RAxML-HPC2, remotely run on XSEDE at the CIPRES Science Gateway (www.phylo.org), with the topology of Fernández *et al.* (2018) used as a constraint. The concatenated matrix was partitioned by gene, and an unlinked GTR+CAT substitution

model was assigned to each gene. The resulting phylogeny was made ultrametric (congruify.phylo function, geiger R package) (Harmon *et al.* 2008), and the dated phylogeny of Fernández *et al.* (2018) was used as a reference to provide fixed calibration points to date the target phylogeny using the program treePL (Smith & O’Meara 2012). The tree was then pruned (prune.sample function, picante R package) (Kembel *et al.* 2010) to include only species present in the local community (123 species). Blomberg’s K was then calculated for both species abundance and occupancy at archipelago scale, using the function ‘Kcalc’ in the ‘picante’ R package (Kembel *et al.* 2010).

Results

Field sampling, DNA sequencing, dispersal and niche classification

A total of 21,082 spider individuals were collected and classified into 148 PUs (no type II PU were recovered, i.e., all PU could be cross referenced among plots based on taxonomy), from which 3,338 individuals were selected for sequencing, yielding a total of 2,663 sequences, representing a sequencing success rate of 79.7%. Implementing an intraspecific divergence threshold of 6.8% (Robinson *et al.* 2009) yielded 119 lineages from which 123 species were inferred. 120 of the 148 PUs correspond to a single PBS and the assignment of unsequenced individuals to PBS was unambiguous. For the remaining 18 PUs assigned to more than one PBS, unsequenced individuals per plot were assigned to a PBS following the proportion estimated for the corresponding plot using sequenced specimens. Four lineages yielded more than one species: (i) *Agyneta rurestris* (C. L. Koch, 1836) and *Agyneta fuscipalpa* (C. L. Koch, 1836); (ii) *Walckenaeria alba* Wunderlich, 1987 and *Walckenaeria afur* Thaler, 1984; (i) *Pholcus gomeræ* Wunderlich, 1980 and *Pholcus sveni* Wunderlich, 1987; (iv) *Walckenaeria gomerensis* Wunderlich, 1987 and *Walckenaeria cf. hierropalma* Wunderlich, 1987. Sixty species (49%) were classified as having limited dispersal ability (i.e., non-ballooner), with the remaining 56 having high dispersal ability (i.e., ballooner). Regarding niche breadth, the panel of experts (step 1) were able to classify a total of 77 species (63 % of the total) as being either specialist or non-specialist, being 60 of them

consensually classified. For the 30 species classified as specialist species in step 1, the percentage of occupied cells corresponding with Q50 was 86.7%. Percentages of occupied cells for the other quantiles were Q10 = 62.8%; Q25 = 75%; Q75 = 100%. After the classification of species in step 2 using the 86.7% threshold (Q50), a total of 99 (80%) species were categorised, a total of 63 species (51%) were classified as non-specialist, and 36 species (29%) as specialist. The remaining 24 species (19%) could not be categorised for niche breadth either because: (i) they were identified only to genus level, or (ii) they belong to potentially undescribed species whose distributions are unknown. Among the 63 non-specialist species, 37 (59%) were ballooners and 26 (41%) non-ballooners, while among the 36 specialist species, 20 (55%) were ballooners and 16 (45%) non-ballooners (see supplementary material, table S2 for further details).

Richness, occupancy, and abundance

Regarding phylogenetic signals of abundance and occupancy, Blomberg's K values for both abundance (K = 0.274) and occupancy (K = 0.289) were less than one, suggesting that neither are phylogenetically constrained. A Chi-squared test did not provide evidence for association between dispersal ability and niche breadth (X-squared = 0.05, df = 1, p-value = 0.83). Across all sites, species richness is significantly higher for ballooning species compared to non-ballooning species ($p < 0.001$, figure 2a). There was no significant difference ($p = 0.09$) for local species abundance using mean site abundance at the archipelago scale when comparing between ballooning and non-ballooning species (figure 2b, supplementary material, table S3). Comparing between ballooning and non-ballooning species, abundances were also not significantly different at the scale of individual islands ($p > 0.05$ in all cases) (supplementary material, figure S1a-d). In contrast, analyses using site-level abundance data (i.e., values of abundance per species, where n = the number of occupied sites), resulted in significantly higher abundance for ballooning ($p < 0.001$), at both the archipelago and island scale (supplementary material, figure S2 a-e). Occupancy at both archipelago and island scales were recovered as significant predictors ($p < 0.001$) of abundance (supplementary material, table S3) using both measures of abundance. There

was, however, a significant occupancy difference between the two dispersal categories when accounting for mean abundance as a covariate, with ballooning species inhabiting more islands ($p = 0.002$) and more sites across the archipelago ($p = 0.03$), compared to non-ballooning species (figure 2c,d). At the scale of individual islands, there were no significant differences in site occupancy (number of sites) between ballooning and non-ballooning species for any of the islands ($p > 0.05$ in all cases) (supplementary material, figure S3a-d). When accounting for site-level abundance as a covariate, there were no significant differences in the proportion of site occupancy between ballooning and non-ballooning species at the archipelago scale ($p = 0.13$) (supplementary material, table S3). However, for all islands there was a significant difference ($p < 0.001$), with ballooning species occurring at a higher number of sites (supplementary material, figure S4 a-e).

Regarding niche breadth, the results were similar across all measures of niche breadth categorisation. Hereafter, we only refer to the Q50 threshold while the remaining results are found in Supplementary Material (supplementary material, table S3, S4). Across all sites, species richness is significantly higher for specialist species compared to non-specialist species ($p < 0.001$, figure 2e). Specialist species were significantly more locally abundant (using both mean site abundance and site count data) than non-specialist species across the archipelago ($p < 0.001$) (figure 2f, supplementary material figure S2f). At the scale of individual islands, specialist species were also significantly more abundant than non-specialist species ($p < 0.05$ in all cases) except for El Hierro using mean abundance data (supplementary material, figure S1g-j, S2g-j). When accounting for mean abundance as a covariate, there were significant differences between specialist and non-specialist species with regard to the proportion of islands occupied ($p = 0.03$) (figure 2g), as well as the proportion of all sites at the archipelago scale ($p < 0.001$) (figure 2h). Within islands, there were no significant differences in site occupancy between specialist and non-specialist species ($p > 0.05$ in all cases) (supplementary material, figure S3g-j). When accounting for site-level abundance as a covariate, there was a significant difference between specialist and non-specialist species at the archipelago scale ($p < 0.001$) as well as in the island of La Palma ($p < 0.001$) (supplementary material, figure S4 f,h,i), with abundance being higher in non-specialists. In Tenerife, La Gomera and El Hierro there were

no significant differences ($p > 0.05$; supplementary material, figure S4 g,j). Both mean and site-level abundance were always recovered as significant predictors of occupancy for both the dispersal and niche comparison ($p < 0.001$; supplementary material, table S3).

Figure 2. Box plots showing archipelago-scale differences for species richness (a,e), mean site abundance (mean number of individuals per site) (b,f), occupancy (proportion) across of islands (c,g), and across sites (d,h), for non-ballooning (dark grey) and ballooning species (light grey) in the upper panels, and non-specialist (dark grey) and specialist species (light grey) in the lower panels. Chi-squared ($df = 1$): *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, ns = not significant.

Abundance-occupancy relationship

At the archipelago scale, generalised linear models revealed that the log transformation of abundance was a significant predictor of occupancy ($p < 0.001$), both when variation in dispersal ability and variation in niche breadth are accounted for (table 1). Individual models for species categories (ballooning, non-ballooning, specialist, non-specialist) revealed a positive relationship between species occupancy and local abundance at the archipelago scale in all the cases (table 2). Dispersal ability was found to be significant predictors of occupancy ($p < 0.001$). Niche breadth was recovered as a non-significant predictor of occupancy ($p = 0.938$). The linear model that accounted for both variables, revealed both dispersal ability ($p = 0.46$) and niche breadth ($p = 0.13$) to be non-significant (table 1) AIC results revealed the most suitable model to be that accounting for both

dispersal ability and niche breadth ($\Delta AICc = 0.00$) (supplementary material, table S4). AOR plots revealed that for a given value of local abundance, occupancy was greater for ballooning than for non-ballooning species as well as for non-specialist compared to specialist species (figure 3). There was evidence for a statistical difference between slopes for both niche breadth ($p = 0.003$) and dispersal ability ($p = 0.005$) as well as for niche breadth ($p < 0.001$) when both variables are considered in the model (table 2). Differences between dispersal categories seem to be attributed to differences in the intercept, which was higher for ballooning species (table 2). Generalised linear models at the island scale showed the same pattern as at the archipelago scale, with log-abundance being a strong predictor of occupancy ($p < 0.001$), with neither dispersal ability nor niche breadth being significant predictors ($p > 0.05$ in all cases), with the exception of El Hierro. In El Hierro, dispersal ability ($p = 0.04$) and niche breadth ($p = 0.04$) are significant predictors, but become non-significant when both variables are considered in the model (dispersal: $p = 0.33$; niche breadth: $p = 0.32$) (supplementary material, table S5). Log-abundance and occupancy were positively related in all cases, with strong support ($p < 0.001$), with the exceptions being ballooning and specialist species in El Hierro (supplementary material, table S6). There was no evidence for a statistical difference between slopes (p -values of the interaction > 0.05), except for El Hierro for both dispersal ($p = 0.01$) and niche breadth ($p < 0.001$) as well as niche breadth ($p = 0.02$) when both variables are considered in the model (supplementary material table S5) In Tenerife, for a given level of abundance, occupancy is higher for ballooning species but similar between specialists and non-specialist species. In La Gomera, ballooning species tend to occupy more sites at any given value of occupancy while for niche breadth, at lower values of abundance, specialist species tend to occupy more sites. In La Palma and El Hierro, at lower values of abundance, ballooning species tend to occupy more sites, while at higher values of abundance, they tend to occupy fewer sites than non-ballooning species. In La Palma, for any given value of abundance, non-specialist species tend to occupy more sites than specialist whereas in El Hierro, for lower values of abundance, occupancy is higher for specialist species while at higher values of abundance, non-specialist species occupy more sites (supplementary material, figure S5).

Figure 3. Abundance-occupancy relationships (AOR) for (a) ballooning and non-ballooning species and (b) specialist and non-specialist species, at the archipelago scale. Abundance of each species was measured as the mean local abundance among sites where it was sampled, while occupancy was considered the proportion of sites where the species is present. Abundance was log-transformed.

Table 1. Generalised linear models at the archipelago scale, examining the effects of (a) dispersal ability and (b) niche breadth on the abundance-occupancy relationship. Site occupancy (proportion of sites) was treated as the response variable. Log transformed species abundance (mean site abundance) and either dispersal ability or niche breadth (category) were considered as predictor variables. Significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are highlighted in bold.

	(a) Dispersal ability				(b) Niche breadth				(c) Dispersal ability * Niche breadth			
	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	p(> z)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	p(> z)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	p(> z)
Intercept	-2.082	0.099	-20.960	<0.001	-2.625	0.117	-22.425	<0.001	-2.625	0.157	-16.762	<0.001
Log abundance	1.510	0.092	16.381	<0.001	2.262	0.121	18.745	<0.001	2.549	0.175	14.542	<0.001
Dispersal ability	-0.849	0.176	-4.840	<0.001					-0.183	0.246	-0.743	0.457
Niche breadth					0.016	0.211	0.078	0.938	0.415	0.277	1.498	0.134
Log abundance: Dispersal	0.477	0.169	2.824	0.005					-0.401	0.248	-1.613	0.107
Log abundance: Niche breadth					-0.552	0.185	-2.984	0.003	-1.064	0.242	-4.395	<0.001

Table 2. Intercept, slope and R^2 of linear models at the archipelago scale for occupancy (response) vs. log-abundance (predictor) for different subsets of species based on dispersal ability and niche breadth. Significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are highlighted in bold.

	Intercept	p-value Intercept	Slope	p-value Slope	Mc Fadden R^2
Ballooning	-2.0816	<0.001	1.5101	<0.001	0.3052
Non-ballooning	-2.9312	<0.001	1.9871	<0.001	0.2846
Specialist	-2.6085	<0.001	1.7093	<0.001	0.3647
Non-specialist	-2.6249	<0.001	2.2618	<0.001	0.3861

Discussion

Influence of dispersal and niche breadth on species abundance and occupancy

Dispersal facilitates the colonisation of new patches of habitat for resource exploitation (Bowler & Benton 2005), thus increasing patch occupancy and enhancing connectivity among populations. Consistent with this, we find statistically significant differences in occupancy between ballooning and non-ballooning species across all sites (figure 2c-d). However, in contrast, there were no significant differences in abundance between the two dispersal categories for mean site abundance (figure 2b). At the scale of individual islands, there were no significant differences for abundance or occupancy, between the two dispersal categories (supplementary material, figures S1,3). Although significant differences were found when considering abundance and occupancy measures at the level of individual sites at both scales (supplementary material, figures S2,4), it seems likely that these results are influenced by a taxonomic bias. The twenty highest site-level abundances involved only six species, all of them ballooning species. Mean abundance across sites for each species is a less biased estimator, and conclusions are therefore based on this measure. These results highlight how variation in dispersal ability influences species occupancy within a spatial scale and landscape dependent context. At smaller spatial scales (within islands), within habitat landscapes that are likely to have been largely continuous through time (del Arco Aguilar *et al.* 2010; Parsons 1981), dispersal limitation among spider species would appear to be insufficient to limit occupancy, relative to more dispersive species. However, at a larger spatial scale (among islands), within which habitat patches are separated by large areas of uninhabitable landscape (ocean), the influence of dispersal limitation becomes apparent. At this spatial scale, dispersal limitation acts to limit movement among patches, and a clear signature of higher site occupancy is associated with species with higher dispersal ability (ballooning species). Overall, ballooning categorisation serves as a robust proxy for passive dispersal, in line with previous works (e.g., Bonte *et al.* 2003; Carvalho & Cardoso 2014; Suárez *et al.* 2022), with ballooning enhancing patch occupancy across the metacommunity. Regarding abundance, previous work (Borregaard & Rahbek 2010; Gaston & Blackburn 2003; Holt *et al.* 2002) have found that species with

higher dispersal ability were significantly more abundant compared to species with dispersal limitation, at both broader and narrower geographical scales. We found no significant differences in mean abundance comparing ballooning and non-ballooning spiders species, consistent with Levine & Murrell (Levine & Murrell 2003), who have suggested that differences in dispersal ability are unlikely to influence abundance patterns at metapopulation scales. As dispersal ability influences the rate of individual arrival, its influence in shaping abundance patterns is likely to be more determinant in the early stages of habitat colonisation, such as after disturbance, or the emergence of new habitat (Hovestadt *et al.* 2000; Rydin & Borgegård 1991). Given the origin of the youngest island in the study system, El Hierro, is relatively old [estimated to date back 1.12 million years, Troll & Carracedo (2016)], and the relative habitat stability of the laurel forest through time [(del Arco Aguilar *et al.* 2010; Parsons 1981) but see (Salces-Castellano *et al.* 2020)], both factors may underpin similar local abundance patterns between dispersal limited and dispersive species. Further studies are needed in order to understand the temporal scale and disturbance dynamics at which spider dispersal ability could constrain species local abundance.

Niche differences among species can play a key role in structuring communities through processes such as competitive displacement and habitat partitioning (Verberk *et al.* 2010). In contrast to dispersal ability, comparisons between habitat specialist and non-specialist species revealed statistically significant differences for abundance, but not occupancy. Compared to specialist species, non-specialist species were found to occupy a similar number of habitat patches (islands) and sites across the entire archipelago (figure 2g,h), and within islands they occupied a similar number of sites (supplementary material, figure S3). However, non-specialist species displayed lower abundances, compared to specialist species, at both archipelago and island scales (figure 2f). These results provide support for the ‘niche position’ (Hanski *et al.* 1993) and ‘jack-of-all-trades is a master of none’ hypothesis (MacArthur 1984), which implies that specialist species perform better than non-specialist (generalist) species in their optimal habitats, at the expense of a poor performance in other suboptimal habitats (Jasmin & Kassen 2007). An interesting feature of our data is that, in contrast to Verberk *et al.* (2010), who found specialist species to be less

dispersive relative to non-specialist species, we find similar proportions of ballooning species between the two niche breadth categories (56% in non-specialists and 60% in specialists), thus contrasting with the suggestion that habitat specialists are likely to be more sedentary, due to adaptation to stable habitats (Verberk *et al.* 2010).

Influence of dispersal and niche breadth in abundance-occupancy relationship

Results of the linear models support the general ecological pattern of the AOR (Blackburn *et al.* 2006; Gaston *et al.* 1997, 2000), as log-abundance and occupancy were always significantly positively correlated, independently of geographical scale (table 1, supplementary material S1, S2). Dispersal ability was found to be a strong predictor of the AOR, whereby across all sites for a given level of local abundance, occupancy is higher for ballooning species than for non-ballooning species (figure 3a), as predicted by Gaston & Blackburn (2003), and consistent with higher dispersal ability contributing to higher occupancy (figure 2c,d). Slopes were statistically different among dispersive categories, being higher for non-ballooning species. The y-intercept was found to be higher for ballooning species. Contrasting with our findings, both Foggo *et al.* (2007) and Sahara *et al.* (2016) found no significant differences in AOR slopes when comparing dispersal-limited and dispersive species in the marine realm. However, they did recover a higher y-intercept for dispersive species providing more explanation for differences in linear trends. Using four different phyla of marine invertebrate taxa, Foggo *et al.* (2007) revealed a higher fit of the AOR for taxa with planktonic dispersal (good dispersers) compared to taxa with non-planktonic dispersal (poor dispersers). They also found that, for a given level of abundance, occupancy was higher for planktonic dispersal. In their analyses of AORs across species of rocky intertidal gastropod, Sahara *et al.* (2016) also found that regional occupancy was higher for a given level of abundance in planktonic species, resulting in a less aggregated distributions compared to non-planktonic species.

Foggo *et al.* (2007) propose differences in fecundity, mediated by body size, as a potential explanation for a higher fit to the AOR for more dispersive species. They hypothesise that planktonic species (good dispersers) are prone to produce more offspring

than non-planktonic (poor dispersers) due to their larger body size. Higher offspring production increases the probability of population establishment through increased opportunity to encounter suitable environmental conditions (Williamson & Griffiths 1996). Thus, due to higher propagule pressure, good dispersers are more widespread at any given level of abundance. Sahara *et al.* (2016) additionally propose that a dampening effect of larval dispersal can reduce local extinction risk, thus increasing patch occupancy and decreasing spatial patchiness at the metapopulation scale. While it is widely acknowledged that different life stages of smaller spider species and the early juvenile instars of larger species disperse by ballooning (Bonte *et al.* 2003; Dean & Sterling 1985), the relationship between body size, offspring density and ballooning remains unknown in the case of spiders. If larger species produce more offspring and disperse by ballooning, they may be expected to be more abundant in ballooning studies. However, families with larger species are usually absent or at extremely low frequencies (<1%) in ballooning studies, with smaller species being more abundant (Blandenier 2009; Dean & Sterling 1985). This suggests that ballooning propensity is not correlated to differences in fecundity driven by body size, as suggested for marine invertebrates by Foggo *et al.* (2007). In the case of spiders, ballooning appears to be phylogenetically conserved across spider families (Bell *et al.* 2005; Cardoso *et al.* 2011). Although it is unknown why some families exhibit higher ballooning frequencies than others, it has been suggested that it may be related to microhabitat requirements, with non-ballooning lineages being typically associated with more specialised narrow niches (e.g., species strongly linked to edaphic or underground environments) that are less susceptible to convective air currents (Bell *et al.* 2005). Our results are suggestive of a model for spiders where propagule pressure is higher in ballooning species, potentially driven by a higher exposition to passive dispersal vectors, rather than by body size or offspring density differences, leading to higher occupancy for a given level of abundance for ballooning species. However, more understanding is needed with regard to the suggested relationship between dispersal and other species traits.

Niche breadth was found to be a significant predictor of the AOR, with specialist species occupying more sites at any given value of abundance (figure 3b). Our results fits with Verberk *et al.* (2010), who found that for a given value of occupancy, specialists were

more abundant than non-specialists, with the AOR for non-specialist species also providing a higher fit to the data than that for specialist species. Verberk *et al.* (2010) suggest that this difference may be explained by specialist species being more affected by the spatial distribution of environmental conditions. Comparing our results with Verberk *et al.* (2010) is complicated because they implemented abundance as a dependent variable and occupancy as a covariate, whereas in our analyses, occupancy was considered as the dependent variable. There are also contrasting approaches between Verberk *et al.* (2010) and this study, with regard to the classification of specialist and non-specialist species. Verberk *et al.* (2010) were able to derive estimations of niche-breadth for species, thus allowing the comparison of patterns between species that are specialised within a habitat, to those that are not. Our classification is more coarse-grained, where species are considered specialist if they are largely limited to the habitat, and non-specialist if they occur in other habitats. Thus, it remains plausible that variation in niche specificity among species within the laurel forest habitat may explain variation in AORs. Our research has focused on a single habitat type and, while logistically challenging, expanding the scope of sampling across multiple habitat types would enable broader estimations of niche specialization (Boulangéat *et al.* 2012; Clavero & Brotons 2010), including not only niche breadth but also species niche position.

Conclusions

Our results highlight the relevance of both dispersal ability and niche breadth for understanding patterns of abundance and occupancy among spider species, together with the landscape-scale context of habitat suitability within which both variables act. Higher dispersal ability favours site occupancy within landscapes of discontinuous habitat (archipelago level) but appears to be less consequential within continuous habitat (within islands). Specialist species appear to be more abundant than non-specialists, supporting the ‘jack-of-all-trades is a master of none’ hypothesis. We found a strong relationship between log-abundance and occupancy, with significant effects of both niche breadth and dispersal ability on the AOR, where good dispersers and non-specialist occupy more sites for a given level of abundance. Our community-scale framework highlights the importance of spatial scale when seeking to understand what factors shape species abundances and occupancy, with particular reference to spatial patterns of landscape variation. Our results thus suggest that taking into account niche landscapes of individual species will lead to improved understand of the AOR. Further studies integrating dispersal ability, niche and habitat landscape are needed for a fuller understanding of AORs and the variation they present.

Supplementary material

- Figure S1. Box plots showing island-scale differences for mean local abundance (mean number of individuals per site).
- Figure S2. Box plots showing differences for individual site abundance (sum of all number of individuals within a given site).
- Figure S3. Box plots showing island-scale differences for site occupancy (proportion of sites), using mean site abundance as covariate.
- Figure S4. Box plots showing differences for site occupancy (proportion of sites), using individual site abundance as covariate.
- Figure S5. Abundance-occupancy relationships.
- Table S1. Sampling sites and coordinates.
- Table S2. List of presumed biological species.
- Table S3. Linear models at the archipelago scale examining the effect of dispersal ability and different measures of niche breadth on abundance and occupancy.
- Table S4. AIC results addressing the strength of the linear models at archipelago scale.
- Table S5. Linear models at the archipelago scale and at the island scale examining the effect of the interaction of log abundance and either dispersal ability or niche breadth on the abundance-occupancy relationship.
- Table S6. Intercept, slope and R^2 of the linear models at the island scale.

Figure S1. Box plots showing island-scale differences for mean local abundance (mean number of individuals per site) for non-ballooning (dark grey) and ballooning species (light grey) in the upper panels, and non-specialist (dark grey) and specialist species (light grey) in the lower panels, at the archipelago scale (a,f) and within the islands of Tenerife (b,g), La Gomera (c,h), La Palma (d,f) and El Hierro (e,j). Chi-squared (df = 1): *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, ns = not significant.

Figure S2. Box plots showing differences for individual site abundance (sum of all number of individuals within a given site) for non-ballooning (dark grey) and ballooning species (light grey) in the upper panels, and non-specialist (dark grey) and specialist species (light grey) in the lower panels, at archipelago scale (a,f) and within the islands of Tenerife (b,g), La Gomera (c,h), La Palma (d,f) and El Hierro (e,j). Chi-squared (df = 1): *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, ns = not significant.

Figure S3. Box plots showing island-scale differences for site occupancy (proportion of sites), using mean site abundance as covariate, for non-ballooning (dark grey) and ballooning species (light grey) in the upper panels, and non-specialist (dark grey) and specialist species (light grey) in the lower panels, at the archipelago scale (a,f) and within the islands of Tenerife (b,g), La Gomera (c,h), La Palma (d,f) and El Hierro (e,j). Chi-squared (df = 1): *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, ns = not significant.

Figure S4. Box plots showing differences for site occupancy (proportion of sites), using individual site abundance as covariate, for non-ballooning (dark grey) and ballooning species (light grey) in the upper panels, and non-specialist (dark grey) and specialist species (light grey) in the lower panels, at archipelago scale (a,f) and within the islands of Tenerife (b,g), La Gomera (c,h), La Palma (d,f) and El Hierro (e,j). Chi-squared (df = 1): *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, ns = not significant.

Figure S5. Abundance-occupancy relationships for ballooning and non-ballooning spiders (upper panels) and for specialist and non-specialist spiders (lower panels) at the archipelago scale (a,f) and within the islands of Tenerife (b,g), La Gomera (c,h), La Palma (d,i) and El Hierro (e,j).

Table S1. Sampling sites and coordinates.

Site code	Site name	Island	Latitude	Longitude
AGU	Monte Aguirre	Tenerife	28.5334	-16.2698
ANE	Aguas Negras	Tenerife	28.54	-16.2251
CHI	Chinobre	Tenerife	28.559	-16.1736
CTE	Cabezo Tejo	Tenerife	28.562	-16.1714
IJU	Hoya de Ijuana	Tenerife	28.5602	-16.1692
MOQ	El Moquinal	Tenerife	28.5368	-16.3088
NIE	Barranco Nieto	Tenerife	28.5341	-16.3163
PIJ	Pijaral	Tenerife	28.552	-16.1892
TAG	Vueltas de Taganana	Tenerife	28.5443	-16.226
ZAP	Zapata	Tenerife	28.5355	-16.2962
COC	Barranco Cochinos	Tenerife	28.3228	-16.8234
PAS	Barranco Los Pasos	Tenerife	28.3349	-16.8316
AGA	Agua García	Tenerife	28.4579	-16.4041
PBL	Palo Blanco	Tenerife	28.3573	-16.5874
CUB	Cubo de La Galga	La Palma	28.7664	-17.7703
CUM	Hilera de la Cumbre	La Palma	28.6304	-17.8267
LOM	Camino del Lomito	La Palma	28.8038	-17.8203
NIQ	Niquiomo	La Palma	28.6003	-17.8103
TAB	El Tablado	La Palma	28.8184	-17.8833
MAG	Barranco de Magdalena	La Palma	28.8109	-17.9079
ACE	Los Acebiños	La Gomera	28.141	-17.2225
APA	Apartacaminos	La Gomera	28.154	-17.3008
CED	El Cedro	La Gomera	28.124	-17.224
EHA	Encima de Las Hayas	La Gomera	28.1355	-17.2773
FUE	Fuensanta	La Gomera	28.1453	-17.2522
MEV	Meseta de Vallehermoso	La Gomera	28.1539	-17.2934
REV	Reventón Oscuro	La Gomera	28.1221	-17.2138
FAY	El Fayal	El Hierro	27.7322	-17.9949
HDC	Hoya del Creal	El Hierro	27.806	-17.949
MEN	Mencáfete	El Hierro	27.7363	-18.0735
PDR	Pedraje	El Hierro	27.7338	-18.0231

Table S2. List of presumed biological species with information regarding dispersal ability and niche breadth assignment, as well as abundance and occupancy.

PBS code	Taxonomic assignment	Dispersal ability	Niche breadth (expert)	Niche breadth (Q10)	Niche breadth (Q25)	Niche breadth (Q 50)	Niche breadth (Q75)	Number of islands	Number of sites	Total abundance
PBS001	<i>Dysdera brevisetae</i> Wunderlich, 1992	Non-ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	11	67
PBS002	<i>Dysdera iguanensis</i> Wunderlich, 1987	Non-ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	3	55
PBS003	<i>Dysdera brevispina</i> Wunderlich, 1992	Non-ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	8	281
PBS004	<i>Dysdera</i> sp.1	Non-ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	1	1
PBS005	<i>Dysdera</i> n. sp.1	Non-ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	2	6
PBS006	<i>Dysdera</i> aff. <i>vermeaui</i> sp.1	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	3	109
PBS007	<i>Dysdera insulana</i> Simon, 1883	Non-ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	2	4
PBS008	<i>Dysdera levipes</i> Wunderlich, 1987	Non-ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	2	6
PBS009	<i>Dysdera</i> aff. <i>vermeaui</i> sp.2	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	5
PBS010	<i>Dysdera</i> n. sp.2	Non-ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	2	21
PBS011	<i>Spermophorides heterogibbifer</i> (Wunderlich, 1987)	Non-ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	4	20
PBS012	<i>Spermophorides mercedes</i> (Wunderlich, 1987)	Non-ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	3	4
PBS013	<i>Zoropsis rufipes</i> (Lucas, 1838)	Non-ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	4	26	403
PBS014	<i>Olios canariensis</i> (Lucas, 1838)	Non-ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	12	55
PBS015	<i>Cladynis insignis</i> (Lucas, 1838)	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	4	31	1061
PBS016	<i>Tegenaria pagana</i> (L. Koch, 1840)	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	4	28	350
PBS017	<i>Tenuiphantes tenuis</i> (Blackwall, 1852)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	3	7	45
PBS018	<i>Tenuiphantes canariensis</i> (Wunderlich, 1987)	Ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	3	25	668
PBS019	<i>Microlinyphia johnsoni</i> (Blackwall, 1859)	Ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	4	29	834
PBS020	<i>Metellina minima</i> (Denis, 1953)	Ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	3	24	1562
PBS021	<i>Cryptachaea blattea</i> (Urquhart, 1886)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	3	12	47

PBS code	Taxonomic assignment	Dispersal ability	Niche breadth (expert)	Niche breadth (Q10)	Niche breadth (Q25)	Niche breadth (Q 50)	Niche breadth (Q75)	Number of islands	Number of sites	Total abundance
PBS022	<i>Cyclosa maderiana</i> Kulczynski, 1899	Ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	4	18	262
PBS023	<i>Meta</i> sp.	Ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	4	8
PBS024	<i>Agyreta rurestris</i> (C.L.Koch, 1836)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	3	7	9
PBS025	<i>Mangora acalypha</i> (Walckenaer, 1802)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	3	14	189
PBS026	<i>Gibbaranea tenerifensis</i> Wunderlich, 1992	Ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	3	6
PBS027	<i>Lasaeola canariensis</i> (Wunderlich, 1987)	Ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	1
PBS028	<i>Hogna brunnea</i> (Bösenberg, 1895)	Ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	1
PBS029	<i>Ero tuberculata</i> (De Geer, 1778)	Non-ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	3	17	108
PBS030	<i>Hyptiotes flavidus</i> (Blackwall, 1862)	Non-ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	4	14	85
PBS031	<i>Rhomphaea nasica</i> (Simon, 1873)	Ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Non-specialist	1	10	137
PBS032	<i>Synema globosum</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	2	2	2
PBS033	<i>Apostenus annulipedes</i> Wunderlich, 1987	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	4	90
PBS034	<i>Alopecosa kulczynskii</i> (Bösenberg, 1895)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	4
PBS035	<i>Araneus bufo</i> (Denis, 1941)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	3	6	10
PBS036	<i>Drassodes</i> sp.1	Non-ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	2	3
PBS037	<i>Theridion musivivum</i> Schmidt, 1956	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	4	26	498
PBS038	<i>Neoscona</i> sp.	Ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	4	11	18
PBS039	<i>Araniella maderiana</i> (Kulczynski, 1905)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	4	22	173
PBS040	<i>Steatoda</i> sp.1	Ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	2	2
PBS041	<i>Macaroeris nidicolens</i> (Walckenaer, 1802)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	4	18	110
PBS042	<i>Paidiscura orotavensis</i> (Schmidt, 1968)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	2	16	109
PBS043	<i>Ero</i> sp.	Non-ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	5	6
PBS044	<i>Xysticus</i> sp.	Ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	3	10	14
PBS045	<i>Macaroeris moebi</i> (Bösenberg, 1895)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	1

PBS code	Taxonomic assignment	Dispersal ability	Niche breadth (expert)	Niche breadth (Q10)	Niche breadth (Q25)	Niche breadth (Q 50)	Niche breadth (Q75)	Number of islands	Number of sites	Total abundance
PBS046	<i>Enoplognatha sattleri</i> Bösenberg, 1895	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	4	11	66
PBS047	<i>Tenuiphantes palmensis</i> (Wunderlich, 1992)	Ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	6	34
PBS048	<i>Canariellanus</i> sp.	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	3	12	68
PBS049	<i>Walckenaeria afur</i> Thaler, 1984	Ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	7	13
PBS050	<i>Improphantes furcabilis</i> (Wunderlich, 1987)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	3	9	74
PBS051	<i>Zygiella minima</i> Schmidt, 1968	Ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	4	19	394
PBS052	<i>Macarophaeus varius</i> (Simon, 1893)	Non-ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	4	27	585
PBS053	<i>Spermophorides</i> sp.1	Non-ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	3	36
PBS054	<i>Pulchellodromus wunderlichi</i> (Muster & Thaler, 2007)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	4	31	1654
PBS055	<i>Porrhoclubiona minor</i> Wunderlich, 1987	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	4	22	89
PBS056	<i>Nigma</i> sp.	Non-ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	3	14	111
PBS057	<i>Cheiracanthium canariense</i> Wunderlich, 1987	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	4	31	1477
PBS058	<i>Steatoda</i> sp.2	Ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	7	32
PBS059	<i>Steatoda nobilis</i> (Thorell, 1875)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	4	31	434
PBS060	<i>Episinus</i> aff. <i>maderianus</i> sp.1	Ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	3	22	1550
PBS061	<i>Episinus</i> aff. <i>maderianus</i> sp.2	Ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	4	13	132
PBS062	<i>Echinotheridion gibberosum</i> (Kulczynski, 1899)	Ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	4	28	2032
PBS063	<i>Macaridion barretti</i> (Kulczynski, 1899)	Ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	4	25	1812
PBS064	<i>Improphantes</i> sp.1	Ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	1	45
PBS065	<i>Improphantes multidentatus</i> (Wunderlich, 1987)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	3	15	219
PBS066	<i>Minicia teneriffensis</i> (Wunderlich, 1979)	Ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	14	694
PBS067	<i>Lathys denticelisis</i> (Simon, 1883)	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	4	27	291

PBS code	Taxonomic assignment	Dispersal ability	Niche breadth (expert)	Niche breadth (Q10)	Niche breadth (Q25)	Niche breadth (Q 50)	Niche breadth (Q75)	Number of islands	Number of sites	Total abundance
PBS068	<i>Mimetus</i> sp.	Non-ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	2	3	10
PBS069	<i>Pholcus gomevae</i> Wunderlich, 1980	Non-ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	2	15
PBS070	<i>Ariadna</i> sp.	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	6	28
PBS071	<i>Steatoda</i> sp.3	Ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	7	86
PBS072	<i>Kochiura aulica</i> (C. L. Koch, 1838)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	3	41
PBS073	<i>Bassaniodes canariensis</i> (Wunderlich, 1987)	Ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	2	9	139
PBS074	<i>Dysdera silvatica</i> Schmidt, 1981	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	11
PBS075	<i>Dysdera enghoffi</i> Arnedo, Oromí & Ribera, 1997	Non-ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	2	8
PBS076	<i>Agyneta fuscipalpa</i> (Koch, 1836)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	1
PBS077	<i>Ostearius melanopygius</i> (Cambridge, 1879)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	1
PBS078	<i>Pholcomma gibbum</i> (Westring, 1851)	Ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	2	5	61
PBS079	<i>Metellina</i> sp.	Ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	2	5	20
PBS080	<i>Walckenaeria alba</i> Wunderlich, 1987	Ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	5	17
PBS081	<i>Walckenaeria gomerensis</i> Wunderlich, 1987	Ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	4	21
PBS082	<i>Misumena spinifera</i> (Blackwall, 1862)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	3	10	23
PBS083	<i>Dysdera ramblae</i> Arnedo, Oromí & Ribera, 1997	Non-ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	2	2
PBS084	<i>Palliduphantes rubens</i> (Wunderlich, 1987)	Ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	6	25
PBS085	<i>Argyrodes incertus</i> Wunderlich, 1987	Ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	8	14
PBS086	<i>Dysdera gomerensis</i> Strand, 1911	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	4	16
PBS087	<i>Oxyopes kraepelinorum</i> Bösenberg, 1895	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	2	3	11
PBS088	<i>Spermophorides gomerensis</i> (Wunderlich, 1987)	Non-ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	6	129
PBS089	<i>Minicia gomevae</i> (Schmidt, 1975)	Ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	7	183

PBS code	Taxonomic assignment	Dispersal ability	Niche breadth (expert)	Niche breadth (Q10)	Niche breadth (Q25)	Niche breadth (Q 50)	Niche breadth (Q75)	Number of islands	Number of sites	Total abundance
PBS090	<i>Olios</i> aff. <i>canariensis</i> sp.1	Non-ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	7	20
PBS091	<i>Drassodes</i> sp.2	Non-ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	3	3
PBS092	<i>Tenuiphantes</i> sp.	Ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	2	3	3
PBS093	<i>Hypsosinga albovittata</i> (Westring, 1851)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	2	3	4
PBS094	<i>Alopecosa gomeræ</i> (Strand, 1911)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	1
PBS095	<i>Agelena gomerensis</i> Wunderlich, 1992	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	1
PBS096	<i>Apostenus gomerensis</i> Wunderlich, 1992	Non-ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	1	1
PBS097	<i>Micaria gomeræ</i> Strand, 1911	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	1
PBS098	<i>Pholcus sveni</i> Wunderlich, 1987	Non-ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	3	13
PBS099	<i>Typhochrestus bogarti</i> Bosmans, 1990	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	2	2	2
PBS100	<i>Agalenatea redii</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	2	4
PBS101	<i>Nigma puella</i> (Simon, 1870)	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	2	2	2
PBS102	<i>Pholcus</i> sp.	Non-ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	2	22
PBS103	<i>Improphantes</i> sp.2	Ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	3	74
PBS104	<i>Dysdera</i> aff. <i>gomerensis</i>	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	4	85
PBS105	<i>Drassodes</i> sp.3	Non-ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	2	3
PBS106	<i>Canariellanus</i> cf. <i>palmense</i>	Ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	3	5
PBS107	<i>Olios</i> aff. <i>canariensis</i> sp.2	Non-ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	6	47
PBS108	<i>Zoropsis</i> aff. <i>rufipes</i>	Non-ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	2	19
PBS109	<i>Spermophorides</i> sp.2	Non-ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	4	74
PBS110	<i>Dysdera</i> aff. <i>silvatica</i>	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	3
PBS111	<i>Dysdera calderensis</i> Wunderlich, 1987	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	2	3
PBS112	<i>Walckenaeria</i> sp.	Ballooning	¿?	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	2	4
PBS113	<i>Minicia</i> aff. <i>gomeræ</i> sp.1	Ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	4	352
PBS114	<i>Minicia</i> aff. <i>gomeræ</i> sp.2	Ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	1	18

PBS code	Taxonomic assignment	Dispersal ability	Niche breadth (expert)	Niche breadth (Q10)	Niche breadth (Q25)	Niche breadth (Q 50)	Niche breadth (Q75)	Number of islands	Number of sites	Total abundance
PBS115	<i>Dysdera</i> aff. <i>iguanensis</i>	Non-ballooning	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	Specialist	1	1	3
PBS116	<i>Alopecosa obscura</i> Schmidt, 1980	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	2	16
PBS117	<i>Dysdera orahan</i> Arnedo, Oromí & Ribera, 1997	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	1
PBS118	<i>Dysdera crocata</i> C.L. Koch, 1838	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	1
PBS119	<i>Dysdera</i> aff. <i>verneau</i> sp.3	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	1
PBS120	<i>Prinerigone vagans</i> (Audouin, 1826)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	1
PBS121	<i>Steatoda grossa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1838)	Ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	1
PBS122	<i>Pholcus ornatus</i> Bösenberg, 1895	Non-ballooning	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	Non-specialist	1	1	1
PBS123	<i>Oecobius</i> sp.	Non-ballooning	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	¿?	1	1	2

Table S3. Linear models at the archipelago scale examining the effect of dispersal ability and different measures of niche breadth on abundance and occupancy. For abundance analyses, the proportion of islands and the proportion of sites were implemented as covariates. For occupancy analyses, abundance was implemented as a covariate. Significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are highlighted in bold.

Variable	Coefficients	Dispersal	Niche breadth (only experts)	Niche breadth (Q10)	Niche breadth (Q25)	Niche breadth (Q50)	Niche breadth (Q75)
Abundance (mean site abundance)	LR Chisq	2.864	7.136	2.629	3.568	7.066	7.573
	df	1	1	1	1	1	1
	P(>Chisq)	0.091	0.008	0.105	0.059	0.008	0.006
	P(>Chisq)						
	Proportion of islands	<0.001	0.032	0.020	0.014	0.033	0.019
	P(>Chisq)						
Proportion of sites	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
Abundance (individual site abundance)	LR Chisq	725.39	4056.8	4056.8	4056.8	4056.8	4056.8
	df	1	1	1	1	1	1
	P(>Chisq)	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	P(>Chisq)						
	Proportion of sites	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	P(>Chisq)						
Proportion of sites (using mean site abundance)	LR Chisq	16.90	15.477	11.62	1.32	25.51	30.46
	df	1	1	1	1	1	1
	P(>Chisq)	0.002	<0.001	<0.001	0.250	<0.001	<0.001
	P(>Chisq)						
	Abundance	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	P(>Chisq)						

Variable	Coefficients	Dispersal	Niche breadth (only experts)	Niche breadth (Q10)	Niche breadth (Q25)	Niche breadth (Q50)	Niche breadth (Q75)
Proportion of sites (using individual site abundance)	LR Chisq	2.249	303.101	303.101	303.101	303.101	303.101
	df	1	1	1	1	1	1
	P(>Chisq)	0.134	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	P (>Chisq) Abundance	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
Proportion of islands (using mean site abundance)	LR Chisq	8.77	5.95	7.46	2.50	8.65	6.88
	df	1	1	1	1	1	1
	P(>Chisq)	0.031	0.015	0.006	0.114	0.003	0.009
	P (>Chisq) Abundance	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

Table S4. AIC results addressing the strength of the linear models at archipelago scale including, for each niche breadth categorisation criteria, one model accounting just for dispersal ability, another one accounting just for niche breadth and one accounting for both variables. The p-value for each model is also included.

Niche criteria	Model	P-value	K	AICc	Delta_AICc	AICcwt	Cum.wt	LL	
	Dispersal	0.016	8	850.57	0.00	1	1	-416.23	
Only experts	Dispersal * Niche breadth	Dispersal:log(abundance)	0.5733						
		Niche	0.035						
		Niche:log(abundance)	<0.001						
	Niche breadth	Niche	0.735	4	896.06	45.49	0	1	-443.75
		Niche:log(abundance)	0.002						
		Dispersal	<0.001	4	1325.22	474.65	0	1	-658.44
	Dispersal	Dispersal:log(abundance)	0.005						
Q10	Dispersal	Dispersal	0.016	8	1036.80	0.00	1	1	-509.60
	Dispersal * Niche breadth	Dispersal:log(abundance)	0.5733						
		Niche	0.887						
		Niche:log(abundance)	<0.001						
	Niche breadth	Niche	0.489	4	1069.65	32.85	0	1	-530.61
		Niche:log(abundance)	0.001						
	Dispersal	Dispersal	<0.001	4	1325.22	288.42	0	1	-658.44
	Dispersal	Dispersal:log(abundance)	0.005						

Niche criteria	Model	P-value	K	AICc	Delta_AICc	AICcwt	Cum.wt	LL	
	Dispersal	0.138	8	1053.61	0.00	1	1	-518.00	
Q25	Dispersal * Niche breadth	Dispersal:log(abundance)	0.1002						
		Niche	0.286						
		Niche:log(abundance)	0.002						
	Niche breadth	Niche	0.593	4	1089.38	35.78	0	1	-540.48
		Niche:log(abundance)	0.032						
		Dispersal	<0.001	4	1325.22	271.61	0	1	-658.44
	Dispersal:log(abundance)	0.005							
Q50	Dispersal	0.457	8	1039.20	0.00	1	1	-510.80	
	Dispersal * Niche breadth	Dispersal:log(abundance)	0.1067						
		Niche	0.134						
		Niche:log(abundance)	<0.001						
	Niche breadth	Niche	0.938	4	1061.40	22.20	0	1	-526.49
		Niche:log(abundance)	0.003						
	Dispersal	<0.001	4	1325.22	286.03	0	1	-658.44	
	Dispersal:log(abundance)	0.005							
Q75	Dispersal	0.404	8	1046.35	0.00	1	1	-514.37	
	Dispersal * Niche breadth	Dispersal:log(abundance)	0.1940						
		Niche	0.182						
		Niche:log(abundance)	<0.001						
	Niche breadth	Niche	0.954	4	1064.67	18.33	0	1	-528.12
		Niche:log(abundance)	0.004						
	Dispersal	<0.001	4	1325.22	278.87	0	1	-658.44	
	Dispersal:log(abundance)	0.005							

Table S5. Linear models at the archipelago scale and at the island scale examining the effect of the interaction of log abundance and either (a) dispersal ability or (b) niche breadth (Q50) on the abundance-occupancy relationship. Site occupancy was treated as the response variable. Log transformed species abundance and either dispersal ability or niche breadth were considered as predictor variables. The interaction between abundance and either dispersal ability or niche breadth was treated as a fixed effect. Significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are highlighted in bold.

	<i>(a) Dispersal ability</i>				<i>(b) Niche breadth</i>				<i>(c) Dispersal ability * Niche breadth</i>			
	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	p(> z)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	p(> z)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	p(> z)
Tenerife												
Intercept	-2.542	0.196	-12.98	<0.001	-2.678	0.218	-12.31	<0.001	-2.702	0.255	-10.60	<0.001
Log abundance	1.597	0.123	12.949	<0.001	1.735	0.137	12.641	<0.001	1.852	0.185	10.014	<0.001
Dispersal	-0.592	0.361	-1.643	0.100					-0.121	0.529	-0.229	0.819
Niche breadth					-0.507	0.429	-1.181	0.238	-0.099	0.538	-0.183	0.854
La Gomera												
Intercept	-0.994	0.219	-4.529	<0.001	-1.228	0.249	-4.922	<0.001	-1.055	0.276	-3.824	<0.001
Log abundance	1.987	0.259	7.657	<0.001	2.280	0.302	7.542	<0.001	2.112	0.360	5.867	<0.001
Dispersal	0.068	0.373	0.183	0.855					-0.841	0.659	-1.275	0.202
Niche breadth					0.596	0.467	1.276	0.202	1.292	0.787	1.642	0.101
Log abundance:Dispersal	-0.119	0.443	-0.270	0.787					0.832	0.758	1.097	0.273
Log abundance:Niche breadth					-0.812	0.477	-1.703	0.088	-1.218	0.681	-1.789	0.073

	<i>(a) Dispersal ability</i>				<i>(b) Niche breadth</i>				<i>(c) Dispersal ability * Niche breadth</i>			
La Palma	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	p(> z)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	p(> z)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	p(> z)
Intercept	-0.670	0.248	-2.702	0.007	-0.975	0.284	-3.437	<0.001	-0.796	0.331	-2.404	0.016
Log abundance	1.334	0.252	5.302	<0.001	2.355	0.378	6.236	<0.001	1.982	0.427	4.645	<0.001
Dispersal	-0.579	0.513	-1.130	0.259					-0.690	0.669	-1.033	0.302
Niche breadth					-0.145	0.579	-0.251	0.802	-0.067	0.617	-0.108	0.914
Log abundance:Dispersal	1.086	0.635	1.710	0.087					1.325	0.913	1.451	0.149
Log abundance:Niche breadth					-1.055	0.544	-1.938	0.053	-0.813	0.581	-1.401	0.161
El Hierro	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	p(> z)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	p(> z)	Estimate	Std. Error	z value	p(> z)
Intercept	0.183	0.384	0.476	0.634	-0.964	0.386	-2.498	0.012	-0.543	0.564	-0.962	0.336
Log abundance	0.616	0.405	1.522	0.128	2.748	0.553	4.970	<0.001	2.138	0.727	2.940	0.003
Dispersal	-1.192	0.576	-2.070	0.038					-0.771	0.794	-0.971	0.331
Niche breadth					1.857	0.932	1.992	0.046	1.023	1.027	0.997	0.319

Table S6. Intercept, slope and R^2 of the linear models at the island scale for occupancy (response) vs. log-abundance (predictor) for different species subsets based on dispersal ability and niche breadth (Q50). *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$ (only for slope and intercept).

Variable	Category	Tenerife	La Gomera	La Palma	El Hierro
Intercept	Ballooning	-2.542***	-0.994***	-0.670***	0.1828
	Non-ballooning	-3.134***	-0.926***	-1.249**	-1.009*
	Specialist	-3.186***	-0.632***	-1.121*	0.892
	Non-specialist	-2.678***	-1.228***	-0.975***	-0.964*
Slope	Ballooning	1.597***	1.987***	1.334***	0.6162
	Non-ballooning	1.777***	1.868***	2.419***	2.553***
	Specialist	1.911***	1.468***	1.300***	-0.353
	Non-specialist	1.735***	2.280***	2.344***	2.748***
Mc Fadden R^2	Ballooning	0.583	0.348	0.229	0.032
	Non-ballooning	0.482	0.241	0.345	0.426
	Specialist	0.619	0.180	0.278	0.011
	Non-specialist	0.589	0.349	0.376	0.419

Chapter III

Environmental heterogeneity rather than stability drives contrasting diversity patterns of spider assemblages between open and closed ecosystems

Suárez D, Arribas P, Srivathsan A, Meier R, Emerson BC. (in prep.) Environmental heterogeneity rather than stability drives contrasting diversity patterns of spider assemblages between open and closed ecosystems.

Abstract

While there is a growing body of evidence explaining how arthropod communities are structured across islands within archipelagos, less attention has been paid to patterns and processes of community structure between different environments within islands. Terrestrial ecosystems can be coarsely categorised as “closed” and “open” ecosystems, with contrasting spatial and temporal environmental heterogeneity. Open ecosystems (e.g., grasslands, prairies, shrublands) tend to be ecologically less stable than closed ones (i.e., forests), and encompass higher spatial heterogeneity in terms of environmental diversity. Such differences are expected to differentially constrain the diversity and structure of the communities that inhabit each of them, but identifying the specific processes driving contrasting biodiversity patterns between open and closed systems is challenging. In order to understand how environmental variability might structure spider assemblages, both between and within open and closed ecosystems, we implement a high throughput multiplex barcode sequencing approach to generate a dataset for 8585 specimens representing 168 species, across open ecosystems within the Canary Islands. Combining these sequences with sequences from closed ecosystems within the same islands, we first test the prediction that spider communities in open ecosystems will show higher species richness, higher beta diversity, and proportionately higher numbers of endemic species and rare species, than communities in closed ecosystems at multiple scales. If differences in habitat stability is an overriding driver differentiating spider communities of both ecosystems, we expect that species within open ecosystem communities will present comparatively lower spatial genetic structuring, both within and among islands, and that the proportion of species with high dispersal capacity will be higher in open ecosystems. On the other hand, if differences in spatial environmental heterogeneity between open and closed ecosystems are more important, we expect a broader range of environmental variability within open ecosystems at both archipelago and island scales, and a significantly greater proportion of species turnover in open ecosystems explained by environmental variation. Our results reveal different spatial patterns of arthropod diversity in open and closed ecosystems in the Canary Islands and point to environmental heterogeneity rather than stability as a major driver of such differences.

Introduction

Oceanic islands have long been considered as ‘natural laboratories’ for developing our understanding of ecological and evolutionary processes (Whittaker *et al.* 2017), due to features including: (i) discrete geographical boundaries that provide natural replicates; (ii) less complex biota compared to mainland systems; (iii) reduced gene flow among island populations due to oceanic barriers, and; (iv) their often well understood temporal origins due to geological analysis (Emerson 2002). Island biodiversity and the processes that both generate and eliminate it are largely understood from empirical data on plants and birds, while in contrast, there is comparatively limited evidence from arthropods (Emerson *et al.* 2022). Despite their typically dominant species richness within oceanic islands, the representation of arthropods in community-scale ecological or evolutionary studies is limited. This is in large part explained by logistical challenges when working across diverse arthropod lineages that frequently require both specialist taxonomic expertise and substantial time and effort to process the high numbers of specimens typically encountered within a single community sample. Arthropod DNA barcoding, the sequencing of a 658-bp fragment of the mitochondrial DNA COI gene (Hebert *et al.* 2003), has considerably simplified arthropod-community analyses by providing a tool for rapid taxonomic assignment, thus reducing the constraints associated with morphological identification (Emerson *et al.* 2017; Hebert & Gregory 2005; Kennedy *et al.* 2020). However, traditional Sanger sequencing-based DNA barcoding is both expensive and time-consuming for most arthropod community-level studies (Kennedy *et al.* 2020).

High throughput sequencing (hereafter, HTS) has recently been leveraged within two different implementations for the generation of arthropod barcode data at scale. Whole organism community DNA (wocDNA) metabarcoding involves a single DNA extraction for multiple individuals from multiple species, that is subsequently amplified and sequenced (e.g., Andújar *et al.* 2022; Arjona *et al.* 2022; Creedy *et al.* 2022; Emerson *et al.* 2022). In contrast, multiplex barcoding combines up to thousands of tagged amplicons from individual extractions, which are pooled and sequenced in parallel on a HTS platform (e.g., Creedy *et al.* 2020; Hebert *et al.* 2018; de Kerdrel *et al.* 2020; Srivathsan *et al.* 2019, 2021). Both approaches reduce operating costs and human resources compared with

Sanger-based barcode sequencing. However, multiplex barcoding connects individual sequences with voucher specimens, providing a distinct advantage over wocDNA metabarcoding, which involves a single DNA extraction of all individuals within a typically large community sample. Thus, while both implementations overcome traditional arthropod biodiversity data limitations, multiplex barcoding provides a more data rich approach, enhancing opportunities for downstream taxonomic analyses with voucher specimens, in turn providing improved opportunities to address outstanding questions regarding arthropod biodiversity.

While there is a growing body of evidence explaining how arthropod communities are structured across islands within archipelagos (e.g., Borges & Hortal 2009; Gillespie 2016; Rominger *et al.* 2016), less attention has been paid to patterns and processes of community structure between different environments within islands. Terrestrial ecosystems can be coarsely categorised into forested, or “closed” ecosystems and non-forested, or “open” ecosystems, where non-forested incorporates habitat types such as grasslands, prairies, shrublands, and open woodlands. Closed ecosystems are dominated by trees that generate a canopy, providing conditions that favour shade-tolerant species (Pausas & Bond 2020). In contrast, open ecosystems are dominated by herbaceous or arbustive shade-intolerant species (Edwards *et al.* 2010; Veldman *et al.* 2015). Previous studies have revealed substantial compositional differences between arthropod communities of closed and open areas, with communities being largely non-overlapping (e.g., Arribas *et al.* 2021; Caruso *et al.* 2012; Lacasella *et al.* 2015; Pitta *et al.* 2019), with higher beta-diversity and rarity associated with open environments. Additionally, recent analyses of spider communities within closed and open ecosystems of the Macaronesian islands have revealed clear structuring of spider assemblages by ecosystem (Malumbres-Olarte *et al.* 2021). Assemblages of open ecosystems were also found to have higher beta-diversity, as well as log-series species abundance distributions, pointing to a higher representation of rare species, compared to closed ecosystems. However, while Malumbres-Olarte *et al.* (2021) have suggested that either temporal or environmental stability could explain these differences, the specific processes driving the contrasting biodiversity patterns remains unknown.

Environmental stability of habitats has been found to impact community structure (Cobb *et al.* 1992; Death 1995) and diversification (Fine 2015 and references therein) of the species that inhabit them. So, environmental stability may drive compositional and structural community differences between closed and open areas. Open ecosystems tend to be ecologically less stable than forests, with the latter having greater ecological stability due to the protective effect of the canopy (Lin *et al.* 2020). A protective canopy has a major effect on temperature, maintaining lower maximum temperatures and higher minimum temperatures, in contrast to open areas (Arroyo-Rodríguez *et al.* 2017; D’Odorico *et al.* 2013; Tuff *et al.* 2016), thus resulting in narrower temperature ranges within forests. Open areas favour enhanced light radiation, desiccation, and evapotranspiration, resulting in greater water stress when contrasted with forested ecosystems (Chen *et al.* 1999; Murcia 1995). Ecoclimatically stable ecosystems favour higher species richness and levels of endemism (Fjeldså *et al.* 1999; Graham *et al.* 2006; Harrison & Noss 2017). Such stability is also associated with spatial structuring, both at the level of community composition, and at the level of genetic diversity within species, due to long-term persistence of populations and less dependency on a metapopulation dynamic of migration and dispersal (Carnaval *et al.* 2009; Ribera & Vogler 2000). In contrast, lower ecosystem stability selects for species with stronger dispersal ability (Hof *et al.* 2006, 2012), as species with limited dispersal ability are more prone to extinction in such environments. This will ultimately lead to lower community turnover and more limited geographic structuring of genetic diversity within species, relative to areas of high ecosystem stability.

An additional factor that could have a causal relationship with the contrasting biodiversity patterns found between open and closed ecosystems is differences in spatial environmental heterogeneity within each ecosystem, in terms of environmental diversity. Areas containing a greater range of habitat types and/or resources are expected to harbour more available niche space, thus favouring higher species coexistence (Lundholm 2009; Stein *et al.* 2014). Spatial environmental heterogeneity is also expected to enhance differences in species composition (Heino & Grönroos 2014; Peláez & Pavanelli 2019; Veech & Crist 2007), due to an increased role of species sorting as environmental gradients increase (Leibold *et al.* 2004). Open areas may encompass a broad variety of bioclimatic conditions and habitat types (Pausas & Bond 2020) that share the presence of shade-

intolerant species (Bond 2021; Power *et al.* 2017). Any such heterogeneity of habitat type developing under heterogeneous abiotic conditions may in turn, lead to a higher diversity of available ecological niches than forested areas. Species richness in open areas increases as the number of available niches increases (Lacasella *et al.* 2015; Pitta *et al.* 2019). Higher spatial heterogeneity for environmental variables within open environments may result in stronger selection gradients for species traits, thus favouring higher community turnover, relative to closed ecosystems.

In order to understand how temporal and spatial environmental variability structures spider assemblages, both between and within open and closed ecosystems, we implement a HTS multiplex barcoding approach to generate a genetic community dataset of barcode sequences from 8585 specimens for 168 species and 1880 haplotypes, sampled in a systematic way across open and closed ecosystems across four of the Canary Islands. Together with 2,663 sequences for 123 species generated using Sanger-sequencing by Suárez *et al.* (2022), a dataset including 11,248 individuals, yielding 2,931 haplotypes, was generated. We first leverage this dataset to confirm previous findings of high community turnover across both ecosystems, as in Malumbres-Olarte *et al.* (2021), which used a traditional morphology-based approach. By incorporating specimen-level barcode data, we take into account potential cryptic or undescribed diversity and establish an objective species delineation method. We then use intraspecific genetic variation across communities for a more nuanced understanding of community patterns and ecological and evolutionary processes between open and closed ecosystems. It has previously been revealed that spatial structuring of spider assemblages within laurel forests of the Canary Islands is influenced by dispersal ability, where limited dispersal ability drives higher turnover (Suárez *et al.* 2022). Here we expand the sampling of Suárez *et al.* (2022) to include open environments, thus providing a spatially explicit framework to test the following hypotheses:

(H1) Consistent with previous findings, we expect spider communities sampled from the same ecosystem to be more similar than communities sampled from different ecosystems, with open ecosystem communities showing higher species richness, higher beta diversity, and proportionately higher numbers of endemic species and rare species.

(H2) If environmental stability is a driver of contrasting spider community patterns between open and closed ecosystems, we expect that (i) open ecosystem species will present comparatively lower spatial genetic structuring both within and among islands, and that (ii) open ecosystem assemblages will be represented by proportionately more species with high dispersal potential.

(H3) If spatial environmental heterogeneity is a driver of contrasting spider community patterns between open and closed ecosystems, we expect a significantly greater proportion of the variance of spider community composition to be explained by environmental variation in open ecosystems at both archipelago and island scales.

Material and methods

Field sampling

A total of 25 sites were sampled within open shrublands characterised by the presence of species of *Euphorbia* across the four western islands of the Canary archipelago (Figure 1; Table S1). These data were complemented with an existing dataset including 32 closed laurel forest sites across the same islands (see Suárez *et al.* 2022 for details, Figure 1). At each of the 25 open ecosystem sites, a standardised field sampling protocol was applied (Appendix S1), combining both active sampling techniques (foliage beating, vegetation sweeping and active searching) and passive sampling (pitfall traps). Spatial scales across sites were similar at both the archipelago and the island scale between ecosystems (Table S2). Sampling was carried out from 2019 and 2021 between the months of March and April. Samples were preserved in absolute ethanol at -20°C until further processing.

Figure 1. Sampling sites within closed (black dots) and open ecosystems (white diamonds) of the Canary Islands. Sampling sites are labelled with three-letter codes (see TableS1 for further details).

Mitochondrial DNA sequencing

Sampled individuals were examined under a stereomicroscope and provisional taxonomic assignments were made to species, genus or family level. Subsequently, all specimens were DNA-barcoded using the multiplex barcoding approach. Depending upon specimen size, a single leg, several legs, or prosome were placed within wells of a 96-well plate for DNA extraction, following the HotSHOT protocol (Truett *et al.* 2000), adding 20 μ L of lysis buffer to each well, placing plates into a thermocycler at 65°C for 18 min, and then adding 20 μ L of neutralisation buffer. A 418 bp region within the 5' region of the mtDNA COI gene was amplified using the primers III_B_F (Shokralla *et al.* 2015) and BR2 (Elbrecht & Leese 2017), with each primer having a 9-bp tag (see Srivathsan *et al.* 2023). Within each 96-well plate, a plate-specific tagged III_B_F primer was used across all wells, while the tagged BR2 primers were unique to each well (for further details, see Srivathsan *et al.* 2021). PCR mix comprised 7 μ L of CWBio 2x master mix, 1 μ L of BSA, 1 μ L of each primer and 3 μ L of DNA template. One μ L of each PCR product was pooled and then, pools were cleaned using CleanNHS beads (CleanNA). A total of 5 pools were made, with

between 384-7776 individuals per pool. Clean-up efficiency was evaluated via gel electrophoresis, with the expectation of a single band of 418-bp. DNA concentration was then measured using Qubit. MinION libraries were generated using the Ligation Sequencing Kit V14 (Oxford Nanopore Technologies) and 200 ng of purified DNA, following kit instructions, but with the following modifications: (i) the FFPE DNA repair mix in the end-pair reaction was excluded; (ii) the reaction volumes for the R10.4.1. flow cell libraries consisted of 50 μ L of DNA, 7 μ L of Ultra II End-prep reaction buffer (New England Biolabs), 3 μ L of Ultra II End Prep enzyme mix (New England Biolabs), 5 μ L of molecular grade water, and; (iii) all bead clean-up steps were conducted at a 1X ratio. Libraries were loaded and sequenced in a MinION R10.4.1 flow cell on a Mk1C at a low-speed setting of 260 bps. Base-calling was performed with both the fast and super-accuracy models using Guppy. Demultiplexing was performed with ONTbarcode (Srivathsan *et al.* 2021). ONTbarcode requires a demultiplexing file comprising tag combinations and labels for each specimen, primer sequences, the expected fragment length, and the FASTQ file generated after base-calling. A barcode is called using an iterative consensus criterion starting at a minimum frequency of at least 30% for each position. If no base/multiple bases reach this threshold, an ambiguity ('N') is inserted (see Srivathsan *et al.*, 2021 for more details).

DNA-based species delimitation

Sequences were first blasted against the Sequence ID tool of GBIF (<https://www.gbif.org/tools/sequence-id>; accession date 13/01/2023), where sequences are queried against a 99% clustered version of the BOLD Public Database, and all non-spider sequences were removed for subsequent analyses. A custom R script (Salces-Castellano *et al.* 2021a) was then used to produce an UPGMA tree from pairwise K2P distances using an alignment of all sequences. A conservative maximum intraspecific divergence threshold of 6.8% was used to create individual alignments (see Emerson *et al.* 2017; Robinson *et al.* 2009). Under this divergence threshold, it is assumed that all individuals of a given presumed biological species (PBS) will be represented within a single lineage, but that a given lineage may comprise more than one PBS. We then took a conservative approach to validate, refine or revise provisional taxonomic assignments performed before DNA

extraction. The two most divergent sequences within each lineage were: (i) blasted against a local barcode reference library comprising 123 species of spider sampled within laurel forests of the same islands (Suárez *et al.* 2022) and 96 species previously sampled within open ecosystems characterised by the presence of *Euphorbia* (Borges *et al.* unpublished), and; (ii) submitted to the BOLD Identification Engine (accession date 29/01/2023). Based on sequence similarity to reference barcodes, we took the following approach to assign a taxonomic name to each PBS:

(i) If a species-level match was recovered with higher than 98% similarity, then the reference sequence taxonomy, even if incongruent with the provisional taxonomic assignment, was assigned unambiguously and considered to be validated.

(ii) If a species-level match was lower than 98%, but higher than 93.2%, then the reference sequence taxonomy was assigned, but not considered to be validated. In the case of incongruence between provisional taxonomic assignment and reference library taxonomic assignment, both reference libraries were queried for the presence of the provisionally assigned species. If the provisionally assigned species was present, then the provisional assignment was updated accordingly. However, if the provisionally assigned taxon was not included within either reference library, then the provisional taxonomic name was retained.

(iii) If a species-level match was lower than 93.2%, then the provisional taxonomic assignment was retained. Thus, while some of our provisional taxonomic assignments to species level may be correct, we consider them unsubstantiated in the absence of a barcode reference library match.

(iv) In the case of phylogenetically structured variation within a lineage segregating with different taxonomic assignments based on provisional taxonomic assignment or taxonomic assignment from the reference libraries, the lineage was accordingly divided into the corresponding species.

Following taxonomic assignment of PBS, dispersal ability was categorised following a family-level classification established by Carvalho & Cardoso (2014), based on the potential for juvenile spider stages to be passively dispersed by air currents, while suspended from silk threads, henceforth referred to as “ballooning”. All species were thus classified as either “ballooning” or “non-ballooning”.

Community composition and structure

Species richness and the proportion of endemic species and ballooning species were calculated for each site. Species richness (Chao index) and total number of endemic species were also estimated at both the ecosystem level and site level (`estimateR` function, `vegan` package; Oksanen *et al.* 2022). Additionally, species accumulation curves within each ecosystem were generated (`specaccum` function, `vegan` package; Oksanen *et al.* 2022). A generalised linear mixed model was implemented to compare estimated richness between ecosystems at the archipelago scale, implementing island as a random factor (`lmer` function, `lme4` package; Bates *et al.* 2015) and following a Gaussian error structure. At the within-island scale, generalised linear models (`glm` function, `stats` package) were fitted with a Gaussian error structure. To test for differences between ecosystems in the proportion of endemic species and ballooning species by site at the archipelago scale, a generalised linear mixed model was implemented with a binomial error structure and island as a random factor. At the within-island scale, generalised linear models were fitted with binomial error structure. Community dissimilarity matrices were estimated at the species level across all sites. Matrices were generated using total β diversity (Sorensen index, β_{sor}) and its additive turnover (Simpson index, β_{sim}) and nestedness (β_{sne}) components (`beta.pair` function, package `betapart`; Baselga & Orme 2012). Dissimilarity matrices were used for nonparametric multidimensional scaling (NMDS). Permutational ANOVAs were conducted over the community dissimilarity matrices to test differences between ecosystems using 999 permutations, with island (between ecosystems and within a same ecosystem) or site (within a same island and ecosystem) as grouping factors. To disentangle the contribution of different factors in the β_{sor} within ecosystems, Generalised Dissimilarity Models (GDM; Ferrier *et al.* 2007) were applied. A matrix of dissimilarity across sites was implemented as the response variables, and geographical distance and bioclimatic variables from the sampling sites were implemented as predictors. Environmental variables (the same 19 bioclimatic variables defined in WorldClim, Fick & Hijmans 2017) were downloaded at the finest resolution available (100 m) from CanaryClim (Patiño *et al.* 2023). Correlations between predictor variables were assessed using Pearson's rank correlation coefficient r , establishing $r < |0.7|$ as a threshold to avoid multicollinearity. Models were then fitted, setting 50 permutations to evaluate the models and variable significance (`gdm` function,

gdm package), to estimate variable importance (gdm.varImp function, gdm package), and to perform deviance partitioning (gdm.partition.deviance function, gdm package). Models were conducted for each ecosystem separately, both across and within islands. To test for differences in environmental heterogeneity between ecosystems, Principal Component Analyses (PCA) (dudi.pca function, ade4 package; Dray & Dufour 2007) were conducted both at the archipelago and the within-island scale using the bioclimatic variables that were not autocorrelated. Significant differences in the mean distance to the centroid between ecosystems were tested using the function betadisper (vegan package; Oksanen *et al.* 2022). Finally, to test for spatial structuring of the environmental heterogeneity, multiple regression on distance matrices (MRM) were assessed across the bioclimatic and geographic distances matrices (MRM function, ecodist package; Goslee & Urban 2007).

Geographical structuring of genetic variation

To test for the geographic structuring of genetic variation within PBS, the fixation index N_{ST} was calculated using SPAGeDI 1.5 (Hardy & Vekemans 2002). N_{ST} was calculated both among islands (each island is considered a population) and within individual islands (each sampling site is considered a population). Assuming that the genetic distance between populations of a given species increases as spatial distance increases (i.e. isolation by distance), heterogeneous spatial distances among sites within ecosystems may impact upon comparisons of N_{ST} between open and closed ecosystems. To address this, N_{ST} was also calculated within islands by selecting pairs of sampling sites that were separated by distances of approximately 3 km, 6 km, and 60 km. Within each pair of sampling sites within the same ecosystem, N_{ST} was estimated for all species sampled in both sampling sites, and the resulting set of fixation indices was compared between ecosystems for each spatial range using generalised linear models (glm function, stats R package), with a Gaussian error structure. Analyses were conducted across all species, and by partitioning species by dispersal ability (i.e., ballooners and non-ballooners).

Results

MinION read processing, species delimitation and taxonomic assignment

Within open ecosystems, a total of 10,007 individuals were collected, of which 10,000 were selected for sequencing, yielding a total of 8585 sequences, representing a sequencing success rate of 85.9%. A total of 164 lineages were recovered with divergences exceeding 6.8%, from which 168 PBS were inferred. Eighty-four PBS were identified to the species level (76 validated and eight not validated), with the remaining 84 identified to the genus ($n = 81$) or family ($n = 3$) level. Four lineages comprised two species and were split into the following eight PBS: (i) *Agyneta rurestris* (C. L. Koch, 1836) and *Agyneta fuscipalpa* (C. L. Koch, 1836); (ii) *Alopecosa gomeræ* (Strand, 1911) and *Alopecosa obscura* Schmidt, 1980; (iii) *Pulchellodromus punctigerus* (O. P.-Cambridge, 1908) and *Pulchellodromus wunderlichii* (Muster & Thaler, 2007); and (iv) *Walckenaeria gomerensis* Wunderlich, 1987 and *Walckenaeria cf. hierropalma* Wunderlich, 1987. For these four lineages, average divergences between species pairs were 4.6%, 4.9%, 4.6% and 6.6%, respectively. For the complete set of PBS, maximum intraspecific genetic divergences within PBS ranged from 0% (single haplotype) to 6.7%, with a mean of 2.33%. Among the 168 PBS obtained in the open ecosystems, 49 were also sampled in closed ecosystems (from Suárez *et al.* 2022), while the remaining 119 were exclusively sampled in the open ecosystems. Among all PBS, 75 were classified as having high dispersal ability (i.e., ballooner), with the remaining 93 having low dispersal ability (i.e., non-ballooner).

New species records and new species

Across all spider species sampled from open (this study) and closed ecosystems (from Suárez *et al.* 2022), a total of 5 species of spider are recorded for the first time for the Canary Islands; *Agyneta rurestris* (C. L. Koch, 1836), *Simitidion simile* (C. L. Koch, 1836), *Siwa dufouri* (Simon, 1874), *Thyene semiargentea* (Simon, 1884), and *Typhochrestus bogarti* Bosmans, 1990. Additionally, 14 species are recorded as new island-level records (Appendix S2). For 10 genera, the number of species recovered exceeds the known number of species inhabiting the Canary Islands, suggesting the presence of cryptic species: *Episinus* (two PBSs obtained vs. one species reported for the Canary Islands), *Hypsosinga*

(two vs. one), *Improphantes* (four vs. two), *Kochiura* (two vs. one), *Macarophaeus* (four vs. three), *Olios* (three vs. one), *Steatoda* (six vs. four), *Styloctetor* (two vs. one), *Zimirina* (ten vs. seven), and *Zoropsis* (two vs. one). Additionally, the recovery of eight species from the family Oonopidae without genus-level identification suggests further unreported species, as only four species are reported for the family Oonopidae in the Canary Islands. Five species within the genus *Dysdera* yielded species-level matches below 93.2%. The genus *Dysdera* is represented by 48 described species within the Canary Islands, of which 47 species are represented within BOLD, with only the troglobitic *D. volcanica* not being represented. Our dataset comprises five *Dysdera* species with low matching to BOLD (< 92%), with none of them being troglobitic. These five species likely represent new and undescribed species within the genus *Dysdera*. Three taxonomic species: *Dysdera silvatica* Schmidt, 1981, *Dysdera verneau* Simon, 1883, and *Minicia gomerae* (Schmidt, 1975), presented evidence for cryptic species. Individuals assigned to *Dysdera silvatica* segregated into two PBS, based on divergence above the 6.8% threshold. Three cryptic species are identified within each of the taxonomic species *D. verneau* and *M. gomerae*, as sampled individuals within each segregated into three PBS, with divergences of 6.9-10.6% and 8.2%-9.8%, respectively (see Appendix S3 for further details).

Community composition and structure

Species accumulation curves (Figure 2a) showed higher completeness within areas of closed ecosystem (completeness: 89.4%), with the curve being closer to a plateau. In contrast, the curve for open ecosystems arrived at a much earlier stage of decrease after an exponential phase (completeness: 71.7%). The proportion of singletons (i.e., species found in just one site) was higher in open ecosystems (29.8%, $n = 50$), compared to closed ecosystems (19.5%, $n = 24$) (Figure 2b). Estimated total and endemic species richness, together with proportions of endemic species and ballooning species per site can be found in Table S3. At the archipelago scale, estimated species richness per site was significantly higher in open ecosystems ($p < 0.001$), while the proportion of estimated endemic species was significantly higher in closed ecosystems ($p < 0.001$). There was no significant difference in the proportion of ballooning species between ecosystems ($p = 0.95$, Figure 2; Table S4).

At the within-island scale, significantly higher estimated species richness by site was found in open ecosystems for the islands of Tenerife ($p < 0.001$) and La Palma ($p < 0.001$), with La Gomera and El Hierro showing non-significant trends in the same direction (Figure S1; Table S5). The proportion of estimated endemic species was significantly higher within closed ecosystems in Tenerife ($p < 0.001$), La Gomera ($p = 0.001$), and La Palma ($p = 0.03$), but not El Hierro ($p > 0.05$) (Figure S1; Table S6). With regard to species-specific dispersal ability, there were no significant differences between ecosystems at the archipelago scale, or at the scale of individual islands for the proportion of ballooning species ($p > 0.05$) (Figure S1; Table S5).

Analyses of beta-diversity revealed a strong influence of species turnover, both between and within ecosystems, both at archipelago and island scales (Table S6), with overall dissimilarity values ranging from 0.375-0.888 (0.296-0.878 turnover component). Non-metric multidimensional scaling showed a primary clustering of communities by ecosystem (Figure 3a), and permutational ANOVAs consistently revealed significant differences between open and closed ecosystems. When spider communities are partitioned by dispersal ability, higher turnover is recovered within both ecosystems for non-ballooning species at the archipelago scale (Table S7). For both dispersive categories, there is a tendency for higher turnover at open ecosystems than closed ecosystems (Table S7). Permutational ANOVAs revealed significant clustering of communities by island for each ecosystem, for both dispersive categories, but with higher values of R^2 within closed ecosystems (Figure 3c,d). After assessing multicollinearity among the 19 bioclimatic variables of CanaryClim across sampling sites, six were retained: annual mean temperature, mean diurnal range, isothermality, annual precipitation, precipitation of driest month, and precipitation of warmest quarter. At the archipelago scale, there were no significant differences in the mean distance to the centroid of the PCA between ecosystems ($p = 0.10$) (Figure S2, Table S8). MRMs revealed higher spatial structuring of environmental heterogeneity within the closed ecosystems ($R^2 = 0.19$) compared to open ecosystems ($R^2 = 0.04$) (Table S9). At the within-island scale, mean distances to the centroid between ecosystems were significantly different, being higher in the closed ecosystems of Tenerife ($p = 0.04$), and in the open ecosystems of La Gomera and El Hierro ($p = 0.03$ and $p = 0.04$, respectively; Figure S2, Table S8), with no significant difference within La Palma ($p =$

0.76). MRMs recovered higher spatial structuring of environmental heterogeneity in closed ecosystems in all islands (Table S9).

GDM results at the archipelago scale showed that the full model accounting for all six environmental variables and geographic distance explained 43.91% and 63.65% of the deviance in open and closed ecosystems, respectively. Deviance partitioning revealed that pure geographic distance explained a comparable proportion of the deviance within each ecosystem (21.63% in open ecosystems and 24.3% in closed ecosystems), whereas climatic variables alone explained more of the deviance in open ecosystems (10.73%) compared to closed ecosystems (4.73%) (Figure 3b). At the island scale, the full model explained more of the deviance in open ecosystems than in closed ecosystems, as well as showing that climatic variables explained more of the deviance than geographic distance in all islands and ecosystems (Table S10).

Figure 2. Community comparisons between closed (dark grey) and open ecosystems (light grey) at the archipelago scale. **(a).** Species accumulation curves. **(b).** Bar plot showing frequencies of species as a function of the number of sites where present, in the closed (left) and the open ecosystems (right). Boxplots showing **(c)** differences in the estimated species per site, **(d)** differences in the proportion of estimated endemic species per site and **(e)** differences in the percentage of ballooning species per site, for the open ecosystem and the closed ecosystems.

Figure 3. **(a).** Non-parametric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) ordination for turnover (β_{sim}) and nestedness (β_{sne}) between ecosystems. Explained variation (R^2) and significance (p) of island as a grouping factor from the permutational ANOVAs over the community dissimilarity matrices are shown. **(b).** Venn Diagram for beta-diversity partitioning between environmental and geographic variables within each ecosystem. **(c).** Turnover (β_{sim}) across islands within the closed ecosystems partitioned by dispersal ability. **(d).** Turnover (β_{sim}) across islands within the open ecosystems subsetted by dispersal ability. TF = Tenerife, LG = La Gomera, LP = La Palma, and EH = El Hierro.

Geographical structuring of genetic variation

No significant differences in population structure within species were found between ecosystems at either the archipelago or within-island scales (Figure 4; Table S11, S12), except for El Hierro, with closed ecosystems having a significantly lower N_{ST} than open ecosystems ($p = 0.03$; Table S11). Partitioning spider communities by dispersal ability also

resulted in no statistical differences between ecosystems, except for non-ballooning species in El Hierro ($p = 0.02$; Table S12), which presented higher geographical structuring in open ecosystems. No significant differences between ecosystems were found by selecting pairs of sampling sites that were separated by distances of approximately 3 km, 6 km, and 60 km (Figure S3; Table S13).

Figure 4. Box-plot showing differences in N_{ST} for the overall spider species set (a-e) and subsetting (f-j) by dispersal ability between the closed (dark grey) and the open ecosystems (light grey). AR = archipelago, TF = Tenerife, LG = La Gomera, LP = La Palma, and EH = El Hierro. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, ns = not significant.

Discussion

Our results reveal strongly differentiated spider communities between open and closed ecosystems in the Canary Islands. We find that spider communities of open and closed ecosystems shared only 48 species (20%) of the 168 found in open ecosystems and 123 in closed ecosystems, despite close geographic proximity of open and closed sample sites in many cases. Significant clustering of spider communities by ecosystem was recovered by community composition analyses (Figure 3), revealing high levels of species replacement between the communities of both ecosystems. It has previously been demonstrated that climatic gradients within islands can be characterised by very differentiated invertebrate communities, comprising species with strong habitat specificity (Andújar *et al.* 2022; Lim

et al. 2022). Two contrasting but not mutually exclusive models can be evoked to explain habitat specificity. Under the niche conservatism model, colonisation of novel ecosystems will be restricted to taxa that are already preadapted to prevailing environmental conditions (i.e., environmental filtering). Under the niche lability model, however, colonisation is suggested to be facilitated by species within high climatic niche lability, or broad climatic tolerances followed by divergent ecosystem-specific selective pressures leading to isolation across ecosystems. Forty-three percent of spider genera are shared across both ecosystems (44 of 103), pointing to a model where either species within these genera with broad climatic tolerances have colonised across both ecosystems, and diverged within each, or where specialist species to one ecosystem have colonised and adapted to an alternative ecosystem. Both are consistent with the niche lability model. The lower percentage of species sampled across both ecosystems (20%), compared to the percentage of genera sampled across both (43%) highlights the role of evolutionary specialisation to habitat within the community assembly of spider species in the Canary Islands.

Disentangling the drivers of differing community structure between open and closed ecosystems

Open ecosystems, such as grasslands, prairies, and shrublands, often exhibit lower environmental stability compared to closed ecosystems like forests (Lin *et al.* 2020). They also typically display high spatial heterogeneity in terms of environmental diversity (Pausas & Bond 2020). While these distinctions are expected to influence the diversity and composition of communities within these ecosystems, identifying the mechanisms underlying such divergent biodiversity patterns between open and closed systems can be a challenging endeavour. Contrasting patterns of spider assemblages may potentially emerge through competing, but not necessarily exclusive, processes. The use of intraspecific genetic variation sampled across communities can provide a more nuanced understanding of community patterns and the ecological and evolutionary processes acting across open and closed ecosystems.

Environmental stability is associated with spatial structuring, both at the level of community composition, and at the level of genetic diversity within species, due to long-term persistence of populations and less dependency on a metapopulation dynamic of

migration and dispersal (Carnaval *et al.* 2009; Ribera & Vogler 2000). Environmental stability is also associated with less selective pressure for high dispersal ability, contrasting with lower environmental stability, which is expected to select for species with higher dispersal ability (Hof *et al.* 2006, 2012), as species with limited dispersal ability are more prone to extinction in such environments. Based on this, we hypothesised that if lower environmental stability within open ecosystems is a driver of contrasting spider community patterns between open and closed ecosystems: (i) open ecosystem species will present comparatively lower spatial genetic structuring both within and among islands, and; (ii) open ecosystem assemblages will be represented by proportionately more species with high dispersal potential. However, we found no significant differences between ecosystem type at the archipelago or within-island scales, for the geographic structuring of genetic variation within species (Figure 4). Statistical differences were found between ballooning and non-ballooning species, with dispersal limitation explaining some of the variation in the geographical structuring of genetic variation among species. However, we found no evidence for this relationship to vary between open and closed ecosystems, nor did we find a significant difference in the proportion of ballooning (higher dispersive) species between ecosystems (Figure 2, S1). Overall, our results do not support a primary role for differences in environmental stability driving contrasting diversity patterns between open and closed ecosystems.

Differences in spatial environmental heterogeneity between open and closed ecosystems could explain differences in their diversity patterns, through higher environmental diversity within open ecosystems contributing to higher habitat heterogeneity and diversity of ecological niche space, compared to closed ecosystems. Increased spatial heterogeneity in environmental variables within open environments may lead to more pronounced selection gradients for species traits, thus promoting higher community turnover, relative to closed environments. We hypothesised that if spatial environmental heterogeneity is an important driver of contrasting community patterns, a significantly greater proportion of the variance of spider community composition will be explained by environmental variation in open ecosystems at both archipelago and island scales. Consistent with our hypothesis, we found that bioclimatic variables explained more of the deviance in open ecosystems at all scales (Table S10). At the archipelago scale,

geography explained the highest deviance, as well as being the most important predictor for both ecosystems, and this was also reflected within the ordination analyses. This can be explained by strong isolation among islands by oceanic barriers to dispersal driving among island differences in community composition. Although the explained deviance of geographic distance was similar, the deviance explained by bioclimatic variables in open ecosystems was more than twice that in closed ecosystems. This difference was even more evident at the within-island scale, except within the island of La Palma. At the within-island scale, the deviance explained by bioclimatic variables was always higher than the deviance explained by geographic distance. The comparison between ecosystems revealed that, for all islands, with the exception of La Palma, the deviance explained by bioclimatic variables was higher in open ecosystems compared to closed ecosystems (Table S10). Both at the archipelago and at the within island scale, a higher heterogeneity of bioclimatic variables (higher value of R^2) was found in closed ecosystems (Table S9). Overall, these results place spatial environmental heterogeneity (i.e., differences in environmental variables across sites) as an important driver of contrasting spider community patterns between open and closed ecosystems in the Canary Islands.

Barcoding at scale for the joint understanding of community assembly and cryptic or unrecorded biodiversity

By applying multiplex barcoding to a sample of 10,000 spiders from different sites within open ecosystems of the Canary Islands, we were able to generate an unprecedented community-level barcode dataset, due to reduced investment in human resources and sequencing costs, in comparison with traditional Sanger sequencing approaches. DNA extraction, PCR amplification, DNA sequencing and sequence alignment took approximately 6 weeks for a single worker (DS). Previous work by us to obtain 2,663 barcode sequences using traditional Sanger sequencing (Suárez *et al.* 2022) was considerably more time-consuming, largely due to the nuances of editing and aligning individual Sanger sequences, and expensive. A per individual MinION sequencing cost of approximately 0.04-0.06 €, compared with a cost of approximately 3-4 € per individual for Sanger sequencing (Srivathsan *et al.* 2021), enabled us to sequence all sampled individuals,

as opposed to only sequencing a subsample of individuals (e.g., Emerson *et al.* 2017; Jiménez-García *et al.* 2023; Salces-Castellano *et al.* 2020, 2021; Suárez *et al.* 2022).

Augmenting the 8,585 sequences generated in this study for spiders sampled from open ecosystems, with 2,663 available sequences from closed ecosystems, reveals 15 cases (i.e., 6% of the 247 sampled species) of unrecorded and potentially new species. By using a conservative threshold of 6.8% divergence (Emerson *et al.* 2017) to delineate species boundaries, these 15 species are identified through the recovery of more species within their respective genera than have been inventoried in the Canary Islands (Gobierno de Canarias 2023) (see Appendix S3). Given that our threshold of 6.8% is conservative, 15 species can be considered a minimum estimate of unrecorded or new species. While the existence of new or unrecorded species is demonstrated, these 15 species will remain anonymous until their taxonomic assignment to the species level.

The genus *Dysdera* serves to highlight the value of local barcode reference libraries for the detection of new species. *Dysdera* is the most studied spider genus in the Canary Islands, due to its high endemic species richness (Macías-Hernández *et al.* 2016). Among the 47 described species, 46 are represented with barcode reference sequences on public repositories. However, five PBS were recovered with a species-level match lower than 92%, thus suggesting the existence of undescribed species. In addition to these five species, two taxonomic species (*Dysdera silvatica* Schmidt, 1981 and *Dysdera verneaui* Simon, 1883) were recovered as two and three independent PBS respectively, suggesting the existence of cryptic species. The presence of cryptic species is also inferred within the Macaronesian endemic species *Zoropsis rufipes* (Lucas, 1838). Our sampling revealed two different PBS that were assigned to *Z. rufipes*. High phylogeographic structure within one of the two *Z. rufipes* PBS was accompanied by five clades with divergences among them ranging from 5-6%, suggestive of further species-level differentiation. Our sampling revealed sympatry for two clades (uncorrected p-distance = 5.01%) at one site, thus providing the opportunity for directly testing the hypothesis of biological species using complementary nuclear genomic data (e.g., Cicconardi *et al.* 2010, 2013; Pérez-Delgado *et al.* 2022).

Perhaps the most surprising evidence for cryptic species comes from the genus *Steatoda*. Five different PBS were recovered, due to divergences exceeding the 6.8%

threshold, with all PBS taxonomically assigned to *Steatoda grossa* (C.L. Koch, 1838), which is listed as an introduced species within the Canary Islands. One PBS was found to be genetically identical to continental sequences of *S. grossa*, confirming its presence in the Canary Islands as an introduced species. However, the remaining four PBS derive from a more ancient colonisation of a *S. grossa* ancestor, as determined by a sister lineage relationship to continental samples of *S. grossa*, based on available sequences in BOLD (accessed 29/01/2023). The four PBS are each restricted to a single island, with one on La Palma, one on La Gomera, and two on Tenerife. Three of the four PBS were sampled in both ecosystems, and provide evidence for repeated structuring of population genetic variation by habitat, with significant values for N_{ST} by ecosystem in La Gomera (0.69) and Tenerife (0.32), and marginal significance in El Hierro (0.60). Thus, in addition to evidence for a history of cryptic speciation within the archipelago, PBS assigned to *S. grossa* also reveal habitat associated differentiation.

Taxonomic limitations and the need for barcode reference libraries

Understanding arthropod biology, ecology and conservation status remains limited due to their overwhelming diversity, and the taxonomic limitations associated with this diversity (Cardoso *et al.* 2011; Emerson *et al.* 2022). DNA barcoding can be extended to the delimitation of objective operational units (e.g., Hartop *et al.* 2022; Salces-Castellano *et al.* 2021; Suárez *et al.* 2022), even with low taxonomic expertise. However, in absence of taxonomic expertise, or reliable barcode reference libraries, objective operational units remain anonymous at the species-level. Thus, barcode reference libraries are an important pillar for species inventory, species discovery, and the identification of previously unrecorded species. Given that 100 of the 247 spider species within our dataset could only be identified to the genus or family level, it remains possible that some of these 100 species are also unrecorded or undescribed species (e.g., *Salticus* spp., *Setaphis* spp., *Scotognapha* spp., *Scytodes* spp., or *Zelotes* spp.). The uncertain taxonomic assignment of these 100 species further highlights the value and importance of barcode reference libraries. A complete reference library for recorded spider species in the Canary Islands, as is the case for the genus *Dysdera* (see above) would provide fully validated species-level taxonomic assignments for all sampled species. The notion of complete reference libraries is becoming

increasingly tractable, as access to barcode sequences from material stored in museums and natural history collections improves through HTS-based approaches (e.g., Hausmann *et al.* 2016; Hebert *et al.* 2013; Levesque-Beaudin *et al.* 2023; Raxworthy & Smith 2021). Any remaining species lacking a species-level taxonomic assignment could then be unequivocally identified as being either new species records (i.e., native or introduced species) or undescribed species. Distinguishing between non-native (introduced) and native species can potentially be inferred from patterns of barcode sequence relatedness (Andersen *et al.* 2019). However, this approach does not distinguish between native endemic and native non-endemic species. High barcode sequence similarity to mainland specimens (>99%) provides a reliable inference of species origin by introduction (e.g., Jiménez-García *et al.* 2023), and enabled us to identify five previously unrecorded introduced species of spider (Appendix S2). Native non-endemic species can similarly be identified when genus-level barcode libraries are fully sampled for all described species. Within such a framework, taxonomically unassigned lineages would be consistent with undescribed species.

Conclusions

Our results revealed higher species richness within an open ecosystem compared to a closed ecosystem, and higher turnover across sites within the open ecosystem, consistent with previous work (Lacasella *et al.* 2015; Malumbres-Olarte *et al.* 2021; Pitta *et al.* 2019). We find that higher turnover across sites in the open ecosystem can be explained by higher environmental heterogeneity across sites. In contrast, we find no support for a role for environmental stability in promoting higher turnover in the open ecosystem, as we found no significant difference between open and closed ecosystems for the geographic structuring of genetic variation within species. Further studies are needed to understand the generality of our findings, and we suggest that multiplex barcoding offers a cost effective and time efficient approach to achieve this.

Supplementary material

- [Appendix S1](#). Sampling protocol.
- [Appendix S2](#). New records.
- [Appendix S3](#). Cryptic diversity.
- [Figure S1](#). Box-plot showing differences for estimated species richness, proportion of estimated endemic richness, and proportion of ballooning species between ecosystems.
- [Figure S2](#). PCA and box-plot showing the mean distance to the centroid between ecosystems.
- [Figure S3](#). Box-plot showing differences in N_{ST} between ecosystems.
- [Table S1](#). Sampling sites and coordinates.
- [Table S2](#). Mean, maximum, and minimum geographic distances among sites on each island, and within each ecosystem within each island
- [Table S3](#). Total and estimated species and endemic species richness and percentage of ballooning species per sampling site.
- [Table S4](#). Generalised linear mixed models at the archipelago scale examining the effect of ecosystem and island on estimated species, and the proportion of endemic species richness and ballooner species.
- [Table S5](#). Multiple comparisons from generalised linear models examining the effect of ecosystem and island on estimated species richness, and the proportion of endemic species and ballooning species.
- [Table S6](#). Total beta diversity and its additive turnover and nestedness components for spider assemblages partitioned by ecosystem, and not considering differences in dispersal ability.
- [Table S7](#). Total beta diversity and its additive turnover and nestedness components for spider assemblages, partitioned by dispersal ability within each ecosystem.
- [Table S8](#). Comparison of mean distance to the centroid of the PCAs between closed and open ecosystems.
- [Table S9](#). Multiple Regression on distance Matrices between environmental and geographic distance matrices.
- [Table S10](#). Generalised Dissimilarity Models for both open and closed ecosystems.
- [Table S11](#). Generalised linear models at the archipelago scale examining the effect of ecosystem and dispersal ability on N_{ST} .
- [Table S12](#). Multiple comparisons from generalised linear models examining the effect of ecosystem and dispersal ability on N_{ST} .
- [Table S13](#). Multiple comparisons from generalised linear models examining the effect of ecosystem and dispersal ability on N_{ST} .

Appendix S1

Sampling protocol

To facilitate comparisons across different sites and islands within the open dry shrublands, a sampling protocol was designed, including a total sampling effort of 18 hours within each sampling site. After the completion of each sampling event, samples were labelled and stored in 100% ethanol at -20°C. From March to April, from 2019 to 2021, a total of 25 sampling sites were established and sampled across four of the Canary Islands (Tenerife - 9, La Gomera - 5, La Palma - 6, El Hierro - 5). The following sampling methods were applied (sampling effort in brackets):

- (i) *Active aerial sampling during the night*: hand collection assisted with pooter, vial, small brush and forceps of all specimens seen on leaves, trunks, soil, and under rocks or dead wood (4 h).
- (ii) *Foliage beating*: a 110 x 80 cm white sheet is used as a drop-cloth (beating tray), while a wooden pole of ca. 1 m is used to beat tree branches (4 h; 2h during day and 2h during night).
- (iii) *Foliage sweeping*: a round sweep net with an opening diameter of 30 to 50 cm is used to sweep bushes and herbs, using a white sheet to separate spider for collection (4 h; 2h during day and 2h during night).
- (iv) *Pitfall traps*: twenty-four pitfall traps are placed in two 12-metres-long parallel rows (12 each), spaced equidistantly, approximately 8 cm wide at the top and 12 cm deep. Traps are filled with 3 - 4 cm of 100% propylene glycol and left in the field for 14 days, with a protection cover from predation, inundation with rainwater, and unwanted vertebrate capture (6 h approximately).

Appendix S2

New records

Chorological data of new spider records are presented. For locality details see Table S1. Taxonomy and worldwide distribution follow World Spider Catalog (<https://wsc.nmbe.ch/>). Distributional data within the Canary Islands was consulted at the Biodiversity Data Bank of the Canary Islands (<https://www.biodiversidadcanarias.es/biota/>).

Family Araneidae

***Agalenatea redii* (Scopoli, 1763)**

EL HIERRO: Ermita de los Reyes, 24.III.2021, 1 *ex.*; Parque Eólico de Valverde, 23.III.2021, 1 *ex.*; El Golfo, 23.III.2021, 1 *ex.*

New record for El Hierro.

***Araneus bufo* (Denis, 1941)**

LA PALMA: El Tablado, 6.II.2020, 1 *ex.*; Barranco de Magdalena, 19.II.2020, 1 *ex.*; Puerto de Trigo, 3.III.2020, 9 *exx.*; Las Caletas, 5.III.2020, 4 *exx.*; Playa de Nogales, 3.III.2020, 20 *exx.*; El Porís, 5.III.2020, 14 *exx.*; La Salemera, 4.III.2020, 5 *exx.*; Tamanca, 4.III.2020, 17 *exx.*

EL HIERRO: Pedraje, 19.II.2020, 1 *ex.*; Hoya del Creal, 18.II.2020, 2 *exx.*; La Restinga, 24.III.2021, 6 *exx.*; Ermita de los Reyes, 24.III.2021, 8 *exx.*; Parque Eólico de Valverde, 23.III.2021, 12 *exx.*; El Golfo, 23.III.2021, 4 *exx.*; Sabinar, 24.III.2021, 12 *exx.*

New record for La Palma and El Hierro.

***Cyclosa insulana* (Costa, 1834)**

LA PALMA: La Salemera, 4.III.2020, 1 *ex.*

LA GOMERA: San Sebastián, 24.III.2021, 1 *ex.*; Tazo, 23.III.2021, 2 *exx.*; Tamargada, 4.III.2020, 2 *exx.*

New record for La Palma and La Gomera.

***Cyclosa maderiana* Kulczyński, 1899**

EL HIERRO: Pedraje, 19.II.2020, 5 *exx.*; Hoya del Creal, 18.II.2020, 21 *exx.*; Fayal, 10.III.2016, 1 *ex.*; Mencáfete, 10.III.2016, 31 *exx.*

New record for El Hierro.

***Siwa dufouri* (Simon, 1874)**

TENERIFE: Barranco de Igueste de San Andrés-1, 11.III.2019, 1 *ex.*

New record for the Canary Islands.

Worldwide distribution: Western Mediterranean.

Observations: The sequence matched with a 100% similarity to a sequence of an individual identified as *Siwa dufouri* by Luis Crespo (unpublished data). After its original description, this species has been rarely recorded, suggesting that this species is quite rare and with cryptic habits (Melic 2000).

Family Clubionidae

***Porrhoclubiona minor* (Wunderlich, 1987)**

EL HIERRO: Parque Eólico de Valverde, 23.III.2021, 2 *exx.*; El Golfo, 23.III.2021, 13 *exx.*

New record for El Hierro.

Family Gnaphosidae

***Leptodrassex hylaestomachi* (Berland, 1934)**

LA GOMERA: San Sebastián, 24.III.2021, 5 *exx.*; Tazo, 23.III.2021, 15 *exx.*; Altos de Hermigua, 22.III.2021, 6 *exx.*; Tamargada, 4.III.2020, 12 *exx.*; Alojera, 23.III.2021, 14 *exx.*

New record for La Gomera.

***Macarophaeus insignis* Wunderlich, 2011**

EL HIERRO: Ermita de los Reyes, 24.III.2021, 1 *ex.*; Parque Eólico de Valverde, 23.III.2021, 4 *exx.*

LA PALMA: Puerto de Trigo, 3.III.2020, 1 *ex.*; Las Caletas, 5.III.2020, 2 *exx.*; La Salemera, 4.III.2020, 1 *ex.*; Tamanca, 4.III.2020, 3 *exx.*

LA GOMERA: Tazo, 23.III.2021, 1 *ex.*; Tamargada, 4.III.2020, 1 *ex.*; Alojera, 23.III.2021, 1 *ex.*

New record for El Hierro, La Palma and La Gomera.

Family Linyphiidae

***Agyreta fuscipalpa* (C. L. Koch, 1836)**

LA GOMERA: San Sebastián, 24.III.2021, 3 *exx.*; Tazo, 23.III.2021, 6 *exx.*

New record for La Gomera.

***Agyreta rurestris* (C. L. Koch, 1836)**

TENERIFE: Barranco de Ijuana, 27.II.2013, 1 *ex.*; Barranco de los Pasos, 10.I.2014, 1 *ex.*; Barranco de San Andrés-1, 13.III.2019, 1 *ex.*

LA GOMERA: El Cedro, 28.II.2014, 1 *ex.*; Encima de Las Hayas, 27.I.2016, 1 *ex.*; Meseta de Vallehermoso, 15.III.2016, 1 *ex.*; San Sebastián, 24.III.2021, 2 *exx.*; Tazo, 23.III.2021, 6 *exx.*; Altos de Hermigua, 22.III.2021, 2 *exx.*

LA PALMA: Hilera de la Cumbre, 19.I.2017, 1 *ex.*; Puerto de Trigo, 3.III.2020, 1 *ex.*; Las Caletas, 5.III.2020, 3 *exx.*

EL HIERRO: La Restinga, 24.III.2021, 1 *ex.*; Ermita de los Reyes, 24.III.2021, 1 *ex.*

New record for the Canary Islands.

Worldwide distribution: Europe, Turkey, Caucasus, Russia (Europe to South Siberia), Iran, Central Asia, China, Korea.

Observations: Sequences matched with a 100% similarity to several sequences of *Agyneta rurestris* from Austria, Bulgaria, Egypt, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Russia, and Slovenia. This species showed 8 different haplotypes in a total of 23 individuals (98.9% pairwise identity) without any phylogeographic structure ($N_{ST} = 0$). The genus *Agyneta* in the Canary Islands comprises two species, *Agyneta fuscipalpa* (C. L. Koch, 1836) and *Agyneta canariensis* (Wunderlich, 1987). The latter has been found in laurel forest areas of Anaga and Garajonay, coinciding with sampling sites within our study. We haven't detected *A. canariensis* within our samples despite the high sampling effort conducted. Taking this into account, a potential synonymization of *A. canariensis* under *A. rurestris* should be further studied.

***Canariellanus arborensis* Wunderlich, 1987**

LA PALMA: Hilera de la Cumbre, 2.II.2017, 2 *exx.*; Lomo Oscuro, 2.II.2017, 1 *ex.*

New record for La Palma.

***Typhochrestus bogarti* Bosmans, 1990**

TENERIFE: Barranco de los Cochinos, 10.I.2014, 1 *ex.*

EL HIERRO: Fayal, 10.III.2016, 1 *ex.*

New record for the Canary Islands.

Worldwide distribution: Portugal, Spain, France, Morocco.

Observations: Sequences matched with a 99.7% similarity to four sequences of *Typhochrestus bogarti* from mainland Spain. This species showed three different haplotypes in a total of four individuals (99.8% pairwise identity) without any phylogeographic structure ($N_{ST} = 0.001$). The genus *Typhochrestus* in the Canary Islands comprises four species, all of them being single island endemics.

Family Salticidae

***Thyene semiargentea* (Simon, 1884)**

LA GOMERA: San Sebastián, 24.III.2021, 1 *ex.*; Tazo, 23.III.2021, 2 *exx.*

TENERIFE: Barranco de Igueste de San Andrés-1, 11.III.2019, 2 *exx.*; Barranco de Igueste de San Andrés-2, 11.III.2019, 7 *exx.*; Valle Brosque, 14.III.2019, 1 *ex.*

New record for the Canary Islands.

Worldwide distribution: Sudan, Uganda, Tanzania, South Africa.

Observations: Sequences matched with a 99.3% similarity to four sequences of *Thyene semiargentea* from Sudan, as well as with a 98.7% to two sequences identified at family level from Oman and France presumably belonging to *T. semiargentea*. This species showed three different haplotypes in a total of 13 individuals (99.8% pairwise identity) without any phylogeographic structure ($N_{ST} = 0$). The genus *Thyene* in the Canary Islands comprises the species *Thyene imperialis* (Rossi, 1846). Sequences matched with a 92% similarity to *T. imperialis* sequences from India, Israel, and Pakistan. Further studies are needed in order to revise whether reports from *T. imperialis* in the Canary Islands are a misidentification or, in fact, both species are co-occurring.

Family Theridiidae

***Cryptachaea blattea* (Urquhart, 1886)**

LA PALMA: Cubo de la Galga, 18.I.2017, 1 *ex.*; Hilera de la Cumbre, 2.II.2017, 1 *ex.*; Lomo Oscuro, 2.II.2017, 6 *exx.*; El Tablado, 6.II.2020, 4 *exx.*; Barranco de Magdalena, 19.II.2020, 1 *ex.*

LA GOMERA: Meseta de Vallehermoso, 15.II.2016, 2 *exx.*

New record for La Palma and La Gomera.

***Rhomphaea nasica* (Simon, 1873)**

EL HIERRO: Hoya del Creal, 18.II.2020, 2 *exx.*; Mencáfete, 10.III.2016, 6 *exx.*

New record for El Hierro.

***Simitidion simile* (C. L. Koch, 1836)**

TENERIFE: Barranco de San Andrés-1, 13.III.2019, 3 *exx.*; Barranco de Iguete de San Andrés-1, 11.III.2019, 1 *ex.*

New record for the Canary Islands.

Worldwide distribution: Europe, North Africa, Turkey, Israel, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Iran, Central Asia. Introduced to Canada.

Observations: Sequences matched with a 100% similarity to four sequences of *Simitidion simile* from the Netherlands, Germany, Slovenia, and mainland Spain, and with between 98 and 99% similarity to *S. simile* from Italy, Turkey, Georgia, France, Norway, and Canada. This species showed two different haplotypes in a total of four individuals (98.7% pairwise identity). The genus *Simitidion* in the Canary Islands comprises the species *Simitidion lacuna* Wunderlich, 1992. Further studies are needed in order to revise whether reports from *S. lacuna* in the Canary Islands are a misidentification or, in fact, both species are co-occurring.

Family Thomisidae

***Synema globosum* (Fabricius, 1775)**

EL HIERRO: La Restinga, 24.III.2021, 2 *exx.*; Ermita de los Reyes, 24.III.2021, 7 *exx.*; Parque Eólico de Valverde, 23.III.2021, 2 *exx.*; El Golfo, 23.III.2021, 14 *exx.*; Sabinar, 24.III.2021, 2 *exx.*

New record for El Hierro.

Appendix S3

Cryptic diversity

Data on potential cryptic diversity is presented and discussed. For locality details see Table S1. Taxonomy follows World Spider Catalog (<https://wsc.nmbe.ch/>). Distributional data within the Canary Islands was consulted at Gobierno de Canarias (2023).

Family Araneidae

Genus Hypsosinga

Hypsosinga albovittata (Westring, 1851) is a native non-endemic species present in El Hierro, La Palma, and La Gomera. It is the only species of the genus *Hypsosinga* inhabiting the Canary Islands. Two PBS previously identified as *H. albovittata* have been recovered, one inhabiting at Tenerife and the other one at El Hierro. Sequences from Tenerife matched with *H. albovittata* sequences from Alaska (USA) with 89.9% of similarity, while sequences from El Hierro matched with *H. albovittata* sequences from Alaska (USA) with 90.7% similarity. Overall, sequence relatedness suggests that *H. albovittata* in the Canary Islands represents either new undescribed endemic species, or either native or introduced described species that are not represented by a barcode sequence.

Family Dysderidae

Genus Dysdera

The genus *Dysdera* is one of the best known genera in the Canary Islands as a result of the long attraction that it has received due to their impressive adaptive radiation leading to 47 endemic species (Macías-Hernández *et al.* 2016). This results in a near complete barcode reference library (47 sequences on BOLD of a total of 48 described species). However, five PBS did not yield a high-similarity match (all were < 95%), suggesting potential undescribed species. In fact, two of these PBS were taxonomically examined and were confirmed to be new species yet to be described (Macías-Hernández, comm. pers.)

Dysdera silvatica Schmidt, 1981 is an endemic species from El Hierro, La Palma and La Gomera. Three different PBS were recovered, due to divergences exceeding the 6.8% threshold, with each presenting high or closest matching to *D. silvatica* sequences in BOLD (95-100%). Each PBS was sampled on a different island from which the species is known. Divergences suggest that *D. silvatica* should more correctly be considered as three different cryptic species.

Dysdera verneau Simon, 1883 is endemic to Tenerife, where it is distributed throughout the island. Within our dataset we have recovered three different PBS, one in three localities of western-Anaga, one in Chinobre (eastern-Anaga) and one in Agua García. All PBS showed a high match to *D. verneau* in BOLD (>99%). Divergences suggest that *D. verneau* should more correctly be considered as three different cryptic species.

Family Gnaphosidae

Genus Macarophaeus

Three species of the genus *Macarophaeus* are known to inhabit the Canary Islands, *Macarophaeus cultior* (Kulczynski, 1899), *Macarophaeus insignis* Wunderlich, 2011 and *Macarophaeus varius* (Simon, 1893). Within our samples 4 PBS with divergences exceeding 6.8% were assigned to this genus, two of them each being unequivocally assigned to the taxonomic species *Macarophaeus insignis* Wunderlich, 2011 and *Macarophaeus varius* (Simon, 1893). Those two PBS showed high values of N_{ST} ; 0.6863 and 0.8005 respectively, suggesting a strong inter-island structuring. Of the two remaining PBS, one is distributed in 10 localities within the four sampled islands and the other in four localities of Tenerife. Whether one of those PBS belongs to *M. cultior*, or both species are potentially undescribed or unrecorded species requires further attention.

Family Linyphiidae

Genus Improphantes

The genus *Improphantes* comprises two taxonomic species, endemic within the Canary Islands; *Improphantes furcabilis* (Wunderlich, 1987), distributed in El Hierro, La Gomera, La Palma, Tenerife, and Gran Canaria, and *Improphantes multidentatus* (Wunderlich, 1987), being present in Tenerife and Gran Canaria. Within our samples four lineages were recovered (i.e., exceeding 6.8% divergence). As we did not perform an examination of genital characters, each lineage was further considered as a PBS. *Improphantes sp1* (n = 8 sequences) was found in three localities of western Tenerife (Teno and Palo Blanco), *Improphantes sp2* (n = 19) was found in two localities of La Gomera, three localities of El Hierro and seven localities of Anaga (Tenerife), *Improphantes sp3* (n = 24) was found across eight localities of Anaga (Tenerife) and *Improphantes sp4* (n = 19) was found in four localities of La Gomera, two of La Palma and four of Tenerife (two in Anaga, one in Palo Blanco, and one in Barranco de San Andrés-3). Thus, in Palo Blanco both *Improphantes sp1* and *Improphantes sp4* co-occur. *Improphantes sp2* co-occurs with *Improphantes sp3* in Anaga and with *Improphantes sp4* in La Gomera. Whether those PBS represent true biological species or not can be tested by ddRADseq (see Pérez-Delgado et al., 2022). As morphological examination of genitalia was not carried out, and chorological data (i.e., island or area they inhabit) was not conclusive enough to identify species based on location, none of the lineages were assigned to known taxonomic species.

Genus *Minicia*

The genus *Minicia* comprises three endemic species within the Canary Islands. The species *Minicia gomerae* Schmidt, 1975 is distributed in El Hierro, La Gomera, and La Palma. Individuals parataxonomically assigned to *M. gomerae* were recovered as three PBS, one on each of the aforementioned islands, suggesting that there is cryptic diversity within *M. gomerae* and that it in fact represents three different species, one on each island.

Genus *Styloctetor*

The genus *Styloctetor* in the Canary Islands is represented by the native non-endemic *Styloctetor romanus* (Cambridge, 1872). Within our samples, two PBS were recovered, one assigned to *S. romanus* (96.6% match in BOLD to sequences from Germany) and another assigned only to the genus level. The latter was only found in the locality of Barranco de Carrizales, while *S. romanus* was present in almost all remaining localities and absent in Barranco de Carrizales, suggesting an undescribed species at that locality.

Family Oonopidae

The family Oonopidae in the Canary Islands comprises four species belonging to four different genera. Within our data, eight different PBS have been recovered, none of them identified at genus level due to low matches in the BOLD database (< 85%). There are 85 species and 24 genera of Oonopidae represented on BOLD, including two of the four reported genera for the Canary Islands (*Opopaepa* and *Orchestina*, accession date 09/11/2023). This suggests that the eight PBS sampled in this study may belong to unsequenced or even to undescribed genera.

Family Prodidomidae

Genus *Zimirina*

The genus *Zimirina* is composed of seven different species in the Canary Islands. However, within our samples we have detected ten different PBS, based on divergences exceeding 6.8%. The real number of species is likely higher, taking into account that only two of the seven known species are recorded within the islands we have sampled; i.e., *Zimirina cineris* Cooke, 1964 (Tenerife) and *Zimirina gomerae* (Schmidt, 1981) (Tenerife and La Gomera). Each PBS was sampled in a single island, with some sampled at just a single site. Only one site (San Sebastián, La Gomera) harbours more than one PBS. Taking into account that among the seven species that inhabit the Canary Islands, five are found in just one island (Gran Canaria), and the high number of cryptic diversity that we have detected, it seems likely that there is an even higher number of undiscovered species.

Family Sparasiidae

Genus *Olios*

The genus *Olios* in the Canary Islands comprises the endemic species *Olios canariensis* (Lucas, 1838), together with the native non-endemic *Olios argelasius* (Walckenaer, 1805). Within our samples, individuals parataxonomically assigned to *O. canariensis* were recovered as three PBS, due to divergences exceeding 6.8%, one distributed in Tenerife, one in La Gomera and one in La Palma. None can be assigned to *O. argelasius* due to substantial taxonomic differences, and no matches on BOLD higher than 90% with *O. argelasius*. It thus seems likely that classical taxonomy underrepresents true species richness.

Family Theridiidae

Genus *Episinus*

Episinus maderianus Kulczyński, 1905 is a Macaronesian-endemic species, and the only *Episinus* species inhabiting the Macaronesian archipelago. Individuals parataxonomically assigned to *E. maderianus* recovered were recovered as two PBS, with divergence between them exceeding 6.8%. One is distributed in Tenerife, La Gomera, and La Palma, with the other sampled in Tenerife, La Palma and El Hierro. As both PBS co-occur in seven localities their status as biological species can be directly tested in sympatry by ddRADseq.

Genus *Kochiura*

Kochiura aulica (C. L. Koch, 1838) is a native non-endemic species present at all islands within the Canary archipelago, being the only species for the genus *Kochiura* reported for the archipelago. Individuals parataxonomically assigned to as *K. aulica* were recovered as two PBS, with divergence between them exceeding 6.8%. One of them, recovered in all sampled islands, was 100% similar to sequences of *K. aulica* from mainland Spain, Turkey, Egypt, France, and Italy. The other one, recovered only in three localities of Tenerife and three of La Gomera, is only 88.9% similar to *K. aulica*, suggesting that it may belong to either an undescribed species or an unrecorded native or introduced described species without any reference barcode available.

Genus *Steatoda*

In the Canary Islands, four species of the genus *Steatoda* has been reported; the native non-endemics *Steatoda latifasciata* (Simon, 1873), present in the eastern islands, and *Steatoda nobilis* (Thorell, 1875), which is present in all islands, as well as the introduced species *Steatoda grossa* (C.L. Koch, 1838) and *Steatoda triangulosa* (Walckenaer, 1802). Within our sampling, two PBS were each unambiguously assigned to *S. grossa* (100% match in BOLD) and *S. nobilis* (100% match in BOLD). However, four additional PBS that were parataxonomically assigned to *S. grossa* were also recovered. Two were sampled in Tenerife, one in La Gomera and the other one in El Hierro. These four PBS were grouped together monophyletically with regard to related to *S. grossa* sequences from the continent. Overall, it suggests a high level of cryptic diversity within this clade. It is also notable that sequences within each PBS were grouped according to ecosystem type, suggesting ecologically-driven population genetic structure.

Family Zoropsidae

Genus *Zoropsis*

The genus *Zoropsis* comprises only one species in the Canary Islands, the Macaronesian endemic *Zoropsis rufipes* (Lucas, 1838), which is distributed across all islands except for Lanzarote and Fuerteventura. Two different PBS are recovered, with one being distributed across all sampled islands and one being found only in the locality of Pedraje (El Hierro). Uncorrected p-distances within the PBS distributed across all islands were close to the objective threshold set at 6.8%, thus suggesting a potential for cryptic species even within this PBS. Of special interest should be the island of El Hierro, with two lineages being paraphyletic and with co-occurrence in the locality of Mencáfete. Together with the unique PBS found at Pedraje, this places as a potential case of testing whether those PBS represent true biological species or not, through direct testing for cosegregation of nuclear genomic variation with mtDNA lineages.

Figure S1. Box-plot showing differences for estimated (chao) species richness (a-e), proportion of estimated (chao) endemic richness (f-j), and proportion of ballooning species (k-o) for spiders between the closed (dark grey) and the open ecosystems (light grey). ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05, ns = not significant.

Figure S2. PCA (top) and box-plot showing the mean distance to the centroid (bottom) for species of spider between closed forest (dark grey) and open dry shrublands (light grey). *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, ns = not significant.

Figure S3. Box-plot showing differences in N_{ST} for species of spider between closed (dark grey) and open ecosystems (light grey). Plots are clustered at spatial scales of (a) 3 km, (b) 6 km, and (c) 60 km. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$, ns = not significant.

Table S1. Sampling sites and coordinates.

Site code	Site name	Island	Latitude	Longitude	Ecosystem
AGU	Monte Aguirre	Tenerife	28.5334	-16.2698	Closed
ANE	Aguas Negras	Tenerife	28.54	-16.2251	Closed
CHI	Chinobre	Tenerife	28.559	-16.1736	Closed
CTE	Cabezo Tejo	Tenerife	28.562	-16.1714	Closed
IJU	Hoya de Ijuana	Tenerife	28.5602	-16.1692	Closed
MOQ	El Moquinal	Tenerife	28.5368	-16.3088	Closed
NIE	Barranco Nieto	Tenerife	28.5341	-16.3163	Closed
PIJ	Pijaral	Tenerife	28.552	-16.1892	Closed
TAG	Vueltas de Taganana	Tenerife	28.5443	-16.226	Closed
ZAP	Zapata	Tenerife	28.5355	-16.2962	Closed
COC	Barranco Cochinos	Tenerife	28.3228	-16.8234	Closed
PAS	Barranco Los Pasos	Tenerife	28.3349	-16.8316	Closed
AGA	Agua García	Tenerife	28.4579	-16.4041	Closed
PBL	Palo Blanco	Tenerife	28.3573	-16.5874	Closed
CUB	Cubo de La Galga	La Palma	28.7664	-17.7703	Closed
CUM	Hilera de la Cumbre	La Palma	28.6304	-17.8267	Closed
LOM	Camino del Lomito	La Palma	28.8038	-17.8203	Closed
NIQ	Niquiomo	La Palma	28.6003	-17.8103	Closed
TAB	El Tablado	La Palma	28.8184	-17.8833	Closed
MAG	Barranco de Magdalena	La Palma	28.8109	-17.9079	Closed
ACE	Los Acebiños	La Gomera	28.141	-17.2225	Closed
APA	Apartacaminos	La Gomera	28.154	-17.3008	Closed
CED	El Cedro	La Gomera	28.124	-17.224	Closed
EHA	Encima de Las Hayas	La Gomera	28.1355	-17.2773	Closed
FUE	Fuensanta	La Gomera	28.1453	-17.2522	Closed
MEV	Meseta de Vallehermoso	La Gomera	28.1539	-17.2934	Closed
REV	Reventón Oscuro	La Gomera	28.1221	-17.2138	Closed
FAY	El Fayal	El Hierro	27.7322	-17.9949	Closed
HDC	Hoya del Creal	El Hierro	27.806	-17.949	Closed
MEN	Mencáfete	El Hierro	27.7363	-18.0735	Closed
PDR	Pedraje	El Hierro	27.7338	-18.0231	Closed
IGU1	Barranco Iguete de San Andrés-1	Tenerife	28.5331	-16.1595	Open
IGU2	Barranco Iguete de San Andrés-2	Tenerife	28.5217	-16.1682	Open

Site code	Site name	Island	Latitude	Longitude	Ecosystem
SAN1	Barranco de San Andrés-1	Tenerife	28.5384	-16.2000	Open
SAN2	Barranco de San Andrés-2	Tenerife	28.5300	-16.1945	Open
SAN3	Barranco de San Andrés-3	Tenerife	28.5200	-16.1902	Open
BRO1	Valle Brosque	Tenerife	28.5189	-16.2280	Open
TEN1	Punta de Teno	Tenerife	28.3473	-16.9118	Open
TEN2	Infra El Palmar	Tenerife	28.3575	-16.8431	Open
TEN3	Barranco Carrizales	Tenerife	28.3197	-16.8677	Open
NOG	Playa Nogales	La Palma	28.7564	-17.7366	Open
PTR	Puerto de Trigo	La Palma	28.7267	-17.7363	Open
SAL	La Salemera	La Palma	28.5750	-17.7677	Open
CAL	Las Caletas	La Palma	28.5048	-17.8111	Open
POR	El Porís	La Palma	28.5311	-17.7968	Open
TAM	Tamanca	La Palma	28.5538	-17.8734	Open
TGA	Tamargada	La Gomera	28.1955	-17.2479	Open
AHE	Altos de Hermigua	La Gomera	28.1706	-17.1787	Open
TAZ	Tazo	La Gomera	28.1889	-17.3085	Open
ALO	Alojera	La Gomera	28.1753	-17.3161	Open
SSE	San Sebastián	La Gomera	28.1036	-17.1180	Open
EOL	Parque Eólico Valverde	El Hierro	27.7907	-17.9163	Open
RES	La Restinga	El Hierro	27.6600	-17.9756	Open
ERM	Ermita de los Reyes	El Hierro	27.7255	-18.1178	Open
SAB	Sabinar	El Hierro	27.7503	-18.1416	Open
GOL	El Golfo	El Hierro	27.7491	-18.0272	Open

Table S2. Mean, maximum, and minimum geographic distances among sites on each island, and within each ecosystem within each island. Values are expressed in km.

Ecosystem	Variables	Tenerife	La Gomera	La Palma	El Hierro
CLOSED	Mean	25.34	4.77	14.99	8.36
	Maximum	69.40	9.23	25.26	14.49
	Minimum	0.29	0.73	2.54	2.78
OPEN	Mean	36.82	11.62	15.84	14.14
	Maximum	76.37	20.98	28.89	22.61
	Minimum	1.08	1.68	3.24	3.62

Table S3. Total and estimated (chao) species and endemic species richness and percentage of ballooning species per sampling site.

Site code	Island	Ecosystems	Species richness	Species richness (Chao)	Endemics richness	Endemics richness (Chao)	Percentage of ballooners
AGU	Tenerife	Closed	33	36	21	22.5	48.5%
ANE	Tenerife	Closed	25	31.5	15	16.8	64.0%
CHI	Tenerife	Closed	27	35	17	21	59.3%
CTE	Tenerife	Closed	26	34	17	33	46.2%
IJU	Tenerife	Closed	22	26	15	16	59.1%
MOQ	Tenerife	Closed	33	42.5	22	29	54.5%
NIE	Tenerife	Closed	39	46.7	22	23.5	53.8%
PIJ	Tenerife	Closed	26	34.6	17	20	65.4%
TAG	Tenerife	Closed	25	36.3	13	15.5	64.0%
ZAP	Tenerife	Closed	31	46	26	29.5	61.3%
COC	Tenerife	Closed	41	43.2	22	23.5	56.1%
PAS	Tenerife	Closed	37	41.8	18	22	62.1%
AGA	Tenerife	Closed	33	36	21	22.5	48.5%
PBL	Tenerife	Closed	25	31.5	15	16.8	64.0%
CUB	La Palma	Closed	27	35	17	21	59.3%
CUM	La Palma	Closed	26	34	17	33	46.2%
LOM	La Palma	Closed	22	26	15	16	59.1%
NIQ	La Palma	Closed	33	42.5	22	29	54.5%
TAB	La Palma	Closed	39	46.7	22	23.5	53.8%
MAG	La Palma	Closed	26	34.6	17	20	65.4%
ACE	La Gomera	Closed	25	36.3	13	15.5	64.0%
APA	La Gomera	Closed	31	46	26	29.5	61.3%
CED	La Gomera	Closed	41	60	21	28	58.5%
EHA	La Gomera	Closed	42	50	24	30	54.8%
FUE	La Gomera	Closed	40	51	21	32.5	57.5%
MEV	La Gomera	Closed	37	45	20	28.5	51.4%
REV	La Gomera	Closed	34	56	19	26	51.4%
FAY	El Hierro	Closed	26	28.5	11	12	61.3%
HDC	El Hierro	Closed	25	30	12	13	57.7%
MEN	El Hierro	Closed	31	39	16	18.5	61.3%
PDR	El Hierro	Closed	24	33	14	16.5	66.7%
IGU1	Tenerife	Open	59	75	23	25.2	62.7%
IGU2	Tenerife	Open	56	63	25	29	53.6%

Site code	Island	Ecosystems	Species richness	Species richness (Chao)	Endemics richness	Endemics richness (Chao)	Percentage of ballooners
SAN1	Tenerife	Open	42	45.3	20	21.6	61.9%
SAN2	Tenerife	Open	40	42.7	19	20	57.5%
SAN3	Tenerife	Open	47	50.1	20	21.5	57.4%
BRO1	Tenerife	Open	42	48.6	16	24.5	54.8%
TEN1	Tenerife	Open	26	36	13	15	50.0%
TEN2	Tenerife	Open	47	55.5	18	19.3	53.2%
TEN3	Tenerife	Open	44	49.5	23	26.7	56.8%
NOG	La Palma	Open	38	57.2	16	18.5	52.6%
PTR	La Palma	Open	40	43	14	21.5	55.0%
SAL	La Palma	Open	43	66.8	20	26	46.5%
CAL	La Palma	Open	42	52.4	18	21	52.4%
POR	La Palma	Open	39	52	19	22	48.2%
TAM	La Palma	Open	43	52.3	19	27.5	53.5%
TGA	La Gomera	Open	45	80.2	20	35	60%
AHE	La Gomera	Open	43	44.7	23	24.6	65.1%
TAZ	La Gomera	Open	46	52.5	20	21.2	54.3%
ALO	La Gomera	Open	42	58	21	27	54.8%
SSE	La Gomera	Open	41	68.3	15	19	56.1%
EOL	El Hierro	Open	31	39.5	15	16.3	54.8%
RES	El Hierro	Open	23	25	11	12	47.8%
ERM	El Hierro	Open	34	42.3	14	17.5	61.8%
GOL	El Hierro	Open	34	44.4	16	24.5	61.8%
SAB	El Hierro	Open	19	34	11	22	52.6%

Table S4. Generalised linear mixed models at the archipelago scale examining the effect of ecosystem and island on estimated species, and the proportion of endemic species richness and ballooner species at the archipelago scale. Significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are highlighted in bold.

Response variable	Independent variable	LR Chisq	df	p-value
Species richness (Chao)	Ecosystem	28.631	1	<0.001
Proportion of endemics richness (Chao)	Ecosystem	34.699	1	<0.001
Proportion of ballooners	Ecosystem	0.0041	1	0.9487

Table S5. Multiple comparisons from generalised linear models at the island scale examining the effect of ecosystem and island on estimated species richness, and the proportion of endemic species and ballooning species. Significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are highlighted in bold. OPEN: open ecosystems, CLOS: closed ecosystems, EH: El Hierro, LP: La Palma, LG: La Gomera, TF: Tenerife.

Response variable	Contrast	LR Chisq	df	p-value
Species richness (Chao)	OPEN_EH – CLOS_EH	0.9914	1	0.3194
	OPEN_LP – CLOS_LP	19.615	1	<0.001
	OPEN_LG – CLOS_LG	3.2396	1	0.0719
	OPEN_TF – CLOS_TF	14.539	1	<0.001
Proportion of endemic richness (Chao)	OPEN_EH – CLOS_EH	0.4557	1	0.4987
	OPEN_LP – CLOS_LP	4.9972	1	0.0254
	OPEN_LG – CLOS_LG	10.1920	1	0.0014
	OPEN_TF – CLOS_TF	29.537	1	<0.001
Proportion of ballooners	OPEN_EH – CLOS_EH	0.0020	1	0.9642
	OPEN_LP – CLOS_LP	2.2311	1	0.1353
	OPEN_LG – CLOS_LG	0.5169	1	0.4722
	OPEN_TF – CLOS_TF	0.4608	1	0.4974

Table S6. Total beta diversity (Sorensen dissimilarity, β_{sor}) and its additive turnover (Simpson dissimilarity, β_{sim}) and nestedness (β_{sne}) components for spider assemblages at both the archipelago and island geographical scales, partitioned by ecosystem, and not considering differences in dispersal ability.

	Closed ecosystems			Open ecosystems		
	Total (β_{sor})	Turnover (β_{sim})	Nestedness (β_{sne})	Total (β_{sor})	Turnover (β_{sim})	Nestedness (β_{sne})
Archipelago	0.888	0.861	0.027	0.878	0.846	0.032
Tenerife	0.744	0.674	0.070	0.697	0.621	0.075
La Gomera	0.462	0.363	0.099	0.598	0.581	0.017
La Palma	0.455	0.391	0.064	0.518	0.491	0.027
El Hierro	0.375	0.296	0.078	0.557	0.443	0.114

Table S7. Total beta diversity (Sorensen dissimilarity, β_{sor}) and its additive turnover (Simpson dissimilarity, β_{sim}) and nestedness (β_{sne}) components for spider assemblages at both the archipelago and island geographical scales, partitioned by dispersal ability within each ecosystem.

		Total (β_{sor})		Turnover (β_{sim})		Nestedness (β_{sne})	
		No ballooning	Ballooning	No ballooning	Ballooning	No ballooning	Ballooning
Closed ecosystems							
Archipelago scale		0.742	0.597	0.641	0.477	0.101	0.120
	Tenerife	0.751	0.752	0.604	0.685	0.147	0.067
Island scale	La Gomera	0.486	0.494	0.291	0.402	0.195	0.092
	La Palma	0.447	0.501	0.304	0.436	0.143	0.065
	El Hierro	0.448	0.438	0.351	0.364	0.097	0.074
Open ecosystems							
Archipelago scale		0.895	0.863	0.869	0.813	0.026	0.050
	Tenerife	0.733	0.666	0.675	0.560	0.059	0.106
Island scale	La Gomera	0.538	0.671	0.497	0.639	0.041	0.032
	La Palma	0.548	0.489	0.444	0.538	0.044	0.057
	El Hierro	0.596	0.527	0.538	0.333	0.057	0.194

Table S8. Comparison of mean distance to the centroid of the PCAs between closed and open ecosystems. Significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are highlighted in bold.

Scale	Variable	df	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	F value	p-value
Archipelago	Groups	1	1.4723	1.4723	2.7841	0.101
	Residuals	54	28.5573	0.5388		
Tenerife	Groups	1	7.7015	7.7015	5.0643	0.035
	Residuals	21	31.935	1.5207		
La Gomera	Groups	1	3.2766	3.2766	6.9392	0.024
	Residuals	10	4.7219	0.4722		
La Palma	Groups	1	0.0721	0.0721	0.097	0.762
	Residuals	10	7.4307	0.7431		
El Hierro	Groups	1	2.9409	2.9409	5.6577	0.048
	Residuals	7	3.6386	0.5198		

Table S9. Multiple Regression on distance Matrices (MRMs) between environmental and geographic distance matrices in closed and open ecosystems. Significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are highlighted in bold.

Scale	Ecosystem	R ²	F	p-value
Archipelago	Open	0.0362	11.1991	0.007
	Closed	0.1868	108.3771	<0.001
Tenerife	Open	0.1884	7.8944	0.02
	Closed	0.6709	181.4471	<0.001
La Gomera	Open	0.0016	0.0125	0.923
	Closed	0.4009	12.7194	0.003
La Palma	Open	0.0033	0.0429	0.812
	Closed	0.0798	1.1274	0.253
El Hierro	Open	0.0126	0.1023	0.806
	Closed	0.0856	0.3743	0.852

Table S10. Generalised Dissimilarity Models for both open and closed ecosystems at the archipelago and within-island scales. Geographic variable is expressed as the geographic distance across sites while the climatic variable is a combination of the six significant bioclimatic variables extracted from CanaryClim. BIO1: annual mean temperature, BIO2: mean diurnal range, BIO3: isothermality, BIO12: annual precipitation, BIO14: precipitation of driest month, BIO18: precipitation of warmest quarter.

Scale	Ecosystem	Variable	% deviance explained	I-spline	Predictor importance	Predictor p-value	
Archipelago	Open	BIO1		0.064	1.163	0.46	
		BIO2		0	NA	NA	
		BIO3		0.269	8.644	0.34	
		BIO12		0.041	1.363	0.68	
		BIO14		0.083	2.911	0.36	
		BIO18		0	NA	NA	
		Climatic	10.73				
	Geographic	21.63	0.352	50.085	0		
	Full model	43.91					
	Unexplained	56.09					
	Closed	BIO1			0.051	0.377	0.58
		BIO2			0.028	0.193	0.56
		BIO3			0.121	0.839	0.32
		BIO12			0.024	0.173	0.78
BIO14				0.025	0.205	0.72	
BIO18				0	NA	NA	
Climatic		4.73					
Geographic	24.3	0.528	38.101	0			
Full model	63.65						
Unexplained	36.35						

Scale	Ecosystem	Variable	% deviance explained	I-spline	Predictor importance	Predictor p-value
Tenerife	Open	BIO1		0	NA	NA
		BIO2		0	NA	NA
		BIO3		0	NA	NA
		BIO12		0.065	1.603	0.54
		BIO14		0	NA	NA
		BIO18		0.446	33.619	0.38
		Climatic	38.77			
	Geographic	4.1	0.137	4.81	0.12	
	Full model	80.14				
	Unexplained	19.86				
	Closed	BIO1		0.075	3.449	0.24
		BIO2		0.363	3.449	0
		BIO3		0	NA	NA
		BIO12		0	NA	NA
BIO14			0.057	0.237	0.78	
BIO18			0.008	0.603	0.48	
Climatic		25.87				
Geographic	0	0.009	0.313	0.82		
Full model	69.13					
Unexplained	30.87					

Scale	Ecosystem	Variable	% deviance explained	I-spline	Predictor importance	Predictor p-value	
La Gomera	Open	BIO1		0.099	1.173	0.82	
		BIO2		0	NA	NA	
		BIO3		0.242	19.439	0.1	
		BIO12		0.353	22.211	0.32	
		BIO14		0.061	1.824	0.88	
		BIO18		0	NA	NA	
		Climatic	91.66				
	Geographic	3.49	0.191	3.18	0.38		
	Full model	95.15					
	Unexplained	4.85					
	Closed	BIO1			0.102	15.256	0.32
		BIO2			0.231	49.599	0.32
		BIO3			0	NA	NA
		BIO12			0	NA	NA
BIO14				0	NA	NA	
BIO18				0.019	0.466	0.64	
Climatic		68.94					
Geographic	0	0	NA	NA			
Full model	74.33						
Unexplained	25.67						

Scale	Ecosystem	Variable	% deviance explained	I-spline	Predictor importance	Predictor p-value	
La Palma	Open	BIO1		0	NA	NA	
		BIO2		0	NA	NA	
		BIO3		0.084	9.985	0.3	
		BIO12		0	NA	NA	
		BIO14		0.211	10.341	0.46	
		BIO18		0	NA	NA	
	Climatic	46.89					
	Geographic	3.49	0.166	17.36	0.08		
	Full model	91.82					
	Unexplained	8.18					
	Closed	BIO1			0.305	90.674	0.28
		BIO2			0.026	4.098	0.74
		BIO3			0.069	2.268	0.72
BIO12				0.013	1.409	0.66	
BIO14				0	NA	NA	
BIO18				0	NA	NA	
Climatic		65.1					
Geographic		0	0	NA	NA		
Full model	70.9						
Unexplained	29.1						

Scale	Ecosystem	Variable	% deviance explained	I-spline	Predictor importance	Predictor p-value	
El Hierro	Open	BIO1		0	NA	NA	
		BIO2		0.284	18.254	0.42	
		BIO3		0.464	36.917	0.18	
		BIO12		0.098	1.418	0.22	
		BIO14		0.066	0.613	0.24	
		BIO18		0.07	0.376	0.62	
		Climatic	97.95				
	Geographic	0.61	0.095	0.555	0.48		
	Full model	99.62					
	Unexplained	0.38					
	Closed	BIO1			0	NA	NA
		BIO2			0.059	10.567	0.8
		BIO3			0	NA	NA
		BIO12			0	NA	NA
BIO14				0	NA	NA	
BIO18				0.065	45.166	0.4	
Climatic		NA					
Geographic	NA	0.046	35.718	0.6			
Full model	47.2						
Unexplained	52.8						

Table S11. Generalised linear models at the archipelago scale examining the effect of ecosystem and dispersal ability on N_{ST} across different scales (across islands and across sites). Significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are highlighted in bold.

Scale	Independent variable	LR Chisq	df	p-value
Archipelago	Ecosystem	0.1917	1	0.6615
	Dispersal	6.5523	1	0.0105
	Ecosystem*Dispersal	0.1091	1	0.7411
Tenerife	Ecosystem	0.0635	1	0.8011
	Dispersal	16.6945	1	<0.001
	Ecosystem*Dispersal	0.7142	1	0.3980
La Gomera	Ecosystem	4.074	1	0.0435
	Dispersal	14.9754	1	<0.001
	Ecosystem*Dispersal	0.0628	1	0.8021
La Palma	Ecosystem	1.8277	1	0.1764
	Dispersal	1.9886	1	0.1585
	Ecosystem*Dispersal	0.0224	1	0.8810
El Hierro	Ecosystem	4.9337	1	0.0263
	Dispersal	7.9571	1	0.0048
	Ecosystem*Dispersal	5.2247	1	0.0223

Table S12. Multiple comparisons from generalised linear models examining the effect of ecosystem and dispersal ability on N_{ST} . Significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are highlighted in bold. OPEN: open ecosystems, CLOS: closed ecosystems, Ball: balloner, NoBall: no balloner, AR: archipelago, EH: El Hierro, LP: La Palma, LG: La Gomera, TF: Tenerife.

Scale	Contrast	Estimate	SE	t.ratio	p-value
AR	Ball_OPEN-Ball_CLOS	-0.043	0.0783	-0.549	0.9468
	NoBall_OPEN-NoBall_CLOS	0.001	0.1043	0.001	1.000
	Ball_OPEN-NoBall_OPEN	-0.179	0.081	-2.205	0.1288
	Ball_CLOS-NoBall_CLOS	-0.1365	0.1018	-1.341	0.5392
TF	Ball_OPEN-Ball_CLOS	0.0372	0.0927	0.402	0.9779
	NoBall_OPEN-NoBall_CLOS	-0.076	0.097	-0.785	0.8610
	Ball_OPEN-NoBall_OPEN	-0.223	0.082	-2.723	0.0385
	Ball_CLOS-NoBall_CLOS	-0.336	0.106	-3.161	0.0115
LG	Ball_OPEN-Ball_CLOS	0.137	0.096	1.425	0.4889
	NoBall_OPEN-NoBall_CLOS	0.176	0.1212	1.451	0.4729
	Ball_OPEN-NoBall_OPEN	-0.314	0.1020	-3.076	0.0162
	Ball_CLOS-NoBall_CLOS	-0.275	0.116	-2.361	0.0956
LP	Ball_OPEN-Ball_CLOS	0.099	0.091	1.095	0.6943
	NoBall_OPEN-NoBall_CLOS	0.079	0.099	0.807	0.8507
	Ball_OPEN-NoBall_OPEN	-0.084	0.082	-1.028	0.7340
	Ball_CLOS-NoBall_CLOS	-0.104	0.107	-0.977	0.7631
EH	Ball_OPEN-Ball_CLOS	0.011	0.111	0.103	0.9996
	NoBall_OPEN-NoBall_CLOS	0.388	0.122	3.186	0.0153
	Ball_OPEN-NoBall_OPEN	-0.367	0.101	-3.630	0.0048
	Ball_CLOS-NoBall_CLOS	0.009	0.130	0.074	0.9999

Table S13. Generalised linear models at the archipelago scale examining the effect of ecosystem and dispersal ability on N_{ST} across different distance ranges. Significant p-values ($p < 0.05$) are highlighted in bold.

Response variable	Independent variable	LR Chisq	df	p-value
N_{ST} (subset 3 Km)	Ecosystem	0.0616	1	0.8040
	Dispersal	0.3154	1	0.5744
	Ecosystem*Dispersal	1.9322	1	0.1645
N_{ST} (subset 6 Km)	Ecosystem	1.9463	1	0.1630
	Dispersal	0.4952	1	0.4816
	Ecosystem*Dispersal	0.0005	1	0.9830
N_{ST} (subset 60 Km)	Ecosystem	0.6039	1	0.4371
	Dispersal	7.6415	1	0.0057
	Ecosystem*Dispersal	0.0039	1	0.9504

General discussion

Dispersal ability structuring biodiversity

There is a growing body of evidence for adaptive radiations in oceanic archipelagos (e.g., Carson & Kaneshiro 1976; Gillespie *et al.* 1994; Losos 1997; Rees *et al.* 2001; Witter & Carr 1988), in which ecological adaptation plays an important role such that species evolve to exploit different parts of the environment (Losos & Ricklefs 2009). However, the extent to which ecology is the driver of initial cladogenesis is often assumed rather than tested, and there is evidence that geographic isolation may be a necessary precursor for the establishment of reproductively isolated gene pools, which may subsequently adaptively diverge through divergent ecological conditions (Goodman *et al.* 2012; Rundell & Price 2009). Non-adaptive pathways to speciation in insular taxa through geographic isolation are thus of particular interest, but have received only limited attention. In this thesis, by applying a standardised sampling protocol modified from Emerson *et al.* (2017), we have been able to characterise spider communities, and genetic variation within their constituent species, across two contrasting habitats on four of the westernmost Canary Islands. Variation in dispersal ability among species, which may promote geographic isolation, and ultimately non-adaptive speciation, has been used to understand the role of dispersal ability in community assembly and structure. Dispersal ability is known to minimise competition and inbreeding, while also allowing individuals to encounter new patches of habitat for resource exploitation (Bowler & Benton 2005), thus having major effects on individual fitness, population dynamics and species distributions. Within the context of this thesis, we have found that ballooning, i.e., the dispersal over long distances via passive transport in air currents, has significant effects on the geographical structuring of genetic variation, as well as on the structuring of biodiversity, both within and between habitats.

Using an assembly of beetle communities within the Canary laurel forests (Salces-Castellano *et al.* 2021a) it was previously found that non-dispersive lineages (wingless species) display higher levels of geographic genetic structuring between islands and between sites within a given island, compared to dispersive lineages (winged species) suggesting that dispersal limitation leads to geographic isolation. In this thesis, by extending the taxonomic scope of Salces-Castellano *et al.* (2021) with data from spiders, and by estimating mean and maximum node divergences within genera using all available

mitochondrial data from public repositories for endemic species of beetle and spider from the Canary Islands, together with the number of endemic species per genus as a proxy for diversification rate, we have found that: (i) non-dispersive lineages show higher levels of geographic genetic structuring; (ii) non-dispersive lineages have on average more species per genus than dispersive ones, and; (iii) non-dispersive lineages show higher rates of diversification and more recent speciation events, when compared to dispersive lineages. Overall, within this thesis an important role for non-adaptive speciation is supported, where geographic isolation leads to genetic structuring and, ultimately, is translated into species formation. This process is especially acute for non-dispersive taxa, for which a higher extinction rate is also inferred.

While our results are robust, it should be noted that there are likely power limitations within our dataset due to taxonomic assignment limitations, due to limited taxonomic resources and the incompleteness of the regional barcode reference libraries. Regarding the analyses of diversification rate, which included all available mitochondrial data from public repositories, from a total of 47 spider and 198 beetle genera represented by at least two endemic species, only 29 (61.7%) and 72 (36.3%), respectively, had available sequences for at least two species, and were thus included in the analyses. Additionally, across all genera included in the analyses, one third of endemic species were not represented in public repositories, resulting in a sampling completeness of only 66%. With an increasingly more complete reference library, we would expect greater power to detect significant differences across both orders, due to increased sample size of genera, and species within genera. In order to avoid overestimating MRCA node ages for genera that comprised non-monophyletic endemic species, i.e., multiple colonisations within a same genus, if a given genus comprised more than one subgenus with mainland relatives, subgenera were analysed independently. An increasingly complete reference library is also likely to provide a more objective understanding of how genera are partitioned by independent colonisation events. Although the use of subgenus affiliation decreases this issue, many beetle genera are not structured into subgenera, and subgenera are largely non-existent in spider taxonomy. A complete genus-level alignment would identify monophyletic clades within the Canary Islands, through sister lineage relationships to non-

Canary Island taxa, thus allowing Canary Island lineages of independent origins to be partitioned accordingly. Faced with reference library limitations, the significant differences in beetle lineages and non-significant trends in spider ones are strong arguments pointing to higher speciation and extinction rates within non-dispersive taxa, while also highlighting the potential for further investigation. Our analyses comprised multiple independent genus-level alignments that comprised one sequence per species. Estimating diversification rates within genera using well resolved (i.e., multigene) phylogenies could complement the analyses and results presented here by comparing across genera that are fixed for alternative dispersal types, or comparing rates within genera with both dispersal types. This second options is more achievable within the order Coleoptera, where several genera having both winged and wingless species (e.g., *Trechus*, *Philorhizus*, *Psylliodes*, *Longitarsus*, *Rhopalomesites*, *Oxypoda*), potentially incorporating approaches such as Bayesian analysis of macroevolutionary mixtures (BAMM), which jointly estimates the number of distinct evolutionary rate regimes across a phylogenetic tree and the speciation and extinction rates within each of the regimes (Harvey *et al.* 2017). Such genus-level approaches may allow for a more information rich and direct comparison between population genetic differentiation (estimated with N_{ST}) and speciation rate at the species-scale, but will require a concerted effort to achieve the sampling needed.

Dispersal limitation may also have major effects on community assembly. From a neutral perspective, species that have high dispersal ability are more prone to be widespread (Gaston 1994), as individuals are more able to colonise favourable habitat patches for resource exploitation. In this thesis, at the within-ecosystem scale, we have found that although there were no significant differences in mean abundance per site between dispersive categories, there was a significant difference in the number of occupied islands, with dispersive species being more widespread. This was also supported with abundance-occupancy analyses, which showed that for a given value of local abundance, occupancy was greater for dispersive than for non-dispersive species. At the scale of both ecosystems (i.e., dry shrublands and laurel forests), there were no significant differences between ecosystems for the proportion of dispersive species per site. Also, higher turnover values were recovered in both ecosystems for non-dispersive species. Overall, this suggests a

model where environmental filtering structures communities at the scale of both ecosystems, with few species shared across ecosystems. However, within each ecosystem at the within-island scale, neutral processes structure communities similarly, with dispersive species being more widespread across sites, while non-dispersive are constrained to a smaller number of sites, which translates into higher levels of turnover in the latter. Within our dataset we found a low number of species being shared across ecosystems (ca. 20%) whereas when accounting for genera, the percentage was double the number of species (ca. 40%). Taking advantage of the sharp environmental gradient between open shrublands and laurel forests, and the results presented in this thesis, both variation in species range size and speciation across environmental gradients are fertile areas for further investigation. By more densely sampling across environmental gradients encompassing both open dry shrublands and laurel forests, to also include intermediate stages (i.e., ecotones), more precise community composition across the environmental gradient may be captured. We hypothesise that dispersive taxa will be present along such environmental gradients, but with higher abundance within their climatic optima. In line with the findings of this thesis, we expect that non-dispersive taxa will present lower occupancy across sites within the same ecosystem, with a higher tendency for presence in only one ecosystem. We also hypothesise that turnover across the environmental gradient will be greater as we move forward to the ecotone. Our results also enable us to speculate about speciation across an environmental gradient, for which hypotheses can be put forward. It has been mathematically demonstrated that speciation can occur along an environmental gradient as a function of the steepness of the gradient and individual dispersal distances, with speciation being more likely when the gradient is steep, and dispersal is limited (Doebeli & Dieckmann 2002). We thus expect higher speciation rates in non-dispersive taxa compared to dispersive species. To test this prediction, species-pairs evolving from the same ancestor should be candidates for an intensive sampling across the elevational gradient. Taking advantage of the relative accessibility of multi-locus nuclear genomic SNP data (e.g., Bougie *et al.* 2021; Burns *et al.* 2017; Ivanov *et al.* 2018, 2021, 2023), complementary indices can be estimated, such as directionality of gene flow (to test whether open habitats are source-sink of forests), date of divergence (to test whether non-dispersive taxa diverged

more recently than dispersive lineages, following the assumptions of Chapter I), or potential secondary contact between sister-species at ecotones.

Massive multi-locus sequencing and integrative taxonomy aiding species discovery

Reduced representation genome sequencing, such as double-digest restriction site associated DNA sequencing (ddRAD-seq; Peterson *et al.* 2012), by potentially yielding data from thousands of loci, offers the opportunity to quantify individual relatedness, population genetic structure, and demographic history, with only a few individuals per population (e.g., García-Olivares *et al.* 2019; Mastretta-Yanes *et al.* 2015; Salces-Castellano *et al.* 2021b). Such data also facilitate direct testing of the biological species concept (Mayr 1942) when divergent mtDNA divergent lineages occur in sympatry (e.g., Pérez-Delgado *et al.* 2022). In the dataset generated for this thesis, there are three cases of genera with more PBS recovered than taxonomic species reported (i.e., lineages exceeding the 6.8% threshold for species delimitation) for the Canary Islands, and for which all taxonomic species were recovered in the sampling. Within the genera *Episinus*, *Improphantes* and *Zoropsis*, all taxonomically described species were sampled, but with multiple PBS assigning to the same taxonomic species. These three cases represent candidates for direct testing of the species-level significance of divergent mtDNA lineages that assign into the same taxonomic species, as they can be found sympatrically within sites. Testing for the cosegregation of nuclear genomic variation with mtDNA lineages in sympatry (e.g., ddRAD-seq data, see Pérez-Delgado *et al.* 2022) will determine if there is reproductive isolation between mtDNA lineages, and thus the presence of new species requiring formal taxonomic treatment.

The case of *Zoropsis* is one of the most striking, with two different PBS inhabiting the island of El Hierro, one of them exclusively there and the other also distributed on the islands of Tenerife, La Gomera, La Palma, and El Hierro. In the latter case, there are two divergent clades found in El Hierro, co-existing in sympatry at one site (uncorrected p-distance = 5.01%; Figure 1). This results in potentially three endemic species in the youngest island of the Canary archipelago. By analysing SNP data from potentially thousands of loci across the nuclear genome for specimens from El Hierro, it would be

possible to directly test if divergent mtDNA lineages represent biological species and infer the historical biogeographical history of the genus on El Hierro, for which mitochondrial data suggests three independent colonisations (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Maximum-Likelihood tree of 418 bp of the mtDNA COI gene of the *Zoropsis rufipes*-complex. Clades from La Gomera, Tenerife, and La Palma have been collapsed. Two sequences belonging to *Zoropsis media* and *Zoropsis spinimana* were used as outgroups. Colours of sampling sites correspond to genetic lineages shown in the tree. Photo of *Zoropsis rufipes* courtesy of Pedro Oromí.

Our mtDNA sequencing results reveal another interesting candidate for follow up work with nuclear genomic data, the genus *Steatoda*. Although parataxonomically all individuals were assigned to the introduced species *S. grossa*, mtDNA data suggests the existence of four different, and most likely endemic species, due to the discovery of four lineages exceeding our 6.8% threshold. Species were restricted to single islands and, within each island, mtDNA variation was structured by ecosystem type, thus displaying what appears to be ecologically driven phylogenetic structure (Figure 2). This complex represents fertile ground for testing a hypothesis of parallel adaptation to contrasting bioclimatic conditions. Whether dry shrubland populations evolved from the laurel forest populations, or vice versa, or that both emerged from a more generalist species inhabiting both ecosystems, could be assessed by examining the directionality of gene flow between ecosystems within each PBS. This could also allow for the estimation of lineage divergence times and potential secondary contact. Additional PBS presenting evidence for habitat-associated structuring of genetic variation (e.g., *Apostenus annulipedes*, *Alopecosa kulczynskii*, *Dysdera gomerensis*, *Lathys dentichelis*) could also be leveraged as independent case studies for a comparative analysis of adaptive evolution change across a shared environmental gradient.

Figure 2. Maximum-Likelihood tree of 418 bp of the mtDNA COI gene of the *Steatoda grossa* complex. Lineages comprising sequences from *S. nobilis* and *S. grossa* (*sensu stricto*) have been collapsed. A sequence of *Steatoda triangulosa* was used as an outgroup. Green-labelled sequences belong to specimens collected in the laurel forest whereas orange-labelled ones were collected in the open dry shrubland. Individual PBS are highlighted within blue shaded boxes. Photo of *Steatoda grossa* courtesy of Jørgen Lissner.

In addition to the aforementioned taxa, several other PBS were revealed to be phylogenetically structured by island ($N_{ST} > 0.5$), with divergences below the 6.8% threshold but exceeding the less conservative threshold of 2% (Hebert *et al.* 2003). This is exemplified by *Araniella maderiana* (ca. 3% divergence), *Cheiracanthium canariense* (ca. 3.5% divergence), *Enoplognatha sattleri* (ca. 3% divergence), *Lathys dentichelis* (ca. 5% divergence) and *Metellina minima* (ca. 3% divergence). Thus, each PBS is composed of multiple isolated insular populations and each population could conceptually be considered as single evolutionary unity due to an apparent absence of gene flow across them. The extent to which these insular populations should be considered different taxonomic entities

remains an open question. Although within this thesis a conservative threshold has been established at 6.8%, other integrative taxonomic studies have implied a broader range of interspecific divergences, ranging from 2-3% (Domènech *et al.* 2022; Řezáč *et al.* 2014) to ca. 10% (Planas & Ribera 2015). More detailed investigation using complementary approaches such as morphological examination of genitalia, morphometric analyses, nuclear genomic analyses, and niche modelling would help to provide a broader perspective of segregation across islands.

Arthropod barcoding: present and future perspectives

Due to a high proportion of endemic species, with many threatened by ongoing climatic change, there is a clear urgency for effective arthropod monitoring within insular settings. To effectively manage and preserve insular biodiversity, reliable information on arthropod inventories is needed. To overcome the taxonomic impediment (Audisio 2017), DNA barcoding stands out as an effective tool to properly identify both known and yet-to-be-described species (Emerson *et al.* 2017, 2022; Hebert & Gregory 2005; Kennedy *et al.* 2020). Recent advances in fast, accessible, and cost-effective methods in obtaining barcodes (e.g., Andújar *et al.* 2022; Arjona *et al.* 2022; Srivathsan *et al.* 2019, 2021) hold much potential for the delivery of large-scale species inventories. However, inventories will only be useful if reference barcodes are available to correctly assign a taxonomic name to each molecular entity.

By applying both traditional Sanger sequencing and a new development in high throughput sequencing using Oxford Nanopore Technology, we have been able to successfully sequence more than 11,000 spider specimens that were grouped into a total of 247 presumed biological species. Currently, 510 spider species inhabit the Canary Islands and 367 are present in, at least, one island that have been sampled within this thesis (Gobierno de Canarias 2023). This means that more than two thirds of those species now have an available reference barcode sequence. The remaining unbarcoded species likely inhabit ecosystems that were not sampled within the context of this thesis. By expanding our sequencing protocol to unsampled habitats and islands, we expect that a reference barcode library of all spider species inhabiting the Canary archipelago is feasible.

The diverse assemblage of Canary Island spiders serves as an example of how barcode reference libraries might be achieved for other arthropod orders within the Canary Islands. Although recent advances in the barcoding of Coleoptera have been accomplished (e.g., Jiménez-García *et al.* 2023; Machado 2022; Schütte *et al.* 2023), many other orders have very limited data for a barcode reference library within the context of the Canary Islands (but also globally). Hyperdiverse and taxonomically neglected groups, the so-called ‘dark taxa’, often account for high values of both abundance and species richness (Srivathsan *et al.* 2023a). However, recent advances (Hartop *et al.* 2022; Meier *et al.* 2023) suggest affordable and effective ways to deal with such groups. By applying multiplex barcoding to a community sample (e.g., a Malaise trap), resulting barcode sequences can be used to cluster specimens into putative species. This reduces the workload for any subsequent morphological examination as only a subset of individuals is needed for morphology-based taxonomic assignment (e.g., 5.1% in Hartop *et al.* 2022; 7% in Meier *et al.* 2023), thus reducing the time-consuming process of identifying thousands of specimens. MinION sequencing has been proven to be fast (Srivathsan *et al.* 2019; Vasilita *et al.* 2023) and cost-effective (Srivathsan *et al.* 2021). Thus, in combination with non-destructive extraction methods, this technology stands as a useful tool for achieving complete reference libraries for the Canary Islands biota, even for ‘dark-taxa’.

Although intense entomological surveys will enhance a reference barcode library, a complete representation of all catalogued species is likely to be both logistically and economically challenging. For inconspicuous taxa or taxa for which there is only limited available taxonomic expertise, it is difficult to assign a barcode reference to a taxonomic species with certainty. Reference library completeness may also be compromised by species rarity (low abundance, low population densities or low site occupancy). In this context, recent advances in DNA sequencing technology have facilitated the use of historical collections stored in natural history collections (museomics) (Raxworthy & Smith 2021). Museomics has been broadly used, not only for sequencing short DNA fragments (Hajibabaei *et al.* 2006; Lozier & Cameron 2009), but also mitogenomes (Guschanski *et al.* 2013; Jin *et al.* 2020) or even complete genomes (Hung *et al.* 2014; van der Valk *et al.* 2019). In order to avoid stored voucher damaging, DNA template can be achieved by using

non-invasive extraction methods (e.g., Andersen & Mills 2012; Cilia *et al.* 2022; Gilbert *et al.* 2007). Thus, future efforts toward complete barcode reference libraries for the arthropods of the Canary Islands are likely to be enhanced by access to historical taxonomic material, such as those within both public and private collections.

Conclusions

1. The sampling and molecular protocol applied in this thesis has proved to be an effective method to quantify spider diversity, and to compare geographic structuring of both communities and genetic variation at different spatial scales: from regional (among islands) to local (among sites within islands) (Chapters I and III).
2. Population genetic structure in spiders and in beetles tends to be higher in non-dispersive lineages, at both archipelago and island scales (Chapter I).
3. Population differentiation and diversification are positively associated, pointing to dispersal limitation as a key factor in both processes (Chapter I).
4. Higher diversification rates in non-dispersive genera is not simply driven by a higher speciation rate, but also it is moderated by higher extinction rates than in dispersive genera (Chapter I).
5. Across all laurel forest sites, species richness and occupancy are significantly higher for ballooning species compared with non-ballooning species. However, there is no significant difference for local species abundance between ballooning and non-ballooning species (Chapter II).
6. Across all laurel forest sites, species richness, abundance and occupancy are significantly higher for specialist species compared with non-specialist species (Chapter II).
7. A positive significant abundance-occupancy relationship was recovered both at archipelago and at island scales. Dispersal ability and niche breadth were recovered as strong predictors of the abundance-occupancy relationship, whereby across all sites for a given level of local abundance, occupancy was greater for ballooning than for non-ballooning species as well as for non-specialist compared with specialist species (Chapter II).
8. A higher species richness was recovered within an open shrubland ecosystem compared to closed forest ecosystem, as well as a higher turnover across sites within the open ecosystem (Chapter III).
9. A higher turnover across sites in the open ecosystem can be explained by higher environmental heterogeneity across sites (Chapter III).
10. There is no evidence for environmental stability promoting higher turnover in the open ecosystem, as there was no significant difference between open and closed ecosystems for the geographic structuring of genetic variation within species (Chapter III).

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Appendix

Additional contributions to the invertebrate fauna in the Canary Islands made by the PhD candidate.

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